

WP3 - Accounting for agroforestry benefits: tools for beneficiaries of agroforestry products and services

Methods to Verify and Account for the Carbon and Soil Health Benefits of Agroforestry

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Executive Summary

The DigitAF research project (July 2022 - June 2026), funded by the European Commission, aims at a high-quality implementation of agroforestry to foster climate change mitigation and adaptation in agriculture and to ensure sustainable management of natural resources. Our goal is to provide the main actor groups with tools, digital tools in particular, capable of meeting their needs. The three actors' groups that are targeted by DigitAF are:

- Policy actors: policymakers and administrations concerned with applying agroforestry-related regulations, at regional, national and European levels, who set the scene for the adoption (or not) of agroforestry.
- Practitioners: farmers, landowners, and by extension, farm advisers playing an active role in designing and managing agroforestry systems and whose choices determine the agronomic, economic, environmental, and social performance at farm-level and beyond.
- Beneficiaries: of agroforestry products and services in the value chain, including wholesalers, retailers, organisations trading the carbon sequestration and biodiversity benefits of agroforestry, and final consumers seeking verification of the benefits of agroforestry in clear and accessible terms.

This report is most relevant for the third stakeholders' group. The first half of the report describes expert-validated methodologies to measure soil health in agroforestry systems. Five Living Lab teams in Czechia, Finland, Germany, Italy, the Netherlands, and the United Kingdom plus two other project partners in Portugal and Spain used a common set of soil sampling approaches to determine the effects of agroforestry on soil health, using protocols decided in DigitAF Milestone 13 "Report on methods for carbon and soil health assessments (den Herder et al., 2024). The measurements included soil bulk density, soil pH, soil organic carbon content, and earthworm abundance, which are four parameters considered in the UKCEH Soil Health Tool (UKCEH, 2024a). The results indicate that the presence or addition of trees generally increased the level of soil organic carbon relative to cropland and grassland values, but the effect was most apparent where the trees had been present for many decades.

The second part of the report contains a validated methodology to predict the effect of agroforestry on net greenhouse gas emissions and carbon sequestration. In this section, selected greenhouse gas collection tools were tested at sites associated with the Living Labs in Czechia, Finland, Germany, Italy, the Netherlands, and the United Kingdom. The examined tools include CARAT, the Farm Carbon Calculator, and the Open Farm Carbon Tracker. These evaluations highlight how digital tools can quantify both emissions and carbon storage, thereby supporting more accurate and transparent reporting along agroforestry value chains. However, their ability to account for agroforestry-specific carbon sequestration varied substantially. Some tools rely on generic allometric factors or IPCC Tier 1 values, which do not reflect species, age, spacing, or management, and lacked species-specific growth curves for many tree types used in agroforestry.

Together, the soil health assessments and GHG tool evaluations demonstrate that agroforestry delivers measurable improvements in soil condition and climate mitigation potential. At the same time, they reveal the need for more accurate, harmonised, and user-friendly digital tools capable of fully capturing agroforestry's contribution to carbon sequestration and low-emission farming.

Strengthening these tools is essential for integrating agroforestry benefits into carbon accounting methodologies, certification schemes, and emerging market mechanisms such as biodiversity credits and nature credits.

1. Introduction

It has been estimated that the food system was responsible for about 34% of the increase in global net man-made GHG emissions in 2015 (Crippa et al., 2021), and that about 70% of those emissions are due to agricultural production or land use change. Globally, industrial intensive agriculture has led to severe land degradation. Soil degradation is an underestimated and neglected problem that threatens agricultural productivity, food security and ecosystem health. Currently about 30-62% of the agricultural land globally is facing some form of degradation (Heinrich-Böll Stiftung, 2024, EU Soil Observatory 2024). Agroforestry offers opportunities for restoring the productive capacity of degraded soils by restoring soil health and for mitigating climate change by reducing greenhouse gas emissions through the storage of carbon in the soil and woody biomass. However, the extent to which agroforestry systems can restore soil health or sequester carbon in particular situations is still difficult to measure in the field. One way to address this is to use models, for instance in the form of a soil health or GHG assessment tool.

Agroforestry can improve soil health through its capacity to enrich soil organic carbon compared to arable monocropping systems and improve soil nutrient availability and soil fertility due to the presence of trees in the system. This, in turn and over time, can enhance soil microbial dynamics resulting in more healthy and productive soils. There are current EU directives to improve soil health, but simple metrics to quantify and capitalise changes in soil health that can be appreciated in value chains are limited. There is substantial interest in the use of digital tools to calculate the role of trees in carbon sequestration, and the use of digital tools to calculate the level of greenhouse gas emissions associated with food and fibre production at a farm- and at a product level.

There are several reasons why tools to support carbon and soil health are important. Two initial reasons are: i) these tools can help farmers to quantify the greenhouse gas and soil health benefits of agroforestry, thus providing an added incentive for adoption of agroforestry and ii) their methods can be used to enhance the incorporation of agroforestry practices in the verification and marketing of greenhouse gas and soil health benefits throughout the value chains of agroforestry products using existing carbon verification tools¹. Two additional reasons are iii) methods to quantify potential benefits of agroforestry can drive economy towards activities that reduce or remove emissions, and iv) reliable foot-printing methods can be used to better inform consumers, creating added value for agroforestry products, thus enhancing value chains of agroforestry products, benefiting producers and increasing consumer satisfaction. On top of these reasons, there are also legal obligations.

For example, in the European Union, the Non-Financial Reporting Directive (Directive 2014/95/EU) requires about 12000 large companies in the EU, including retailers, to disclose information of environmental and social matters (EU, 2014). This includes the level of scope 1, 2, and 3 emissions²,

¹ For a complete description of existing carbon verification and their suitability for agroforestry, please refer to DigitAF D1.5 Policies and MRV methods for carbon farming in the voluntary and statutory sectors

² The Greenhouse Gas Protocol, a partnership between the World Resources Institute (WRI) and the World Business Council for Sustainable Development (WBCSD), is one of the main organisations helping to develop international GHG accounting and reporting standards (GHG Protocol, 2025). It

and many companies have set company targets to reduce the levels of their emissions. Therefore they need assessment tools to evaluate the emissions of their input products, including agroforestry products. Finally, supermarkets play a major role in driving innovation in the food system, laying the foundation of product requirements and standards for producers with their environmental strategies. So they also need assessment methods to quantify greenhouse gas emissions linked with the products that they buy. Hence a pertinent question is how can the effect of agroforestry be included in greenhouse gas assessments?

Therefore, the purpose of this deliverable report is evaluating the suitability for including agroforestry in existing assessment methods, by testing them in real cases to evaluate their usability, and comparing their results with "ground truth" measurements to assess their accuracy. Thus, soil health tools and farm carbon and greenhouse gas calculators were examined in eight Living Lab farms in countries across Europe, namely Czechia, Finland, Germany, Italy, the Netherlands, Portugal, Spain and the United Kingdom. In each Living Lab, a participating farm was selected to carry out a soil health assessment and evaluate a soil health tool (Chapter 2), as well as a range of carbon and greenhouse gas calculators (Chapter 3).

distinguishes between scope 1, 2 and 3 emissions. Scope 1 emissions consist of the organization's direct GHG emissions, scope 2 relates to purchased electricity, and Scope 3 relates to indirect emissions (both down and upstream) (Greenhouse Gas Protocol, 2022).

2. Soil health assessments

2.1. Introduction

Soil and soil organic matter are critical for global society as it provides the water and nutrients required for food and fibre production. Agricultural land covers about 37% of the world's land area (FAO, 2023) and the soils can store high amounts of carbon exerting a large effect on the global climate system. However, it is also the case that a large proportion of our agricultural land is degraded (Heinrich-Böll Stiftung, 2024, EU Soil Observatory 2024).

According to a review by the Soil Science Society of America, the terms soil health and soil quality are often used interchangeably and they can be defined as “the soil's fitness to support crop growth without becoming degraded or otherwise harming the environment” (Karlen et al., 1997). However in the same review the authors also note that soil quality can be viewed in two ways which are i) an inherent characteristic of the soil (which determines its potential) and ii) the ‘health’ of the soil which describes the ability of the soil in meeting that potential (Karlen et al., 1997). Likewise, a review by the Cambridge Institute for Sustainability Leadership (2017) outlined that the three characteristics of a healthy soil were that: i) it is suitable for agricultural production, ii) it is stable or improving in a measurable physical, chemical, or biological property over time, and iii) that it is not adversely impacting its ecosystem.

Possible agricultural measures to improve soil health include minimum or zero tillage, the use of cover crops and green manure, organic farming, mixed farming, conservation agriculture, intercropping and agroforestry (Burgess et al., 2023). Agroforestry offers a promising alternative to enhance soil health, yet empirical, cross-regional evidence using harmonised methods remains limited. Soil health is complex and evaluating it is challenging as it is affected by many biotic and abiotic factors and land management. For this reason, Approaches to determine the effect of agroforestry on soil health face several challenges. Firstly there is the challenge of the diversity of agroforestry systems (den Herder et al 2017) . The second challenge is the selection of appropriate indicators which can capture the impact of diverse agroforestry management practices on soil health.

Doran and Zeiss (2000) have argued that indicators of soil health should ideally be easy and inexpensive to measure, be responsive to management, and be interpretable by land managers. Liptzin et al. (2022) argue that measurement of soil organic carbon is often the basis for soil health assessment. However other potential indicators include compactness (or bulk density), acidity, salinity, and a measure of biodiversity. In order to address the challenge posed by the diversity of agroforestry systems, we included in our analysis eight contrasting agroforestry systems across Europe.

Across the eight sites, a consistent four parameters of soil health were measured, which are also required within the UKCEH Soil Health Tool (UKCEH, 2024a). The four parameters are the level of soil organic matter (or soil organic carbon), the level of acidity (pH, in water and KCl), the soil bulk density, and the number of earthworms (Table 1). A step-by-step guide is provided on the [website](#) to explain how the four measurements can be taken (UKCEH, 2024b). On the website, the results from an individual site can then be compared with the national distribution of the same properties for soils of the same type, land use, and rainfall amount.

Table 1. Soil characteristics and specific instructions given by the UKCEH Soil Health Tool (UKCEH, 2024b).

Soil characteristic	Specific instructions
Soil organic matter	Litter and stubble should not be included Bulk sample (0-15 cm) produced from 25 locations across the field
pH	Bulk sample (0-15 cm) produced from 25 locations across the field
Soil bulk density (g cm ⁻³)	Advice is to seek professional help.
Earthworms (per 8000 cm ³)	At 5-10 points across a field, a pit of 20 cm x 20 cm x 20 cm should be dug and placed on a plastic sheet. Count and record the number of earthworms

Measurements of the effect of agroforestry on soil health parameters were completed in the eight sites following a common protocol (Aynekulu et al., 2026, annexed to this report). However in some sites, the protocol was modified to accommodate the differences in agroforestry system design, soil type, and in some cases to allow direct comparisons with previous measurements. Hence the detailed sampling protocols are described for each of the eight sites. All soil data will be available on Zenodo and accessible via the DigitAF Agroforestry Data Catalogue (DigitAF, 2026) before the end of the project.

2.2. Czechia

Two silvoarable agroforestry case studies were selected for the examination of soil health in Czechia: one in Central Bohemia and one in the South Moravia region.

2.2.1. Site description

Site 1: Jagava Farm near Veselice is located in Central Bohemia, in undulating landscape (slopes 3-7°) with moderately warm and humid climate (Table 2; Figure 1); the prevailing soil type is brown soil with moderate fertility. The farmer follows organic practices and seeks to farm in harmony with nature, and to restore the farm through the practice of increasing soil organic matter with the intention to increase soil water retention and buffer the effects of climate change. An objective is maintaining crop cover throughout the year as this reduces the creation of heat islands. The aim of creating several new woody elements on the farm was to reduce wind and water erosion of the soil, to capture water, accumulate nutrients, and to provide shade and increased biodiversity. The usual crop rotation in alley cropping AFS is vegetable, potatoes, cereals and cover/catch crops.

Table 2. Characterisation data of the two sites | Czechia at Jagava Farm and Gregorovič Farm.

Parameters	Czech Site 1 Jagava farm (40 ha)	Czech Site 2, Gregorovič farm (200 ha)
Coordinates	50.3966 N, 15.1268 E	48.9818N, 17.0383E
Altitude	350 m asl	180-230 m asl
Farm type	Arable	Arable
Production system/s	Organic	Organic
Agroforestry system in place	Yes	Yes
Soil type	Brown soil	Chernozems
Average annual rainfall	550-650 mm	550-600 mm
Average annual temperature	8°C	7-9°C

a)

b)

c)

Figure 1. Jagava Farm: a) aerial view of agroforestry field (drone). b) picture of fruit tree and cropped alley, c) picture of hedges on the edge of the field aerial and ground-based photographs showing the alley cropping agroforestry system.

Site 2: Gregorovič Farm is located near the village of Šardice (Figure 2) in the Kyjovská Pahorkatina Hills in south-eastern Czechia. It is an area known for lignite mining, and the landscape is characterized by gently undulating terrain. The mean annual rainfall and temperature at the site is broadly similar to that at Site 1 (Table 2). The climate and soil conditions are considered to provide favourable conditions for arable farming and viticulture, with limited areas of forests. From a geological perspective, the area is part of the Outer Western Carpathians and loess deposits form the basis for highly fertile soils. The dominant soil types are chernozems (which are degraded in places), which are deep, well-structured, and rich in organic matter. The soils at the site are characterised by medium to high infiltration rates, but they are susceptible to erosion on sloping terrain. The agroforestry system was established in 2010 (originally as “biobelts”), later with plantations of plum trees (*Prunus domestica*) that became and “intensive orchards” and “other orchards” in terms of agro-environmental measures. The agroforestry system is an alley cropping system with 48 m between tree strips (15 m wide). Crops farmed include a rotation of cereals (wheat), rape seed, and cover crops. Both arable land and “orchards” are in cultivated organically (Figure 3).

Figure 2. Location of agroforestry system under monitoring near the municipality of Šardice.

Figure 3. Appearance of the agroforestry site at the Gregorovič farm.

2.2.2. Sampling design and measurements

On Jagava Farm, soil sampling was carried out in a silvoarable field with an alley cropping design of 18 m between tree strip and 2 m wide tree strips (Figure 4), where tree alleys were established 8-10 years ago. The tree alleys were planted along the slope contour (East-West direction) mainly with productive fruit trees (e.g. walnut, chestnut, cherry, rosehip, dogwood, hawthorn) and berries (gooseberries, currants, raspberries). Arable alleys are cropped annually with vegetables, potatoes, beans and various cover crops.

Figure 4. Soil sampling design showing the three transects on Jagava Farm near Veselice.

The soil samples were collected on 15 May 2025 in three transects (A, B, C) perpendicular to the beginning, middle and end of a tree alley (Figure 4), and spaced about 60 m apart. Seven soil samples were derived from each transect: i) in the centre of tree alley (point zero), ii) on both sides of the alley (North and South) to the crop alleys at distances of 1 m (edge), 3 m and 9 m (middle of crop alley) from the trees. At each sampling point, soil samples were taken using Kopecky cylinders (for estimating bulk density) at two depths, 0-15 cm and 15-30 cm. From the subsoil layer below 30 cm only samples for estimating C content were collected, not for measuring bulk density. As a control, samples were also taken in the same way from three sampling points that were randomly selected in a neighbouring open field. All samples were dried, sieved at 2 mm sieve and send to the soil laboratory of the Research Institute for Landscape in Brno, Czechia.

On the Gregorovič Farm near Šardice, soil samples were also collected using a transect design perpendicular to the tree strips, (strips A, B, C) at the upper, middle, and lower parts of the slope (Figure 5). On the Gregorovič Farm, sampling locations compared soil under the tree, soil in the grassed strips (at two distances, 2.5 m and 5 m from the tree), soil at the edge of the strip (but already in the arable cropping area), and soil in the arable cropping area (in the middle of the alleys). As a control, sampling locations were placed in the centre of open arable fields south of the agroforestry field. Samples were taken from four depths, 0-10, 10-20, 20-40, and 40-60 cm. The samples were analysed for total and organic carbon. Bulk density values were derived from existing soil analyses completed at an earlier date.

Figure 5. Sampling design on the Gregorovič Farm in Šardice: tree (under tree), grass strip (2.5 m and 5 m from the tree), edge (7.5 m from the tree, already in arable area), and field (in the middle of arable cropping area).

At each site, soil bulk density was determined using a steel cylinder of 5 cm diameter and 10 cm height (i.e. volume 196.35 cm³). The undisturbed soil sample was then sieved to 2 mm and oven-dried for 24 hours until constant mass was reached. The level of soil acidity was determined in terms of the pH in water. Since the two sites contained inorganic carbon (CaCO₃), organic carbon was determined using the thermal differentiation method where the soil is subjected to a temperature up to 400°C (DIN Media, 2016) using a Microelementar Analyser Elementar SoliTOC Cube. The soil carbon stock was determined from the soil organic carbon contents and the bulk densities.

The soil carbon stock was calculated following Equation 1:

$$\text{Soil carbon stock (to depth } d) = BD \times \text{SOC} \times d \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

where *BD* is the bulk density, *SOC* is the soil organic carbon content, and *d* is the soil depth.

For the Czechia results, the statistical analysis of the results was completed using Microsoft Excel with soil depth, distance from tree, and North/South orientation taken as the main independent variables.

2.2.3. Results

Jagava Farm

At Jagava Farm, the soil organic carbon (SOC) content was substantially influenced by all independent variables – soil depth, distance from the tree row and orientation (Figure 6). As expected, the SOC is decreasing with soil depth, however there is a higher decrease in the control plot than in alley cropping AFS. The highest and significant SOC was measured right in the centre of the tree strip (AF0) at all depths, with substantial decrease with increasing distance from the tree strip. However, we also

found significantly higher SOC content in lower-top horizon (15-30 cm), even with increasing distance from the tree alley compared to the control plot. Those differences are especially visible in the northern orientation (up the slope) of the transect, where at the distance of 3 m, we measured the highest SOC in the depth of 15-30 cm.

Figure 6. Soil organic carbon content for a) south, b) north, and c) the mean transect orientation for different depths and distances from the tree row (AF0,1,3,9 with the distance from tree row in m and the control plot (CTL), at Jagava Farm.

Figure 7. Soil organic carbon stock within two depth increments in the a) south, b) north, and c) the mean alley in terms of depth and distance from the tree row in metres (AF0, AF1, AF3, AF9) and the control plot (CTL), at Jagava Farm.

The soil organic carbon stock followed the same pattern as the soil organic content (Figure 7). In general, a higher soil organic carbon stock was found in the tree rows than in the cropped alleys, and the control. There was also indication of a transect orientation, where in the north (up-slope) transect the SOC stock was comparable between tree and crop alleys.

Gregorovič Farm

The soil carbon analysis for Gregorovič Farm allowed the separate calculation of the thermally labile fraction of organic carbon (TOC400) and thermally stable/recalcitrant carbon (ROC). Together the two values give the total carbon content (%) (Figure 8). The highest soil carbon was found within the grass strips with trees at all depths (Figure 8). When the results were expressed as a soil carbon stock, the highest carbon content was also found in the tree rows (Figure 9).

Figure 8. Stable/recalcitrant carbon (ROC) and labile organic carbon (TOC400) - together total organic carbon for specific locations (trees/grassland/edge/field/control) and soil layer (0-10 cm; 10-20 cm; 20-40 cm; 40-60 cm), at Gregorovič Farm.

Figure 9. Stock of stable/recalcitrant carbon (ROC) and labile organic carbon (TOC400) (0-60 cm depth) for specific distances from the tree row, in the field and in the control area at Gregorovič Farm.

2.2.4. Discussion

As expected, the soil organic content (SOC) decreased with increasing soil depth. At both the Jagava and Gregorovič farms, the soil organic carbon levels and the soil carbon stocks were higher under the areas with permanent vegetation (tree strips with grass) compared to the cultivated areas, with the edge (field) variant representing an intermediate condition. These higher levels of carbon can be related to the presence of non-disturbed perennial woody and non-woody vegetation, with deep root systems in those tree strips.

In the cropped alleys, we cannot see the influence of trees on SOC in the topsoil, as this soil is annually tilled, however on Jagava Farm in Veselice, we found a positive influence of trees in lower soil horizons (below 15 cm), in all distances from tree alleys, compared to the control. This is especially pronounced in the northern orientation of the transects, on the higher end of the slope, which can be caused by reduced erosion and the accumulation of organic matter above the tree alleys.

The tree strips exhibited the highest content of soil carbon and carbon stocks across soil depths. This reflects the long-term inputs of organic matter from litterfall and root biomass, limited soil disturbance, and enhanced stabilization of organic carbon. However, there was a decline of carbon content with depth. The grass tree strips also showed elevated carbon content and carbon stocks, particularly in the upper soil layers. Dense root systems and continuous organic matter inputs contribute to soil carbon accumulation, although total stocks remained slightly lower than under trees. Nevertheless, grass tree strips soils stored substantially more carbon than arable soils, highlighting their role as effective carbon reservoirs.

The edge (field) locations displayed intermediate carbon contents and carbon stocks. Values were clearly higher than in the interior of the arable cropped area but lower than in tree and grassland locations. This pattern indicates a pronounced edge effect, where proximity to permanent (woody and/or grassland) vegetation reduces disturbance intensity and enhances organic matter inputs, partially mitigating carbon losses typical of arable management. The field area had the lowest carbon content and carbon stocks, especially in surface horizons. Intensive soil cultivation together with erosion and reduced organic matter return promote rapid mineralization and carbon depletion, resulting in limited carbon storage.

Overall, the results demonstrate that permanent vegetation substantially enhances soil carbon storage and stability. The ranking (from higher to lower) of treatments for both carbon content and carbon stocks is consistent: tree > grassland > edge (field) > field, and the total carbon stocks of edges is close and comparable to that of the grass strips. These findings underline the importance of integrating trees, grasslands, and vegetated edges (i.e. "landscape features") into agricultural landscapes to improve soil quality and increase long-term carbon sequestration potential.

2.3. Finland

2.3.1. Site description

The Finnish farm Sammallahti, is located in the region of North Karelia in Eastern Finland. The landscape is characterised by gently sloping low hills and dominated by boreal coniferous and mixed forests and lakes. In the more fertile areas farming takes place, mainly livestock farming or grass/silage production. The area has a continental climate with cold winters and cool summers. The average annual temperature is 4.0°C (Liperi weather station) with an approximate 747 mm average annual precipitation (Table 3).

Table 3. Characterisation data of the Finnish farm.

Parameters	Information
Coordinates	62.589315 N, 29.234567 E
Farm type	Livestock
Farm size	13.24 ha
Production system/s	Organic
Agroforestry system in place	Yes
Soil type	Sand moraine - clay
Average annual rainfall	747 mm
Average annual temperature	4°C

The soil cover in the area is mainly represented by aluminium and iron humus soils (Podzols); thin soils (Leptosols) are widespread. Characteristic morphological features of soils are relatively shallow profiles, high stone content, and underlying by hard bedrock with fine earth material in crevices between large boulders. Soils in the area generally have high carbon and low nitrogen content, which points to unfavourable conditions of organic matter transformation (Medvedeva et al. 2018).

The soil on the farm is sand moraine (Mr RT) in forested areas and clay (Sa RT) on grasslands (Finnish Geological Survey 2025). Before the establishment of the farm, slash-and-burn cultivation was a common practice in Finland and particularly in eastern Finland this was practised at a large scale (Delgado Matas 2004).

The farm was established more than 100 years ago for livestock farming. The farming gradually changed from traditional to more intensive farming until livestock farming was abandoned about 20 years ago. The new generation took over the farm about 15 years ago, revived the business, took up sheep farming and restored the wood pastures. Since then, the wood pastures have been grazed by sheep. The area covered by permanent grass is grazed by sheep and cattle and does not have tree cover, but some woody elements are present as forest islands. The surrounding forests are about 100 years old. About 100 years ago forest cover was much lower in the area and in some places there was no forest cover at all (Figure 10), mainly because of the exploitation of the forest resources for slash-and-burn cultivation, ship building and tar production. Forests started growing back after wooden ship building was replaced by steel, and slash-and-burn cultivation was abandoned with the arrival of synthetic fertiliser.

a) Around 1890

b) 2024

Figure 10. Siikakoski rapids near Sammallahti farm a) around 1890 and b) 2024. Forest cover was much lower in Finland at the turn of the 19th and 20th centuries.

To explore the effects of agroforestry management on soil health, soil samples were taken in three different fields with different management treatments: permanent grass (grazed), forest grazing/wood pasture (grazed), forest (ungrazed) (Figure 11, Table 4).

Table 4. Overview of the three ‘treatments’ for comparison.

Treatment	Trees	Understorey management
Permanent grassland (PG)	No trees	Grazed by sheep and cattle
Silvopasture: Forest grazing and wood pasture (FG)	100+ year old mixed pine forest. The southeastern part of the parcel is a more open wood pasture with birch and juniper	Sheep grazing: No understorey management in the forest. In the wood pasture shrub clearance to keep the area under the power lines open.
Forest (FO)	Mixed pine forest (about 60 yrs)	Commercial forest management

2.3.2. Sampling design and measurements

To explore the effects of agroforestry management on soil health, soil samples were taken in three treatments using a stratified random sampling design: permanent grass (grazed), forest grazing/wood pasture (grazed), forest (ungrazed) (Figure 11, Table 5). Sampling took place between 26 May and 2 June 2025. In each treatment 10 points were sampled. For the permanent grass, two fields were sampled separately because of a difference in grazing regime. At the time of sampling, the first field (sampling points 0-9) was mainly grazed by sheep. The second field (sampling point 16-24) was mainly grazed by cows, although this grazing regime was not applied consistently in preceding years, and according to the farmer both fields were grazed by both sheep and cows. Due to time constraints, in both the grazed forest (sample 25-34) and the forest (sample 41-50) only ten samples were taken instead of the 15 initially planned as indicated in the map (Figure 11).

Bulk density was measured once at each sample point of each treatment. A steel cylinder of 5 cm diameter and 10 cm height (i.e. volume 196.35 cm³) was inserted in the soil. An undisturbed soil sample was collected, sieved to 2 mm and sun-dried for two weeks until constant mass was reached. The bulk density was measured at two different depths, at 0-20 cm and at 20-40 cm. The bulk density

is equal to the ratio of the soil sample's dry mass divided by its volume and is expressed in grams per cubic centimetre (g cm^{-3}).

Table 5. Characteristics and location of the sampling plots.

Treatment	Area (ha)	Stocking density (LU ha^{-1})	Tree species	Tree age	Tree density (trees ha^{-1})
Permanent grassland	4	1.68	-	NA	0
	1.26	1.68	-	NA	0
Forest grazing	3.98	0.11	Pine, spruce, birch, alder	100+	92
Forest	4	-	Pine, spruce, birch	60	160

At each sampling point, five sub-samples were taken. One in the centre, and on sample towards the north, south, east and west direction. After sampling, samples were divided in two different depths, at 0-20 cm and 20-40 cm. For the pH, Carbon and Nitrogen analysis, the five sub-samples were mixed in a bucket and analysed as one, to form a composite sample of topsoil (0-20 cm) and subsoil (20-40 cm) using the composite sampling strategy used in the LUCAS guidelines (Orgiazzi et al. 2018). Samples were taken with an auger with a diameter of 2.4 cm and a length of 40 cm. For each composite sample, aliquots of 10g of soil were ground in a ball mill and then analysed in the DUMATHERM® N Pro analyser (C. Gerhardt GmbH & Co. Germany) to determine %C (SOC) and %N (TN). The soil carbon stock was calculated using the same Equation 1 as used in the Czechia study.

Figure 11. Location of the sampling plots for the Finnish site; PG = permanent grass, FG = forest grazing/wood pasture, FO = forest (ungrazed).

Measurements of earthworm numbers were taken from soil cores of 20 cm x 20 cm x 20 cm, excavated with a spade, and placed on a plastic tray and hand sorted. Worms were counted in the field and the fresh weight was recorded in the laboratory.

2.3.3. Results

2.3.3.1. Soil organic carbon, nitrogen, pH and bulk density

All sites were characterised by strongly acid (pH 5.1-5.5) or very strongly acid soils (<4.5-5.0) (Table 6). The pH was very low in all sites, and in the topsoil layer (0-20 cm) it ranged from pH 3.35 (extreme pH for acid peat and acid sulphate soils) in forest to pH 5.05 (strongly acid) in permanent grassland according to the HCL method. The subsoil layers (20-40 cm) had similar low pH as the topsoil layers. Similar to the HCL method, the H₂O method resulted in very similar low pH at all sites.

Soil bulk density was higher in the subsoil layer (20-40 cm) as compared to topsoil layer (0-20 cm). Soil bulk density was highest in grassland (1.18 g cm⁻³ at 20-40 cm) and lowest in the grazed forest (0.38

g cm⁻³ at 0-20 cm). The percentage of nitrogen and soil organic carbon were highest in the topsoil layer (0-20 cm) in the grazed forest, resulting in 0.92% of nitrogen and 13.66% of carbon. Carbon stocks were also highest in the grazed forest with almost 94 tonnes of C ha⁻¹ in the topsoil layer and 58 tonnes of C ha⁻¹ in the subsoil layer (Table 6). In forest sites the carbon stock was about 61 tonnes of C ha⁻¹ (0-20 cm) and in permanent grassland it ranged from 54 to 67 tonnes of C ha⁻¹ in the topsoil and from 37 to 58 tonnes of C ha⁻¹ in the subsoil.

Table 6. Mean results for pH, bulk density, nitrogen, soil organic carbon, and soil carbon stock at soil depths of 0-20 cm and 20-40 cm, in two permanent grasslands (grazed by sheep or cows), one grazed forest, and an ungrazed forest site. Numbers in parenthesis indicate the standard error of the mean.

Treatment	Depth (cm)	pH		Bulk density (g cm ⁻³)	N (%)	C (%)	C stocks (t C ha ⁻¹)
		pH/H ₂ O	pH/HCl				
Permanent grass (sheep)	0-20	5.10 (0.08)	5.05 (0.13)	0.95 (0.04)	0.35 (0.03)	3.67 (0.53)	66.87 (7.18)
	20-40	5.28 (0.11)	4.89 (0.10)	1.18 (0.07)	0.28 (0.04)	2.8 (0.76)	57.76 (11.16)
Permanent grass (cows)	0-20	5.06 (0.04)	5.08 (0.08)	1.03 (0.04)	0.28 (0.03)	2.74 (0.44)	54.00 (5.91)
	20-40	5.18 (0.04)	4.98 (0.12)	1.17 (0.07)	0.21 (0.02)	1.71 (0.27)	37.43 (4.12)
Grazed forest (n=10)	0-20	3.83 (0.12)	3.39 (0.09)	0.38 (0.04)	0.92 (0.10)	13.66 (1.70)	93.66 (7.97)
	20-40	3.82 (0.21)	3.71 (0.08)	0.67 (0.05)	0.35 (0.08)	4.50 (1.07)	57.91 (19.86)
Forest (n=10)	0-20	3.80 (0.07)	3.35 (0.06)	0.60 (0.08)	0.60 (0.05)	11.11 (0.96)	61.38 (11.97)
	20-40	-	-	-	-	-	-

2.3.3.2. Earthworms

The number of earthworms found ranged from 0 in forest to 3.2 (SE ± 0.73) in the permanent grass grazed by sheep (Figure 12). Permanent grass grazed by cows had on average 2.5 (SE ± 0.83) individuals per sample, and grazed forest had on average 1.2 (SE ± 0.66) individuals per sample.

Figure 12. Earthworm abundance (mean number per soil core (20 x 20 x 20 cm, 8 dm³) and standard error of the mean) in two permanent grasslands (grazed by sheep or cows), grazed forest and ungrazed forest sites.

2.3.4. Discussion

The results at the Finnish site are discussed in terms of comparison with the UKCEH dataset and other data.

Bulk density

The measured bulk densities in the permanent grass areas were substantially higher than in the grazed and ungrazed forest areas (Table 7) and the lower bulk densities of forested soils was also evident in the distribution of bulk densities reported for forested sites in the UKCEH dataset (Table 7, Figure 13).

Table 7. Measured bulk density (0-20 cm) for the four land covers at Sammallahti farm compared to UKCEH dataset values for two land covers on medium loamy textured soils.

Measured soil bulk density (g cm^{-3})				UKCEH bulk density (g cm^{-3})	
Permanent grass (sheep)	Permanent grass (cattle)	Grazed forest	Ungrazed forest	Improved grassland	Coniferous woodland
0.95	1.03	0.38	0.35	<0.6	<0.1
				1.1	0.4
				>1.3	>0.8

a) Improved grassland on medium loamy textured soils (annual rainfall = 747 mm)

b) Coniferous woodland on medium loamy textured soils (annual rainfall = 747 mm)

Figure 13. Comparison of the measured bulk density (0-20 cm) with the distribution for a) an improved grassland and b) a coniferous woodland on medium loamy textured soils in the UK with an annual rainfall of 747 mm.

Soil acidity

The forest soils at Sammallahti farm were more acidic than the permanent grassland areas, and this matches the UKCEH dataset which suggests that (in the UK), forested areas tend to be associated more with acidic soils than permanent grass (Table 8; Figure 14).

Table 8. Measured pH values (0-20 cm) for the four land covers at Sammallahti farm compared to UKCEH dataset values for two land covers on medium loamy textured soils.

Measured soil pH				UKCEH pH		
Permanent grass (sheep)	Permanent grass (cattle)	Grazed forest	Ungrazed forest		Improved grassland	Coniferous woodland
5.1	5.1	3.4	3.4	Below typical	<5.0	<3.8
				Mid-point	6.2	4.3
				Above typical	>8.1	>5.1

a) Improved grassland on medium loamy textured soils (annual rainfall = 747 mm)

b) Coniferous woodland on medium loamy textured soils (annual rainfall = 747 mm)

Figure 14. Comparison of the measured pH compared with the UKCEH (2022) soil dataset for a) improved grassland and b) coniferous woodland on medium loamy textured soils (annual rainfall = 747 mm).

Soil organic carbon and organic matter

In our study, especially in the grazed forests, the percentage of soil organic carbon (13.7% in 0-20 cm topsoil) and total carbon stock (93.7 tonnes of C ha⁻¹; 0-20 cm) were high. For comparison, mineral soils in Finland generally contain between 41 and 67 t C ha⁻¹ (0-15 cm) depending on management, soil type and region (Heikkinen et al. 2013). Although we observed a high soil carbon stock at a site in Eastern Finland, the highest regional soil C stocks are in the west and the lowest stocks in the in the east of the country according to the Finnish National Soil Inventory (Heikkinen et al. 2013).

At the case study site, the soil organic carbon (0-20 cm) was higher in the grazed (13.7%) than the ungrazed forests (11.1%). One potential reason for this could be the increased biomass turnover due to sheep grazing, digesting and defecating in the grazed areas. However the effect of grazing on soil carbon content is affected by the grazing intensity, while moderate or light grazing maintaining or slightly improving it, and high intensity grazing leading to reductions (Hao 2024).

The soil organic matter was in excess of 5% at all of the sites in Finland (Table 9). One reason for this is the very acidic soils, typical for podsol soils in the boreal coniferous forest zone, which limits the activity of soil microorganisms (Malik et al. 2018, Medvedeva et al. 2018). Other studies show that moderate acidity (pH 4.2-6.5) can enhance microbial activity and carbon sequestration pathways, creating complex interactions (Liu et al. 2025).

Table 9. Measured soil organic content values (0-20 cm) for the four land covers at Sammallahti farm compared to UKCEH dataset values for two land covers on medium loamy textured soils.

Permanent grass (sheep)	Soil organic matter (%)				UKCEH soil organic matter (%)	
	Permanent grass (cattle)	Grazed forest	Ungrazed forest		Improved grassland	Coniferous woodland
7.34	5.48	27.32	22.22	Below typical	<6.0	<5.8
				Mid-point	7.2	14.2
				Above typical	>17.4	>56.7

A potential reason for the high soil carbon stocks could be the practice of slash-and burn-cultivation in eastern Finland, including at Sammallahti farm (Antti Mutanen, pers. comm.). Although slash-and-burn cultivation ceased to be practised during 1890-1920 in Finland, it still may have a residual effect. One study from Koli National Park in Finland (Delgado Matas, 2004), where slash-and-burn cultivation is still practised on one hectare every year even nowadays to keep this cultural heritage alive, reports a soil organic matter content (without reporting the sampling depth) of 50 t ha⁻¹ in old slash-and-burn areas, and 59 t ha⁻¹ in recent slash-and-burn areas. However, many studies from tropical climates on small-scale slash-and-burn cultivation in forests temporarily cleared for small-holder agriculture reported a loss of soil organic carbon after burning (e.g. García-Oliva et al. 1999, Bieluczyk et al. 2025). Probably there can be differences between the tropics and northern climates in the intensity of burning and the amount of incompletely burned woody biomass and charcoal left after burning. In Finland, slash-and-burn cultivation is generally low-intensity and large amounts of incompletely burned wood or charcoal are left on the site which can turn into a long-lasting carbon storage. The effect of grazing and slash-and-burn cultivation on carbon stocks in northern climates would be an

interesting topic for future research as it could provide important information on the preservation of long-lasting carbon stocks.

The typical range for soil organic matter of the UKCEH distribution curve for medium loamy textured soils on improved grassland and a rainfall of 747 mm is between 6.0 and 17.4% SOM. For coniferous woodland with the same soil type and rainfall, the mid-point is 14.5%, with lower and upper 10% values of 5.8% and 56.7% respectively (Table 9). Unfortunately, because measured soil organic matter values were not available, to enable an initial comparison we assumed that the soil organic matter was twice the soil organic carbon level. On this basis, for both permanent grass and coniferous forest, the assumed indicative soil organic matter was within the typical range what could be expected for medium loamy textured soils (Figure 15).

a) Improved grassland on medium loamy textured soils (annual rainfall = 747 mm)

b) Coniferous woodland on medium loamy textured soils (annual rainfall = 747 mm)

Figure 15. Comparison of the assumed soil organic matter (0-15 cm) compared with the distribution for a) improved grassland and b) coniferous woodland medium loamy textured soils with an annual rainfall of 747 mm.

Earthworms

The number of earthworms recorded at the permanent grass was substantially lower than reported in the UKCEH dataset for a similar soil type and rainfall (Table 10, Figure 16). The level of earthworms in the forest were also lower than indicated in the UKCEH dataset for broadleaf woodlands (no data were provided for coniferous woodlands in the UK). The Finnish grazed and ungrazed forest sites were

a mixed coniferous-broadleaved forest. A possible reason for the low numbers in the forest area is the very high acidity e.g. low pH. Earthworms prefer moist, organic-rich soils, decaying leaf litter and compost, and avoid dry or acidic conditions.

Table 10. Measured earthworm abundance for the four land covers at Sammallahhti farm compared to UKCEH dataset values for two land covers on medium loamy textured soils.

Earthworm abundance (number (8 dm) ⁻³)				UKCEH earthworm abundance ((number (8 dm) ⁻³)		
Permanent grass (sheep)	Permanent grass (cattle)	Grazed forest	Ungrazed forest	Improved grassland	Coniferous woodland	
3.2	2.5	1.2	0	<3.4	<1.7	
				Mid-point	17.0	4.4
				Above typical	>36.4	>15.3

a) Improved grassland on medium loamy textured soils (annual rainfall = 747 mm)

b) Broadleaved and mixed woodland on medium loamy textured soils (annual rainfall = 747 mm)

Figure 16. Comparison of the measured number of earthworms (20 x 20 x 20 cm) compared with the distribution for a) improved grassland and b) broadleaf woodland on medium loamy textured soils in the UK, with an annual rainfall of 747 mm.

2.4. Germany

Methods to verify and account for the carbon and soil health benefits of agroforestry were evaluated at Domin's Farm Peickwitz, located in the DigtAF Living Lab Brandenburg (Germany). Two sites were examined for soil carbon and soil health; a silvoarable plot and a silvopastoral plot (Figure 17).

2.4.1. Site description

The family-run farm is managed conventionally on a total acreage of 370 ha, comprised of 50 ha of grassland and 320 ha of arable land. Of this, 130 ha are remote on lease land of restored mining areas. The farm also includes 50 ha of forest (typically pine), 30 suckler cows, 30-40 fattening pigs, 200 poultry (geese and ducks), and approximately 50 laying hens (see farm characteristics in Cumplido-Marin et al. 2023 for further details).

The farm is located in the "Lusatian Urstromtal" (glacial outwash valley) characterized by sandy glacial and fluvioglacial sediments with a light texture (coarse sand), low water holding capacity, low natural fertility and soils are often acidic (Table 11). The climate is moderately dry with pronounced summer droughts in recent years. The arable land of the farm is characterised by a comparatively low yield levels; expressed in a German-based yield factor of approx. 22 out of 100 points, corresponding to the least productive zones in Germany.

Table 11. Characterisation data of the German case study farm.

Parameters	Information
Coordinates	51.4636 N, 13.9819 E
Farm type	Mixed farm
Farm size	370 ha
Production system/s	Conventional
Agroforestry system in place	Yes
Soil type	Sandy podzols
Average annual rainfall	737 mm
Average annual temperature	10.2°C

As the first agroforestry operation at Domin's Farm Peickwitz started in March 2015, with an initial farm area of about 40 ha dedicated to agroforestry. Tree species include alder (*Alnus* sp.), poplar (*Populus* sp.), willow (*Salix* sp.) and black locust (*Robinia pseudoacacia*) planted in strips on a field to the West of the farm that was at risk of wind erosion. In subsequent years the agroforestry was extended and new tree species such as black alder (*Alnus glutinosa*), sweet chestnut (*Castanea sativa*), wild pear (*Pyrus pyraster*), field maple (*Acer campestre*) and tree hazel (*Corylus colurna*) as well as shrubs such as common rock pear (*Amelanchier rotundifolia*) and elderberry (*Sambucus nigra*) were added.

a) Silvoarable system with short rotation coppice with poplar (Photo: R. Hübner).

b) Silvopastoral system with willow and alder (Photo: R. Hübner).

c) Overview on the living lab farm in Germany with sampled agroforestry systems (Photo: T. Domin).

Figure 17. Images of the a) silvoarable and b) silvopastoral system of the Living Lab farm at Peickwitz, together with c) an aerial photo of the farm showing the location of the agroforestry systems.

Silvoarable AFS: the soil type prevailing in the first 30 cm was identified as loamy sand according to the Soil Mapping Guidelines (Sponagel, 2005) and according to Wulffen et al. (2008) the soil can be assigned to soil group 2. There is slightly silty sand at a depth of 30 to 60 cm becoming sand at a depth of 60 to 100 cm. The average depth to groundwater is about 1.8 m. The typical crop rotation for the field crops is forage rye (year 1), oats (year 2), and winter rye (year 3). The tree component is primarily poplar, planted in Spring 2015:

- R1: 0.777 ha of poplar planted in 2015, comprised of five rows 2.7 m x 1.0 m tree spacing to the East and five rows poplar to the West, 2.7 m x 0.5 m spacing;
- R2: 0.423 ha with five rows poplar, 2.7 m x 0.5 m tree spacing;
- R3: 0.152 ha of a poplar-hardwood combi-system planted in 2020. Subplots are:
 - one row of hybrid poplar (*Populus x canadensis*) to the East (0.076 ha)
 - one row with groups of three value wood trees: sweet chestnut (*Castanea sativa*), field maple (*Acer campestre*), and Turkish hazel (*Corylus colurna*) at a 1.5 m distance within the group, intermitted by 5 m of shrub species copper rock pear (*Amelanchier lamarckii*), elderberry (*Sambucus nigra*), (0,076 ha), and another row of poplar to the West (0.152 ha).

Silvopastoral AFS: this comprises a grazed meadow used to provide shade and potentially fodder from the trees for the grazing herd of cows. In the plot, two strips with poplar and alder were planted in March 2016 with trees in four blocks per strip. Besides choosing two tree species, the experimental planting design was chosen to evaluate the effect of ploughing, thus some blocks were ploughed before planting of the trees, while some of the planting was undertaken without prior soil preparation.

2.4.2. Sampling design and measurements

Silvoarable AFS

The silvoarable agroforestry area has been sampled three times. The first sampling campaign took place 2016 in the AUFWERTEN project and was conducted by Julia Rieken (2017). In the second sampling campaign in April 2025 in the DIGITAF project, the same approximate location were revisited, as metal sticks marked the initial transects, but including additional intermediate samples at 6 m and 24 m. An additional third soil sampling campaign took place in October 2025 to collect probes to determine biological activity (Figure 18).

a) Locations of soil sampling campaign 1 in 2020 along eight transects, blue dots mark the soil samples (Rieken, 2017).

b) Location of soil sampling campaign 2 spring 2025 and campaign 3 autumn 2025 along four transects T1 to T4 (Google Maps and Airbus, 2025).

Figure 18. Soil sampling locations in the silvoarable agroforestry at Domin's Farm Peickwitz (orientation North, not for scale).

Soil samples in the top 30 cm were derived from four transects (T1 to T4) in the silvoarable agroforestry in April 2025 and October 2025 following the protocol of Minarsch et al. (2022). Since the initial measurements, a new agroforestry strip (R3) was added to the system. A stepwise hole was dug out with a spade and three soil samples with cylinders (100 cm³) at a depth of 15 and 25 cm. GPS coordinates of each sampling location were recorded using a Garmin device. Additionally, at each location two cylinders of soil was collected to analyse the biological activity in the soil. All 44 samples were transported to the Czech Landscape Research Institute VUK in a mobile refrigerator the following day.

Silvopastoral AFS

Previous soil sampling had taken place at the silvopastoral site on 25-26 November 2015 and on 23 March 2016 by Michael Kanzler, formerly at BTU Cottbus-Senftenberg. The dried probes were recovered from the BTU archives by DeFAF (Figure 19a). Four push cores samples per profile and depth level (0-10, 10-30, and 30-60 cm) were taken, resulting in 48 push cores in total. The other soil samples were taken at three depth levels: 0-10, 10-30, and 30-60 cm; 2-3 punctures per drilling point with Pürckhauer soil auger, resulting in 75 samples in total.

a) Planned agroforestry layout and initial soil sampling locations. Numbers in white taken Nov 2015, red numbers show samples taken March 2016 (Böhm and Kanzler, pers. comm.).

b) Location of soil sampling campaign III in October 2025 along four transects T1 to T4, (Google Maps and Airbus, 2025).

Figure 19. Soil sampling locations in the silvopastoral agroforestry at Peickwitz farm (orientation North, not for scale).

The third set of samples from the top 30 cm were obtained on 3 October 2025 from four transects (T1 to T4) in the silvopastoral agroforestry. The first sampling point in T1 was located closest to the treeline R1 (approx. 1.5 m distance to the tree row) and measurements continued from south to the second tree line R2 to the north-east. Following this pattern for each transect, the step-wise holes were dug with a spade at 1.5, 3, 4.5, 7.5, and 13.5 m from the tree line, together with a sample about 30 m from the trees marking the middle of the grassland plot. This process was repeated for all four transects. The location of each sampling was marked using a GARMIN GPS device. In total, there were 11 samples per transect; 44 samples in total. At each location approx. two cylinders of soil were collected additionally to analyse the biological activity in the soil. All samples were transferred to VUK in a mobile refrigerator for laboratory analysis.

The laboratory analyses included bulk density, pH-H₂O and pH-KCl³, nitrogen (%) and total soil organic carbon (TOC) in mass %. The soil laboratory analysis undertaken by VUK in Czechia included for the silvoarable treatment the new samples and “old” material obtained in sampling campaign 1 in 2016 with 48 samples, and 40 samples from 2025 campaign 2.

2.4.3. Results

Silvoarable agroforestry

Bulk density was not recorded in campaign 1 in 2016 in the silvoarable plot. The 2025 re-sampling approximated the initial sampling design, however, four probes located 48 m to the East to the tree row – samples 25, 30, 35, 40 – had to be excluded, due to interference from a newly established tree strip planted in 2021. This likely would have affected soil structure and comparability with previous measurements. After data cleaning, although the analysis of variance did not show a significant effect ($p > 0.05$), there was a trend for bulk density to increase from 1.34 g cm⁻³ at 3 m from the trees to 1.42 g cm⁻³ at 48 m from the trees (Table 12).

Table 12. Mean values of bulk density, pH, total organic carbon and nitrogen in 2016 and 2025 for the silvoarable plots at the German case study farm.

Parameter	Year	Distance to trees [m]	N	Mean ± s.d.	Range	F-value	p-value
Bulk density (g cm ⁻³)	2016	n.a.	48	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
		3	8	1.34 ± 0.16	1.08 – 1.49		
	2025	6	8	1.35 ± 0.18	1.02 – 1.54	0.275	0.892
		12	8	1.37 ± 0.14	1.17 – 1.56		
		24	8	1.40 ± 0.15	1.16 – 1.59		
		48	4*	1.42 ± 0.04	1.39 – 1.47		
pH-H ₂ O	2016	3	16	5.44 ± 0.14	5.22 – 5.68	1.45	0.245
		12	16	5.42 ± 0.13	5.17 – 5.60		
		48	16	5.50 ± 0.13	5.17 – 5.67		
	2025	3	8	5.60 ± 0.26	5.16 – 6.05	1.77	0.159
		6	8	5.59 ± 0.26	5.26 – 5.97		
		12	8	5.61 ± 0.17	5.38 – 5.80		
		24	8	5.78 ± 0.31	5.27 – 6.16		
		48	4	5.90 ± 0.09	5.81 – 6.01		
TOC (%)	2016	3	16	3.73 ± 1.94	1.97 – 9.18	0.195	0.824
		12	16	3.72 ± 1.55	1.19 – 6.67		
		48	16	3.44 ± 0.86	2.24 – 5.46		
	2025	3	8	3.35 ± 0.56	2.39 – 4.09	0.304	0.873
		6	8	3.25 ± 0.95	1.97 – 5.16		
		12	8	3.44 ± 1.34	2.30 – 6.36		
		24	8	3.76 ± 2.35	1.19 – 9.18		
		48	4*	2.89 ± 0.88	2.24 – 4.17		
N (%)	2016	3	16	0.198 ± 0.092	0.116 – 0.442	0.203	0.817

³ Both, pH-H₂O and pH-KCl were undertaken as measure different aspects of soil acidity, with pH-H₂O being the active acidity of the soil solution, meaning the conditions directly experienced by plant roots and soil microorganisms and therefore most relevant for nutrient availability and crop management. In contrast, pH-KCl indicates exchangeable or potential acidity and gives insight into long-term soil acidification, buffering capacity, and liming requirements.

		12	16	0.199 ± 0.075	0.083 – 0.363		
		48	16	0.184 ± 0.040	0.136 – 0.288		
		3	8	0.255 ± 0.096	0.140 – 0.409		
		6	8	0.239 ± 0.084	0.157 – 0.392		
	2025	12	8	0.257 ± 0.120	0.138 – 0.514	0.294	0.880
		24	8	0.232 ± 0.090	0.115 – 0.369		
		48	4*	0.202 ± 0.023	0.169 – 0.223		

*Four samples 48 m to the East had to be excluded from analysis from the 2025 campaign due to the planting of a new AF strip interfering with the measurements.

The **pH** at the site was uniformly acidic with mean values in 2025 ranging from 5.59 to 5.90 (Table 12).

The mean values for **total organic carbon** ranged from 3.44 to 3.73% in the 2016 campaign to 2.89 to 3.76% in 2025. In 2016, the mean levels of organic carbon ranged from 3.73% next to 3.44% at a distance of 48 m. In 2025, the pattern comprised mean values of 3.25-3.44% at distances of 3 m to 12 m from the trees, to 3.76% at a distance of 24 m, and 2.89% at a distance of 48 m, but these differences were not statistically different ($p > 0.05$).

There was also no significant ($p > 0.05$) effect of distance on the level of **soil nitrogen**. The mean values in 2015 ranged from 0.20% to 0.25%, with a tendency for higher values in near the trees than in the centre of the alley.

Silvopastoral agroforestry

Although the result was not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$) the **soil bulk density** tended to increase from 1.2 g cm⁻³ at a distance of 1.5 m from the tree to 1.48 g cm⁻³ at a distance of 13.5 m (Table 13).

Across the site the soil pH ranged from 4.70 to 5.15 with no significant effect of distance from the trees (Table 13). The large difference between the minimum (4.31) and maximum (6.67) values indicates strong spatial heterogeneity.

In contrast to bulk density and pH, **total organic carbon** (TOC) showed a statistically significant spatial pattern ($p < 0.001$). The soil carbon ranged from 12.11-13.56% at a distance of 1.5-4.5 m from the trees to 10.58-11.02 at a distance of 7.5 to 30.0 m from the trees (Table 13).

Similarly, **total nitrogen (N)** exhibited a significant effect of distance from the tree row ($p < 0.001$). The farthest zone (30 m) showed the lowest nitrogen concentrations (0.57%) and lowest variability, which may reflect more uniform management and lower organic inputs in the crop or pasture area. In addition, areas close to the tree rows are likely to be preferentially used by cattle for resting and ruminating during hot summer periods, which may further contribute to nutrient accumulation in these zones.

Table 13. Mean values of bulk density, pH, soil organic carbon (TOC) and nitrogen in 2016 and 2025 for the silvopastoral plots at the German case study farm.

Parameter	Year	Distance to trees [m]	n	Mean ± s.d.	Range	F-value	p-value
Bulk density	2016	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
	2025	1.5	8	1.20 ± 0.28	0.81 – 1.51	1.92	0.118

(g cm ⁻³)		3.0	8	1.31 ± 0.27	1.03 – 1.73		
		4.5	8	1.35 ± 0.25	1.04 – 1.76		
		7.5	8	1.40 ± 0.21	1.12 – 1.72		
		13.5	8	1.48 ± 0.31	0.99 – 1.91		
		30.0	4	1.34 ± 0.27	0.96 – 1.62		
pH-H ₂ O	2016	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
	2025	1.5	8	4.94 ± 0.22	4.60 – 5.34	1.48	0.221
		3.0	8	5.00 ± 0.32	4.50 – 5.65		
		4.5	8	4.91 ± 0.18	4.61 – 5.16		
		7.5	8	5.15 ± 0.68	4.59 – 6.67		
		13.5	8	4.70 ± 0.20	4.31 – 4.94		
	30.0	4	4.77 ± 0.36	4.51 – 5.28			
2016	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	
TOC (%)	2025	1.5	8	12.11 ± 4.47	7.09 – 19.65	6.42	< 0.001
		3.0	8	13.56 ± 4.80	7.65 – 21.04		
		4.5	8	12.94 ± 5.51	7.06 – 22.33		
		7.5	8	10.82 ± 3.85	4.53 – 15.68		
		13.5	8	11.02 ± 4.65	6.72 – 19.15		
	30.0	4	10.58 ± 2.39	6.69 – 11.61			
2016	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	
N (%)	2025	1.5	8	0.72 ± 0.23	0.40 – 1.01	7.05	< 0.001
		3.0	8	0.67 ± 0.23	0.40 – 1.08		
		4.5	8	0.69 ± 0.26	0.40 – 1.11		
		7.5	8	0.58 ± 0.17	0.27 – 0.80		
		13.5	8	0.60 ± 0.24	0.36 – 1.00		
	30.0	4	0.57 ± 0.12	0.41 – 0.73			

2.4.4. Discussion

Silvoarable agroforestry

The soil samples derived from the silvoarable treatment showed a high level of variability. One possible reason for this is that soil samples were taken at only one depth of 15-25 cm. Because soil parameters can change markedly with depth, small differences in the depth of measurement could cause differences in the measured results. Secondly the site has received manure applications (derived from housed livestock). This again can result in spatial differences in soil parameters. Thirdly, for some locations at a distance of 48 m from the tree row, a newly planted tree strip in 2021 would have affected the soil structure and hence half of the measurements at this distance were removed.

Although the results were not statistically significant by Anova, the silvoarable area tended to show higher levels of total organic carbon next to the trees (3.35%) compared to the centre of the alleys (2.89%) (Table 12). In addition the bulk density next to the trees (1.34 g cm⁻³) tended to be greater than in the centre of the alley (1.42 g cm⁻³), and the nitrogen content next to the trees (0.25%) was greater than that (0.20%) in the centre of the alley. The above trends could be explained by the addition of leaf matter from the trees resulting in higher soil carbon, which in turn helps to maintain lower bulk densities and higher nitrogen contents. However the high variability of soil measurements means that it was difficult to establish a significant effect at the current level of replication.

Although there was a plan to measure earthworm numbers, this did not occur due to time constraints. Previous research by Vaupel et al. (2023) on a different silvoarable system within the Brandenburg Living Lab in Forst/Lusatia indicated that, generally, trees in alley cropping promoted the abundance of earthworms, which was attributed to tree litter input, the absence of tillage, and an assumed increase in fungal diversity.

Silvopastoral agroforestry

The soil organic carbon content on the silvopastoral site (10.58-13.56%) was substantially higher than in the silvoarable area (5.59-5.90%). Whilst grassland systems are recognised to have higher carbon levels than arable systems, it is considered that the difference is also due to an inherent site effect; there is a reason why the pasture was located in a particular area. The silvopastoral system, planted in 2016, appeared to have a significant positive effect on the level of soil carbon and nitrogen near the trees. This observed increase in soil carbon could also relate to a tendency for lower bulk densities close to the tree. The higher levels of soil carbon could be related to higher organic matter inputs through leaf litter and root turnover, increased bioturbation by soil fauna, and root and microbe-induced aggregation forming more stable humus compounds.

Variability

Within both agroforestry systems there was substantial variability in soil characteristics. In addition to inherent effects and the effect of the trees, soil parameters could also be altered by localized compaction caused by machinery traffic, the distribution of manure, and the activity of cattle. A limitation of the design was that no samples were taken immediately below the trees and this should be included in future studies. Furthermore, composite sampling is highly recommended, as Minarsch et al. (2024) reports higher spatial variability in soil parameters and an increased root fraction in the wooded part of agroforestry systems.

2.5. Italy

2.5.1. Site description

The Arnino Long Term Experiment (LTE) is a 40 ha agroforestry trial site set up in 2017 to compare four different systems. The trial site is located within the agri-environmental research centre “Enrico Avanzi” of the University of Pisa. The experimental farm was selected as a case-study within the Italian Living Lab to represent an example of agroforestry system within a Mediterranean context. The area is located within the Arno valley (Valdarno Inferiore), the main river of the region. In particular, Arnino is located on reclaimed land between the estuary of the Arno River and the sea, which results in a high level of variability of soil characteristics and properties among fields. Characterisation data of the farm is shown in Table 14. The Arnino LTE experiment is divided in four systems (treatments): arable, mixed, and silvoarable and agrosilvopastoral treatments (Table 15). The agroforestry treatments either have a low or high density of poplars. Further details of the experiment is provided by Mantino et al. (2019).

Table 14. Characterisation data of the Italian farm.

Parameters	Information
Coordinates	43.667205 N, 10.313160 E
Farm type	Arable
Farm size	40 ha
Production system/s	Non-organic
Agroforestry system in place	Yes
Soil type	clay-loam textures
Average annual rainfall	920 mm (long-term average 1986–2016)
Average annual temperature	15° C (long-term average 1986–2016)

Table 15. The arable, silvoarable, mixed and agrosilvicultural treatments at the Arnino LTE.

System	Tree density	Cropping
Arable		3-years rotation of durum wheat, sorghum and faba bean
Silvoarable	Low density: 10 m x 30 m poplar (33 poplars ha ⁻¹)	As above
	High density: 10 m x 30 m poplar with an additional central row of poplar (77 poplar ha ⁻¹)	As above
Mixed		7-years crop rotation (durum wheat, sorghum, faba bean, and 4-year of mixed temporary grassland)
Agrosilvo-pastoral	Low density: : 10 m x 30 m poplar (33 poplars ha ⁻¹)	As above
	High density: 10 m x 30 m poplar with an additional central row of poplar (77 poplar ha ⁻¹)	As above

This farm was selected as case-study to conduct the soil sampling to attempt to quantify the benefits that agroforestry is able to deliver at the soil level. Particularly, for the soil analyses two system were compared: the mixed system (orange fields in Figure 20) and the agrosilvopastoral system (pink fields

in Figure 20). More in detail, the chosen area for soil sampling was located on fields 9 and 20 during the first year of the mixed temporary grassland. The mixed temporary grassland is composed of Italian ryegrass (*Lolium multiflorum* Lam. var. *italicum*), orchard-grass (*Dactylis glomerata* L.), tall fescue (*Festuca arundinacea* L.), sulla (*Hedysarum coronarium* L.) and alfalfa (*Medicago sativa* L.) and was seeded on the 05/11/2024. So far, animals are not included within the trial for direct grazing, so the final use of the biomass is for hay production.

The decision to perform soil sampling on the first year of mixed temporary grassland fields was made based on two considerations. Firstly, the inclusion of temporary grasslands within crop rotation scheme is widely recognized as a practice that tends to accumulate higher levels of soil organic matter compared to cultivated fields (Bai et al., 2022). This is mainly associated with continuous root activity, reduced soil disturbance, and a steady input of organic material from plant residues and roots, as documented in the literature (Yang et al., 2019). The second consideration was that soil sampling during the first year of the temporary grassland establishment allowed the assessment of the baseline soil organic matter content. At the fourth year of the temporary grassland, before ploughing, it will be possible to repeat the soil analyses in the same plots. These two considerations allow for a more reliable assessment of temporal changes in soil quality and organic matter accumulation allowing the estimation of the combined effects of grassland and agroforestry systems without interference from soil disturbances.

Figure 20. Aerial map of Arnino LTE. The mixed and agrosilvopastoral systems are coloured in pink and in orange respectively. Sampling site locations are shown with the green boxes: CTRL corresponds to the control treatment while AGF corresponds to the agroforestry treatment.

2.5.2. Sampling design and measurements

Soil sampling was conducted in May 2025, and it was carried out when the soil was moist but not excessively dry and at an interval from the previous manure application. The last manure application was conducted on 25 July 2024 at 40 t ha⁻¹. Two treatments were compared: agroforestry (AGF) and control (CTRL), the corresponding sampling points were placed respectively within the agrosilvopastoral and the mixed system. The paired plots were positioned on the field corresponding to the same year of rotation to reduce the variability that crop rotation might create. Moreover, to reduce the differences in soil variability, sampling plots were chosen to be as close as possible. Detailed characteristics of the sampling sites are presented in Table 16.

Table 16. Description of the three selected treatments at Arnino.

System	Area (m ²)	Crop and/or tree cover	Tree age (years)	Tree density (trees ha ⁻¹)	Intra-row (m)	Alley width (m)	Co-ordinates	N° of points
Mixed (CTRL)	950	Mixed temp. grassland	-	-	-	-	43°39'48.2"N 10°18'11.8"E	25
Agrosilvopastoral (AGF)	800	Mixed temp. grassland with poplar	6	33	10	30	43°39'48.0"N 10°17'56.6"E	25
Agrosilvopastoral tree row (AGF-TR)	60	Fallow with poplar trees	6	33	10	30	43°39'48.0"N 10°17'56.6"E	6

Samplings points were produced following a grid of 5 by 5, for a total of 25 points for each treatment. Moreover, within the Agrosilvopastoral treatment (AGF), six sampling points were placed along the tree line, one soil sample on the right and one on the left of each tree. Figure 21 shows the location of sampling plots on the fields. Each sampling point was geo-referenced to allow for repeated sampling in future years at the same location.

Figure 21. Panels a) and b) show the sampling points within the aerial images of the mixed (CTRL) and agrosilvopastoral (AGF) systems; green dots represent the CTRL treatment, orange dots represent the AGF treatment, yellow dots represent the agrosilvopastoral tree row (AGF-TR) treatment. Images in c) and d) display photographs of the same systems as seen on the ground, respectively.

For the measurement of soil organic carbon and pH, soil samples were collected at 0–10 cm and 10–30 cm, using a cylindric soil sampler. The soil samples were dried at 40°C and sent to an accredited laboratory for the analysis of soil organic carbon (SOC) and pH. In the laboratory, the level of carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen was conducted with a CHN elemental analyser. The pH was determined following the procedure ISO 10390:2021.

The sampling sites and layout used to measure bulk density were the same as those used for the soil quality analyses and the methodology used was the core method proposed by FAO (2023). A rigid cylinder of known diameter (2.60 cm) and height (4.2cm) was inserted in the soil to collect an undisturbed soil sample (Figure 22). The bulk density was measured at two different depths. The first sampling was carried out at the soil surface, after carefully removing the layer of fresh organic litter. The second sampling was taken at a depth of 20 cm. Figure 22 shows two pictures of the sampling procedure.

Figure 22. Cylindric soil sampler used during the procedure for the determination of soil bulk density.

Earthworm abundance was assessed in November 2025 during the autumn season, when soil conditions are not too dry but the temperatures were still warm. For the earthworm sampling, nine sampling points were selected for three locations, with three sampling points each in the control mixed system (CTRL), the agrosilvopastoral treatment (AGF), and the tree row (TR) (Figure 23). At each point, a pit of 20 cm x 20 cm x 20 cm was dug out and soil was placed on a plastic sheet according to the procedure and methodology proposed in Aynekulu et al., 2026. At each site, the soil sample was placed on a tray, hand sorted, and the earthworms were transferred to a pot, counted and weighted (Figure 24). A summary of soil analysis performed at the Italian Living Lab is presented in Table 17.

Figure 23. Sampling scheme to measure earthworms abundance in the control treatment (CTRL), the agroforestry treatment (AGF) and the tree row of the agroforestry (AGF (TR)).

Figure 24. Example of sampling pit (20 x 20 x 20 cm), and example of some of the earthworms collected.

Table 17. Summary of soil analysis conducted at the Italian Living Lab (n of samples in tree row indicated in brackets).

Soil analysis	Depth	Mixed (CTRL)	Agrosilvopastoral (AGF)	Analysed
Bulk density	0-10 cm	25	31 (6)	CiRAA*
	10-30 cm	25	31 (6)	CiRAA*
pH	0-10 cm	25	31 (6)	CiRAA*
	10-30 cm	25	31 (6)	CiRAA*
Carbon	0-10 cm	25	31 (6)	CiRAA*
	10-30 cm	25	31 (6)	CiRAA*
Nitrogen	0-10 cm	25	31 (6)	CiRAA*
	10-30 cm	25	31 (6)	CiRAA*
Earthworm density	0-20 cm	3	6 (3)	

*CiRAA - Agro-environmental Research Center 'Enrico Avanzi'

2.5.3. Results

Bulk density, pH, carbon, nitrogen and carbon stock.

A preliminary data analysis was conducted to calculate mean values, standard deviation, and range of the four variables (bulk density, pH, carbon, nitrogen, and carbon stock) according to the treatment and the depth. Table 18 shows the preliminary results indicating that: the bulk density ranges from 1.22 to 1.71 g cm⁻³ with a mean value of 1.56 g cm⁻³, the pH is alkaline ranging from 7.96 to 8.56 with an average value of 8.31, the carbon content ranges from 0.7 to 2.05% with a mean value of 1.24%, and nitrogen content ranges from 0.07 to 0.27% with an average value of 0.16%. Finally, the carbon stock measured as t C ha⁻¹ calculated using Eq. 1 ranges from 16.02 t C ha⁻¹ to 50.71 Mg ha⁻¹.

Table 18. Preliminary data analysis of the Italian site.

	Treatment	Depth (cm)	n	Mean ± s.d.	Range	
Bulk density (g cm ⁻³)	CTRL	0-10	25	1.53 ± 0.12	1.22 - 1.68	
		10-30	25	1.63 ± 0.09	1.30 - 1.73	
	AGF	0-10	25	1.46 ± 0.13	1.18 - 1.70	
		10-30	25	1.58 ± 0.08	1.45 - 1.71	
pH	AGF-TR	0-10	6	1.49 ± 0.11	1.34 - 1.59	
		10-30	6	1.67 ± 0.04	1.61 - 1.71	
	CTRL	0-10	25	8.25 ± 0.09	8.05 - 8.45	
		10-30	25	8.37 ± 0.09	8.17 - 8.53	
Carbon (%)	AGF	0-10	25	8.27 ± 0.13	7.96 - 8.44	
		10-30	25	8.38 ± 0.13	8.04 - 8.56	
	AGF-TR	0-10	6	8.25 ± 0.16	8.10 - 8.48	
		10-30	6	8.31 ± 0.11	8.12 - 8.41	
Carbon Stock (t C ha ⁻¹)	CTRL	0-10	25	1.40 ± 0.28	1.08 - 2.05	
		10-30	25	1.03 ± 0.17	0.70 - 1.47	
	AGF	0-10	25	1.38 ± 0.15	1.05 - 1.61	
		10-30	25	1.16 ± 0.20	0.90 - 1.70	
	AGF-TR	0-10	6	1.63 ± 0.11	1.50 - 1.77	
		10-30	6	0.82 ± 0.12	0.68 - 1.03	
	Nitrogen (%)	CTRL	0-10	25	0.16 ± 0.04	0.09 - 0.22
			10-30	25	0.12 ± 0.04	0.07 - 0.21
AGF		0-10	25	0.19 ± 0.04	0.11 - 0.25	
		10-30	25	0.14 ± 0.04	0.08 - 0.20	
Carbon Stock (t C ha ⁻¹)	AGF-TR	0-10	6	0.24 ± 0.03	0.21 - 0.27	
		10-30	6	0.10 ± 0.02	0.07 - 0.13	
	CTRL	0-10	25	20.04 ± 2.27	16.99 - 25.05	
		10-30	25	36.71 ± 5.79	27.39 - 50.71	
AGF	0-10	25	24.31 ± 2.87	20.21 - 28.19		
	10-30	25	27.41 ± 3.57	23.19 - 33.75		
AGF-TR	0-10	6	21.38 ± 4.27	16.02 - 29.48		
	10-30	6	33.58 ± 5.81	22.80 - 49.30		

A preliminary assessment of data distribution was conducted through Boxplot based on variable, treatment and depth (Figure 25).

Figure 25. Mean box plot for bulk density, pH, and proportion carbon and nitrogen for two soil depths in the control (CTRL), agroforestry (AGF) and agroforestry tree row (AGF-TR); the horizontal black solid line refers to the median value. The green diagram corresponds to the 0-10 cm of depth, while the orange diagram to the 10-30 cm. Points corresponds to outliers' values.

Statistical analysis was completed using R Studio (R Core Team). A linear model was used to analyse soil properties: (i) bulk density, (ii) pH, (iii) carbon, (iv) nitrogen with two fixed factors treatment ($n = 3$) and depth ($n = 2$), and their interaction. The function 'lm' from nlme package was used to run the model. Assumption for ANOVA were tested with Shapiro-Wilk normality test of residues and Levene test. Significant differences were detected among treatments and depths through ANOVA. Table 19 shows the results of the statistical analysis.

Significant differences were detected between treatments for all variables except the pH. Depth resulted in highly significant differences for all four variables. Significant interactions were determined for C and N content. Bulk density increased in the lower soil layer (1.63 g cm^{-3} for 10-30 cm vs. 1.50 g cm^{-3}) while the control treatment had a higher bulk density compared to the AGF (1.59 g cm^{-3} vs. 1.53 g cm^{-3}). Bulk density on the tree row (AGF-TR) did not differ significantly from that in the control and agroforestry treatments. The pH increased with depth (8.36 for 10-30 cm vs. 8.26 for 0-10 cm) but no significant differences were detected among treatments.

Table 19. Results of the statistical analysis conducted on soil variables.

	Bulk density (g cm ⁻³)	pH	Carbon (%)	Nitrogen (%)	Carbon Stock (t C ha ⁻¹)
n (outliers excluded)	109	111	103	112	107
Treatment					
Control (CTRL)	1.59 ± 0.01 ^a	8.31 ± 0.02	1.16 ± 0.02 ^b	0.14 ± 0.01 ^b	27.15 ± 0.60
Agroforestry (AGF)	1.53 ± 0.01 ^b	8.33 ± 0.03	1.25 ± 0.02 ^a	0.17 ± 0.01 ^a	28.08 ± 0.60
Agrofor. Tree-Row (AGF-TR)	1.58 ± 0.03 ^{ab}	8.28 ± 0.02	1.23 ± 0.04 ^{ab}	0.17 ± 0.01 ^a	25.86 ± 1.21
Depth					
0-10 cm	1.50 ± 0.01 ^b	8.26 ± 0.02 ^b	1.44 ± 0.03 ^a	0.20 ± 0.01 ^a	21.91 ± 0.69 ^b
10-30 cm	1.63 ± 0.01 ^a	8.36 ± 0.02 ^a	0.99 ± 0.03 ^b	0.12 ± 0.01 ^b	32.16 ± 0.70 ^a
P value					
Treatment (df =2)	0.0032	0.3301	0.0043	0.0014	0.1485
Depth (df = 1)	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001
Treat x depth (df = 2)	0.3841	0.7273	< 0.0001	0.0005	< 0.0001
Shapiro-Wilk normality test	0.06	0.17	0.22	0.11	0.14

The carbon (1.44%) and nitrogen (0.20%) content in the first 10 cm of soil was higher than at 10-30 cm (0.99% for carbon and 0.12% for nitrogen). The agroforestry treatment also had a higher ($p < 0.05$) carbon content (1.25%) than the control treatment (1.16%). However, the carbon content in the agroforestry tree row treatment was not significantly different from that in the agroforestry and the control areas. The soil nitrogen content (0.17%) in the agroforestry and the agroforestry tree row treatments were higher ($p < 0.05$) than that (0.14%) in the control area (Table 19). No significant differences were found among treatments regarding the carbon stock ($p = 0.1485$) but depth has a significant influence on C stock, which are higher in higher depth ($p < 0.0001$).

Earthworms

No statistical analysis were performed on the results of earthworms' abundance, but a general overview of the data is presented in Table 20. The number of earthworms ranges from 0 to 12 with variable weight ranging from less than 0.01 g to 3.18 g. Both in the control and agroforestry treatments in one out of three sampling points there were no earthworms found; earthworms were found within all the three sampling points of the agroforestry tree row treatment.

Table 20. Effect of treatment on earthworm abundance and weight.

System (treatment)	Distance from tree rows (m)	Earthworms abundance (n)	Earthworms weight (g)
Control (CTRL)	NA	11	1.85
	NA	0	0
	NA	5	0.49
Agroforestry (AGF)	2.5	11	NA
	2.5	12	1.01

	2.5	0	NA
Agroforestry Tree-Row (AGF-TR)	0	5	0.98
	0	9	3.18
	0	4	1.50

2.5.4. Discussion

The control treatment showed higher values of bulk density than the agroforestry treatment indicating a positive effect of trees in improving soil physical properties, similarly to what Pereira et al. (2025) demonstrated; whereas the intermediate value of bulk density of the agroforestry tree row treatment is explained by the compaction of soil along the tree row which is not subjected to mechanical operation.

The soil analyses show that the soil within the trial site presents high pH values, markedly alkaline soil. Considering that the pH is a property that it is difficult to change over-time, not surprisingly there are not differences among treatments but only with depth that might be explained by the origin/constitution of the soil and not by the presence of trees.

Regarding nutrient content, carbon and nitrogen, the first 10 cm of soil layer contains higher values of both nutrients for all treatments compared to the deeper soil layer (10-30 cm). As reported by previous studies, e.g. Pardon et al. (2017), Rolo et al. (2023), Veldkamp et al. (2023), trees have positive effects on soil fertility by increasing both carbon and nitrogen content.

Overall, trees have positive effects on soil properties, indicating that agroforestry can effectively be used as a winning carbon farming practice. Further analysis should be performed to explore the effects of tree distance on soil properties.

2.6. The Netherlands

2.6.1. Site description

The Dutch case study farm is “Tussen de Hagen” located in Stoutenburg, the Netherlands. It is an organic family-owned dairy farm that has since several years started diversifying its operations, with agroforestry as one of the new practices. The farm comprises 76 hectares of grassland, of which 50 ha is intensively managed grassland and 26 ha is natural grasslands. The productive grassland is rich in clover with an estimated 30% coverage. All fields are loamy sand (>80% sand). The moisture levels on the plots are relatively good for a sandy soil and are approximately equal across the parcels. The average annual rainfall is 870 mm (Table 21).

Table 21. Characterisation data of the selected Dutch farm.

Parameters	Information
Coordinates	52.1467534, 5.4384502
Farm size	76 ha
Farm type	Organic
Production system/s	Dairy
Agroforestry system in place	Yes
Soil type	Sand
Average annual rainfall	870 mm
Mean air temperature	11.3°C

All fields receive standard fertilization of slurry early in the season except for the natural grassland, which is not fertilized. In addition, 15 ha receive an additional application of slurry later in the season. Every two years, farm yard manure is applied on all fields. All labour is undertaken by the farmers, with the exception of cutting of the pasture, producing silage from the grass, spreading of the farm yard manure and sometimes the application of the slurry. For these activities a contractor is hired. A large part of the plots is used for grazing.

The herd consists of 100 milking cows, 30 heifers and 15 beef cattle cows. Annually about 8,200 kg milk per cow is produced with fat and protein contents of 4.4% and 3.4% respectively. Seventeen years ago, Holstein was crossed with Fleckvieh, Montbeliarde and Swedish Red-and-White. Nowadays the dairy herd consists of a mix of six breeds, including Brown Swiss and Jersey. The beef cattle is a mix of Belgian Blue, Angus, Hereford, and Speckle Park. In addition, 200 chickens and 4 pigs are raised.

Two different types of agroforestry systems have been planted over the course of several years: fodder hedges and silvopasture with fruit and nut trees. The largest agroforestry plot (Figure 26) covers 3 ha, with 120 walnut and chestnut trees planted in 20 m rows with a 19 m intercrop area and a 1 m wide tree strip spacing for easy machine passage. Eighteen standard apple and pear trees have been planted on a field of 0.3 ha. In addition, 600 m of fodder hedge have been planted, consisting of willow, alder and hazel, and another 800 m of hedges acting as field boundaries consisting of blackthorn, hawthorn and hornbeam. Part of the fodder hedges is also actively managed (besides the casual browsing by the cows) and therefore this type of fodder hedge could also be classified as short rotation coppice (SRC). Another fodder hedge (mostly consisting of hornbeam) is very actively browsed by the cows and requires no further management.

2.6.2. Sampling design and measurements

Originally, a treatment and control setup was envisioned. Due to time limitations and because the envisioned control plot was recently tilled, the only plot sampled was the treatment plot (Table 22). Here we sampled at different distances from the tree; at half the distance and at a quarter distance between the tree rows. Six repeated measures were taken to ensure sufficient data and variability needed for statistical inference.

Table 22. Characteristics of the sampling plot.

	Area (ha)	Tree species	Tree age	Tree density (trees/ha)	Intra-row distance (m)	Alley width (m)	Row width (m)
Silvopastoral	2.55	Walnut, chestnut	4	53	7.2	19	1

Figure 26. Planned sampling locations. Red = SP. The letters represent the repeated measures (A to F).

- Sampling points worms
- Sampling points Kopecky rings
- Sampling points SOM/pH/RhoC
- Chestnut
- Walnut

The data collection took place on 1 October 2025. The period before had been somewhat wet. It was therefore deemed a suitable moment with regards to the presence of earthworms in the soil due to suitable moisture conditions. The sampling sites for soil organic matter (SOM) and pH sampling point were staked out using plastic field markers. The location of these field markers was collected using a precision GPS. In this way, the exact sampling locations can be retraced in case a remeasuring campaign would take place in the future.

Soil organic matter and pH

Soil organic matter and pH samples were collected at five distances from the tree row (two times at mid distance, two times at quarter distance, and one time in the tree row) in sixfold (see Figure 26; Table 23). A wide soil probe with hammer head was driven into the soil with a hammer up to 60 cm depth. The soil from the probe was collected separately at 0-30 and 30-60 cm. Five subsamples were taken and mixed into one composite sample following the sampling layout of LUCAS (Orgiazzi et al., 2018; Figure 27). The centre sample matches the location of the plastic marker which matches the precision GPS coordinate. Samples were collected and refrigerated for 7 days. Samples were then analysed at the Eurofins laboratory Netherlands. The analyses performed were: soil moisture, pH-CaCl₂, N-mineral, organic matter (LOI), organic matter (elementary), N-total, C-total.

Figure 27. Sampling layout following LUCAS (Orgiazzi et al., 2018).

Table 23. Description of sampling depths and samples for each measurement.

Collection method	Replicates	Sampling depth	N of samples per replicate	N of subsamples per sample	Lab analyses
Soil organic matter and pH using a soil probe	6 (A to F)	0-30; 30-60 cm	5 composite samples	5 sub-samples for 1 composite sample	Soil moisture, pH-CaCl ₂ , N-mineral, organic matter (LOI), organic matter (elementary), N-total, C-total
Bulk density using Kopecky bulk density rings	3 (A, C, F)	15; 45 cm	2 samples	Average of 3 rings	Drying at 105°C for 24 hours and weighing
Bulk density using RhoC meter	6 (A to F)	15; 45 cm	5 measures	NA	NA
Earthwork density in 20 cm x 20 cm x 20 cm block	3 (A, C, F)	0-20 cm	2 samples	NA	Weighing and counting

Bulk density

Bulk density was collected in two ways: 1) using the RhoC meter (Pepers et al., 2024); and 2) using Kopecky bulk density rings. The RhoC meter uses gamma rays to derive the soil moisture and density. It has been recently validated for sandy clay loam and sandy soils in the Netherlands where the relative uncertainty was 9% for the Kopecky rings and 15% for the RhoC-sensor (Pepers et al., 2024). The RhoC sensor fits in the holes made by the wide soil probe, and as a result it was possible to collect many bulk density samples at many depths and at many points. RhoC measurements were taken at every point where SOM and pH samples were collected as well.

As a comparison, and to have a comparable methods to other Living Labs, Kopecky bulk density rings were added as a reference. Bulk density rings were taken at two distances of the tree row (one time at mid distance and one time in the tree row) in threefold (Figure 26). The soil pit that was left over after collecting earthworm samples was enlarged to collect three rings per soil depth (15 cm and 45 cm) horizontally over the soil profile (the open end of the ring oriented horizontally). The rings are driven in using a ring “holder” and a “hammerable” piece (Royal Eijckelkamp) that allowed for relatively undisturbed collection of samples. Care was taken that no soil fell out of the ring during handling, as this would lead to a large underestimation of soil bulk density. If some soil did fall out, a new ring was taken. The rings were dried at 105 °C and weighed at the laboratory of the Louis Bolk Institute. The average bulk density and standard deviation of each set of three rings is reported. The size of the standard deviation relative to the mean provides insight on the variance and reliability of the sample.

Earthworms

A soil block of 20 x 20 cm x 20cm is collected using a metal plate as a marker for the correct size, and two spades. A ‘wedge’ is dug out so that the soil block can be collected in a way so that it is as square as possible. Soil blocks were deposited on a plastic tarp and worms were manually collected from the soil block by systematic deconstruction. Worms were collected in a jar and taken to the Louis Bolk laboratory and stored in a fridge. The next day, worms were washed in 70% ethanol and weighted and counted in the categories adult or juvenile and in the categories epigeic (surface-dwelling) or endogeic (soil-dwelling).

2.6.3. Results

Soil organic carbon and pH

The soil organic carbon (2.13-2.34%) at 0-30 cm was over double that (1.03-1.09%) measured at 30-60 cm) (Table 24). The pH showed very little variation with treatment or depth.

Table 24. Effect of depth and location related to trees on mean, standard deviation (SD) and coefficient of variation (CV) on soil organic carbon (SOC) and pH (method: CaCl₂). n = 60. The data is averaged for six replicates split by distance between the treelines (half distance = D/2, quarter distance = D/4).

Position	Depth (cm)	SOC (%)			pH (CaCl ₂)		
		Mean	SD	CV	Mean	SD	CV
In row	0-30	2.13	±0.36	17%	5.37	±0.08	1%
	30-60	1.03	±0.62	60%	5.37	±0.22	4%
D/2	0-30	2.25	±0.21	9%	5.43	±0.08	1%
	30-60	1.09	±0.56	51%	5.42	±0.13	2%
D/4	0-30	2.34	±0.26	11%	5.47	±0.09	2%
	30-60	1.07	±0.62	58%	5.46	±0.16	3%

Bulk density

To test the accuracy of the RhoC sensor in comparison with the Kopecky rings, the root mean squared error (RMSE), mean bias estimate (MBE), and relative bias (relative to the range of values for the average of the Kopecky rings) were calculated (n=12). The average of the three Kopecky rings was taken as the “true” value with which the reference value of the RhoC sensor was compared. In addition, the coefficient of variation (CV) was calculated for each average of three rings (Figure 28). The RMSE was 0.17 g cm⁻³, the MBE was -0.08 g cm⁻³, and the relative bias was 19.0%.

Figure 28. Comparison of the average dry bulk density collected with rings with the dry bulk density collected with RhoC. The dashed line is the reference line. RMSE, MBE, and relative bias are displayed. The CV is displayed per observation and relates to the Kopecky rings collection method.

Earthworms

Unfortunately, during the sampling process of the sample of repetition A at 10 m was mistakenly taken at 5 m distance. However, for the sake of calculating the mean, and having few samples available, the 5 m distance sample was averaged with the 10 m distance samples. The mean number of earthworms ranged from 17.0 to 21.3 per 8 dm³ block (Table 25). For the summary statistics, the

epigeic, endogeic, juvenile, and adult worms were summed to the total number of worms. No statistic comparisons were made because of the limited size of the dataset.

Table 25. Effect of distance from tree on the number and biomass of earthworms in a 20 cm x 20 cm x 20 cm soil block.. n = 3. *for sample A, the distance samples was actually D/4 instead of D/2.

Position	Depth (cm)	Number of worms			Biomass (g)		
		Mean	SD	CV	Mean	SD	CV
In-row	0-20	21.33	9.18	43%	2.90	0.72	25%
D/2*	0-20	17.00	1.79	11%	4.19	1.99	47%

Soil organic carbon stock

To calculate the SOC stock, first a fixed depth approach was taken. The RhoC density measurements were multiplied by the SOC content. The results were averaged for six to twelve replicates split by distance between the treelines (in the row = in-row, half distance = D/2, quarter distance = D/4) and soil depth (0-30 or 30-60 cm). An ANOVA was executed with Tukey’s HSD as a post-hoc test to look at individual differences (Figure 29). The data is nearly normally distributed, hence no corrections to the data or deviations to non-parametric tests were deemed necessary. When the results were analysed including the effect of the orientation of the tree line, no significant effects were found, so only the aggregated results are presented.

Figure 29. Comparison of SOC stock (ton/ha) over different depths (topsoil on the left, subsoil on the right) and different distances. A difference in letters (a, b) denotes a significant difference based on Tukey’s HSD post-hoc test. The blue dot indicates the average value of six/twelve replicates. The red dots are the replicates, displayed in a “jitter” for improved visibility.

The results show that the in-row SOC stock of the 0-30 cm soil depth layer was lower ($p < 0.05$) than at D/2 and D/4 for the same soil layer. The SOC stock is calculated on the basis of the SOC content and the bulk density combined. Differences in SOC stocks can be due to an interplay of both factors. Figure 30 and Figure 31 show the ANOVA and post-hoc tests for the SOC content and the bulk density. Again, the data is nearly normally distributed, hence no corrections to the data or deviations to non-parametric tests were deemed necessary. In both cases, there was no difference ($p = 0.05$) between the averages of six/twelve replicates for the SOC content and bulk density. However, the effect of both the SOC content and the bulk density being lower in-row than at other distances, the SOC stock calculation in-row comes out as significantly different than the other distances.

Figure 30. Comparison of SOC content (%) over different depths (topsoil on the left, subsoil on the right) and different distances. A difference in letters (a, b) denotes a significant difference based on Tukey's HSD post-hoc test. The blue dot indicates the average value of six/twelve replicates. The red dots are the replicates, displayed in a "jitter" for improved visibility.

Figure 31. Comparison of the dry bulk density (kg/L) over different depths (topsoil on the left, subsoil on the right) and different distances. A difference in letters (a, b) denotes a significant difference based on Tukey’s HSD post-hoc test. The blue dot indicates the average value of six/twelve replicates. The red dots are the replicates, displayed in a “jitter” for improved visibility.

2.6.4. Discussion

Bulk density

Regarding the comparison between methods to estimate bulk density (RhoC vs Kopecky rings), our results show that RhoC give satisfactory (although somewhat biased) results, with a smaller effort than the rings. Pepers et al. (2024) find a comparable RMSE and MBE for a sandy soil when regarding the Kopecky rings as the “true” value and comparing them with the RhoC method. Excluding the top 10 cm of soil (because of the looseness in the topsoil in arable farming it is harder to collect a representative Kopecky ring sample), and looking at the average dry bulk density for three replicates (both for the Kopecky rings as for the RhoC) they find a RMSE of 0.14 g cm^{-3} and an MBE of -0.05 g cm^{-3} for sandy soils. The RMSE and MBE is probably higher in our study because we did not use an average of three RhoC measurements, but only one measurement, and furthermore because the Kopecky rings and RhoC measurements were not taken in *exactly* the same position but in the very near proximity. However, the same conclusion can be drawn, namely that the RhoC meter slightly overestimates the bulk density on sandy soils compared to Kopecky rings. It can be possible to account for what seems to be a structural overestimation when using the bulk density to calculate the soil carbon stock. Despite this slight overestimation, the advantage of the RhoC measurements relative to the Kopecky rings was that it allowed the collection of many more bulk density samples within a short time frame, greatly increasing the number of bulk density measurements. The results of the bulk density itself shows that the top- and subsoil have a comparable density across depth and distances, though variation is much larger in the subsoil than in the topsoil. Another observation is that the

topsoil and subsoil in-row that have on average a lower (though non-significant) density than the soil between rows.

Soil organic carbon stock

The results show that there are in general no differences of soil carbon stock over distances for both the topsoil and the subsoil. The only notable exception is that at 0-30 cm the in-row soil carbon stock is on average lower than the other distances – though the only statistically significant difference is found with the quarter distance east of the tree row (East D/4). A possible explanation for this difference might be that during the planting of the trees the inflicted soil disturbance has caused local loss of carbon as well as a reduced bulk density. This can be typical for a young agroforestry system, where carbon stocks may decline in early stages of the development of trees, but where carbon dynamics are likely to change over time as the trees mature. Another result is that the subsoil has about half of the SOC stock as the topsoil, indicating that the effect of the grassland on the carbon content is strongest in the topsoil (0-30 cm) Possibly when the agroforestry system matures and the tree roots develop further, the tree roots may start to have a bigger effect on carbon dynamics in the subsoil (30-60 cm).

2.7. Portugal

2.7.1. Site description

The MVARC farm, Curralões, covers 240 ha near Mértola in Baixo Alentejo, in south-east Portugal. It is in a landscape dominated by game management and extensive livestock/ arable production on marginal land. The climate is characterised by an average annual rainfall of 548 mm (although in the last 15 years, the average has dropped to 273 mm) falling mainly in the autumn, winter and spring months and hot, dry summers. As elsewhere, climate change impacts are a concern with drought a frequent issue in recent years. The soils are lithosols/leptosols (subgroup Eutric), which are shallow soils over hard rock and comprise of very gravelly material, with a pH between 5.6-6.5 (Figure 32). With a poorly developed structure and weakly expressed horizons, they are characteristic of undulating lands and steep slopes and are also found in areas where the soil is highly eroded (Table 26).

Table 26. Characterisation data of the Portuguese site.

Parameters	Information
Coordinates	37.56418, -7.69005
Farm size	240 ha
Farm type	Organic
Production system/s	Livestock
Agroforestry system in place	Yes
Soil type	Lithosols/leptosols
Average annual rainfall	548 mm
Mean air temperature	17.5°C

Figure 32. (Left) Soil map (Jones N et al. (2011) with study location (yellow star); (Right) 28 years average of precipitation and temperatures (max, min, average). Data source: SNIRH, Martinlongo weather station.

In 1994, over 130,000 *Pinus pinea* trees were planted on 160 ha of the farm under an afforestation measure in the CAP Pillar 2, with the aim of improving the environmental value of the landscape by reducing erosion by wind and water and increasing carbon storage. While Curralões was one of the first farms to implement the afforestation measure, neighbouring farmers soon followed in 1997; these neighbours have now thinned their trees to a much lower density and reintroduced sheep grazing (Silvopasture plots).

The trees were planted at an initial density of 7 m x 1.75 m spacing (~ 800 trees ha⁻¹); in the Forestry plots, these were planted in rows running east-west, while in the silvopasture plots, these were planted on the contours. The forest plots have been thinned to between 400 and 560 trees ha⁻¹ while the silvopasture plots were heavily thinned in 2020 to around 65 trees ha⁻¹ (Table 27). Some areas on the farm were not planted with trees, and these will be used as a 'No-Tree' comparison. In all areas, regular soil disturbance with a disc harrow has been used to control shrub growth, primarily the species *Cistus ladanifer*, for farmers to retain eligibility for CAP payments (shrubs are allowed up to 50 cm height, but farmers opt for disk harrowing as it allows a returning period of 4-5 years, instead of a returning period of 2 years with a shrub-cutter).

Table 27. The three 'treatments' compared in at the case study in Portugal.

Treatment	Trees	Understorey management
Forestry	31-year-old <i>Pinus pinea</i> at 400-560 trees/ha	Shrub clearance with disc harrow every 5-7 years (last clearance 2020). No grazing animals (but wild boar, deer, rabbits present)
Silvopasture	28-year-old <i>Pinus pinea</i> at 65 trees/ha	Sheep grazing. Shrub clearance with disc harrow every 5-7 years (last clearance 2022).
Grassland/ shrubland	No trees	Very occasional sheep grazing. Shrub clearance with disc harrow every 5-7 years (last clearance 2020).

2.7.2. Sampling design and measurements

In 2021, as part of the AGROMIX project, three plots were identified in each treatment with similar altitude (168-207 m), slope and aspect (south-west facing) (Table 28). These plots were sampled for bird and bat species diversity, plant diversity, pollinators and soil invertebrates. An additional plot has been added in each treatment for DIGITAF sampling to allow for four transects per treatment (Figure 33).

Figure 33. Four transects per Treatment (F = Forest; P = Grassland/shrubland; S = Silvopasture).

A nested design was used with 'Treatment' at the highest level (silvopasture/forestry/grassland-shrubland). Within each treatment there were four sampling transects (Figure 33, Table 28). In the forestry and silvopasture treatments, each transect was centred on a tree row (0 m) with samples running north and south of the tree row at 1.5 m (edge of tree canopy) and 3.5 m (alley centre), i.e. each transect was formed of five sample points. This same design was replicated in the grass/shrubland. Sampling was carried out between 6 and 10 May 2025.

Table 28. Characteristics of the transects in Portugal.

Transect ID	Area (ha)	Stocking density (LU/ha)	Tree species	Tree age	Tree density (trees/ha)	Intra-row distance (m)	Alley width (m)	Co-ordinates	Alt. (m)
G1	3.26	0.15	-	NA	-	-	-	37.56277, -7.70089	168
G2	16.90	0.15	-	NA	-	-	-	37.55713, -7.69720	190
G3	1.01	0.15	-	NA	-	-	-	37.55550, -7.69626	203
G4	17.1	0.15	-	NA	-	-	-	37.55875, -7.69830	193
S1	29.20	0.15	<i>P. pinea</i>	28	65	10-20	7-8	37.56418, -7.69005	200
S2	52.80	0.15	<i>P. pinea</i>	28	65	10-20	7-8	37.56297, -7.68266	203
S3	20.90	0.15	<i>P. pinea</i>	28	65	10-20	7-8	37.56097, -7.68223	206
S4	52.80	0.15	<i>P. pinea</i>	28	65	10-20	7-8	37.56376, -7.67991	207
F1	>100	-	<i>P. pinea</i>	31	400-560	3	7	37.57445, -7.69111	180
F2	>100	-	<i>P. pinea</i>	31	400-560	3	7	37.56559, -7.69216	190
F3	>100	-	<i>P. pinea</i>	31	400-560	3	7	37.56184, -7.69891	174
F4	>100	-	<i>P. pinea</i>	31	400-560	3	7	37.55785, -7.69476	202

Figure 34. Clockwise from top left: Earthworm soil core demonstrating shallow soil depth; Forestry transect; Silvopasture transect; Grassland transect.

Bulk density was measured once at each point on the transect (i.e. not at each core taken for the composite sample), using the cylinder method. Soils were very shallow, ranging between 6 and 15 cm in depth, and therefore samples were taken at just one depth (0-10 cm). A rigid cylinder of 6.8 cm diameter and 3.4 cm height (i.e. volume 123.48 cm³) was inserted in the soil. An undisturbed soil sample that was exactly the internal dimension of the cylinder was collected, sieved to <2 mm and oven-dried at 105°C until constant mass was reached. The percentage of particles greater than 2 mm was also calculated based on the weight of sieved particles >2 mm/total weight (Equation 2).

$$\%P_{>2mm} = \frac{P_{>2mm}}{DM} * 100 \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

where $P_{>2mm}$ is the weight of particles above 2 mm (g) and DM is the dry mass (g)

For the measurements of soil organic carbon and pH, because the soils were very shallow, ranging between 6 and 15 cm in depth, samples were taken at just one depth (0-10 cm). At each point on the transect, a composite sample was formed of five cores, spaced 2 m apart, in line with the LUCAS composite sampling strategy. Approximately 500 g of soil was collected, labelled and air-dried before being transported to the laboratory at University of Extremadura (UEX) for subsequent analysis of soil carbon, nitrogen and pH. Soil pH was measured with a glass electrode (soil: water 1:2.5) pH meter (CRISON Basic20, Alella, Spain). Aliquots of 10 g of soil were ground in a ball mill and then analysed in the DUMATHERM® N Pro analyser (C. Gerhardt GmbH & Co. Germany) to determine the soil organic carbon (SOC). Soil carbon stocks (t ha⁻¹) were calculated using the same Equation 1 as used at the Czechia sites.

The density of earthworms was determined from soil cores of 20 cm x 20 cm x 20 cm which were excavated and placed on a tray and hand sorted for earthworms. Initially we planned to take five

points per transect, therefore 3 treatments x 4 transects x 5 points, totalling 60 samples (Table 29). However, as we previously had observed very few/no earthworms in the soils on the farm (only in 'hotspots' of high soil organic matter and moisture), we first carried out one transect per treatment, and on finding no earthworms in any of them, we did not continue sampling. This highlights the limitation of using earthworms as a key indicator in pan-European studies involving semi-arid climates.

Table 29. Summary of number of samples taken per treatment and per soil parameter.

Soil Test	Silvopasture	Forestry	Grassland	Total	Location of analysis
SOC and pH 0-10 cm	20	20	20	60	UEX
Bulk density 0-10c m	20	20	20	60	MVARC
Earthworms	5	5	5	15	MVARC
Soil microbes – MicroBiometer	5	5	5	15	MVARC
Soil microbes – lab analysis	20	20	20	60	VUKOZ

As an alternative measure to earthworms, we also assessed soil microbes, using both an in-situ soil test (the Soil Microbiometer) and lab analyses. We sampled only one transect per treatment as the number of MicroBIOMETER tests were limited. We sampled the top 0-10cm layer where biological activity is assumed to be highest. MicroBIOMETER® is a 20-minute on-site soil test to determine microbial biomass and fungal to bacterial ratio (<https://microbiometer.com/>). The patented method extracts the microbes from the bound soil particles which then settle to the bottom. The soil-coloured microbes remain suspended in the fluid and are sampled. The sample is placed on a testcard which is scanned using a smartphone which measures the colour intensity of the microbes as compared to a colour comparator surround on the testcard. Microbial biomass results are reported as µg of microbial carbon per gram of soil and fungal to bacterial ratio as F:B, F% and B%. Each sample takes at least 25-30 mins (5 mins preparation and results, 20 mins settling time). Soil samples for lab analyses of microbial activity were collected on 7th and 8th October 2025, from the same sampling points as for the SOC analyses (i.e. five points on four transects per treatment = 60 samples in total). Samples were collected from the top 5 cm of soil and kept between 0 and 5°C until analysis.

Statistical analyses

Statistical analyses were performed using R version 4.5.1. The effect of treatment (i.e. habitat type, Forest, Grassland, and Silvopasture) on soil properties was evaluated using linear mixed-effects models (LMMs) via the *lme4* and *lmerTest* packages. To account for the hierarchical structure of the experimental design and avoid pseudo replication, treatment was treated as a fixed effect, while transect was included as a random effect to account for the spatial nesting of the five soil cores collected per transect. Prior to analysis, model assumptions were verified. Normality of residuals was assessed using Shapiro-Wilk tests and Q-Q plots and homogeneity of variance was inspected using Levene's tests and residuals-vs-fitted plots. Where the fixed effect of Treatment was found to be significant ($p < 0.05$), *post-hoc* comparisons were conducted using Tukey's HSD test at a 5% significance level using the *emmeans* package.

The spatial distribution of soil properties with distance from the tree row in the Forest and Silvopasture was analysed separately using a two-way mixed-effects ANOVA to evaluate the influence of treatment (Forest vs. Silvopasture), sampling distance (3.5 m N, 1.5 m N, Tree row, 1.5 m S, and 3.5

m S), and their interaction. To account for the dependency of measurements taken along the same spatial gradient, transect was included as a random effect in the model.

2.7.3. Results

The mean soil bulk density was lowest in grassland and highest in the forest samples, while the particles larger than 2 mm formed between 20% (in the forest) and 25% (in the silvopasture) of the soil core. % nitrogen and carbon were highest in the grassland soils. Carbon stocks were highest in the grassland soils at just under 20 t C ha⁻¹ compared with 16.6 t C ha⁻¹ in the forest and 14.14 t C ha⁻¹ in the silvopasture (Table 30, Figure 35). The only statistically significant difference between treatments was for soil pH ($F = 3.7692$, $p < 0.05$) where the forest soils were significantly lower than the grassland soils (Figure 36).

Table 30. Parameter means (\pm standard error of the mean) per treatment. Letters in parenthesis denote statistically significant differences between treatments.

Treatment	pH	Bulk density (g/cm ³)	>2mm particles (%)	N (%)	C (%)	C stocks (t/ha)
Forest (n= 20)	6.01 ^(a) (0.05)	1.07 (0.05)	20.69 (3.25)	0.14 (0.01)	1.58 (0.27)	16.56 (2.86)
Silvopasture (n= 20)	6.10 ^(ab) (0.09)	1.05 (0.06)	25.22 (3.61)	0.14 (0.01)	1.42 (0.17)	14.14 (1.54)
Grassland (n= 20)	6.25 ^(b) (0.04)	1.00 (0.04)	24.44 (2.99)	0.20 (0.02)	2.00 (0.22)	19.89 (2.34)

Figure 35. Mean soil carbon stocks (\pm SEM) in the forestry, silvopasture and grassland soils

Figure 36. Comparison of soil pH across different habitat types. Boxplots represent the median (horizontal line), the 25th and 75th percentiles (box), and the minimum and maximum values (whiskers).

Within the Forest and Silvopasture treatments, there was a significant difference between sample location and soil carbon content ($p < 0.005$), and soil carbon stocks ($p < 0.01$) (Table 31. Table 31) and Figure 37), but no interaction between treatment and location. The soil carbon content (2.51%) and soil carbon stocks (25.3 t ha^{-1}) were significantly higher at 0 m (i.e. in the tree row than at 1.5 m S (soil carbon = 1.14%, carbon stock = 11.4 t ha^{-1}), 3.5 m S (soil carbon = 1.13%, carbon stock = 11.7 t ha^{-1}) and 3.5 m N (soil carbon = 1.02%, carbon stock = 11.7 t ha^{-1} , Figure 37).

Table 31. Parameter means (\pm standard error of the mean per treatment and location in Portugal).

Location	Treatment	pH	Bulk density (g cm^{-3})	>2mm particles (%)	C (%)	C stocks (t ha^{-1})
3.5 m N	Forest	6.05 (0.13)	1.13 (0.16)	19.37 (9.42)	1.21 (0.24)	13.50 (3.50)
	Silvopasture	6.29 (0.13)	1.18 (0.12)	20.35 (7.70)	0.82 (0.18)	9.87 (2.69)
1.5 m N	Forest	6.09 (0.10)	1.06 (0.14)	19.73 (7.27)	1.77 (0.35)	17.35 (1.46)
	Silvopasture	6.09 (0.17)	1.05 (0.09)	25.66 (5.96)	1.62 (0.35)	16.03 (1.80)
0 m	Forest	5.77 (0.10)	1.05 (0.11)	19.17 (8.73)	3.07 (0.92)	32.98 (10.08)
	Silvopasture	5.96 (0.34)	0.90 (0.11)	26.78 (10.24)	1.95 (0.55)	17.53 (5.61)
1.5 m S	Forest	6.10 (0.15)	1.05 (0.14)	19.55 (7.05)	0.69 (0.13)	7.14 (1.43)
	Silvopasture	6.07 (0.17)	1.01 (0.20)	27.77 (11.29)	1.58 (0.24)	15.67 (3.96)
3.5 m S	Forest	6.07 (0.08)	1.06 (0.07)	25.61 (7.58)	1.14 (0.33)	11.83 (3.24)
	Silvopasture	6.11 (0.17)	1.13 (0.13)	25.54 (8.65)	1.12 (0.31)	11.59 (1.86)

Figure 37. Comparison of soil C stocks across sample locations. Letters above boxplots denote statistically significant differences between treatments. Boxplots represent the median (horizontal line), the 25th and 75th percentiles (box), and the minimum and maximum values (whiskers). Location: 0 m = tree row, 1.5S = 1.5 m South, 3.5S = 3.5 m South, 1.5N = 1.5 m North, 3.5N = 3.5 m North.

Earthworms were not found in the 15 soil cores sampled and so sampling was discontinued. The MicroBIOMETER tests recorded very low microbial biomass and fungal to bacterial ratio for all 15 samples analysed (Table 32); there were some doubts about the accuracy of the tests as in most cases, extra solution needed to be added to the testcard to measure the colour intensity of the microbes as compared to the colour comparator surround, indicating that biomass levels were too low for detection.

Table 32. Effect of vegetation on the microbial biomass and fungi: bacteria ratio using the MicroBIOMETER.

Treatment	Sample	Microbial biomass ($\mu\text{g C/g}$)	Fungi: Bacteria ratio	Fungi %	Bacteria %
Forest	F2/0m	70	0.0:1	3	97
	F2/1.5N	75	0.0:1	3	97
	F2/1.5S	125	0.1:1	10	90
	F2/3.5N	79	0.0:1	3	97
	F2/3.5S	90	0.1:1	6	94
Grassland	G3/0m	70	0.0:1	0	100
	G3/1.5N	52	0.0:1	0	100
	G3/1.5S	99	0.0:1	2	98
	G3/3.5N	52	0.0:1	1	99
	G3/3.5S	153	0.1:1	11	89
Silvopasture	S1/0m	33	0.0:1	1	99
	S1/1.5N	73	0.0:1	3	97
	S1/1.5S	60	0.0:1	2	98
	S1/3.5N	62	0.0:1	2	98
	S1/3.5S	138	0.1:1	11	89

The microbial biomass ranged from 33 to 153 $\mu\text{g C g}^{-1}$ which is well below the 200 to 800 $\mu\text{g C g}^{-1}$ reported by MicroBIOMETER for agricultural soils based on data from their customers. Soils were strongly bacteria-dominated, which is unexpected particularly for forest soils, perhaps again because we were below the detection threshold of the test. However, despite having a wet winter, the soils were already very dry by May (mean 5% soil moisture) and therefore this may have limited microbial activity, leading to low biomass. More samples have been collected in October 2025 and will be analysed in the lab by VUKOZ so we will be able to verify the results of the soil MicroBIOMETER.

2.7.4. Discussion

Only soil pH was found to be significantly different between the three treatments in Portugal, with more acidic soils in the forest compared with the silvopasture and grassland areas. Soil pH influences nutrient cycling and availability, and microbial activity, with more acidic soils potentially reducing phosphorus availability and slowing nitrogen cycling due to a dominance of fungi over bacteria, likely limiting growth of understory vegetation in the Forest, when compared with Silvopasture and Grassland systems.

The soil carbon content and soil carbon stocks in the top 10 cm were highest in the grassland, followed by the forest and silvopasture, although these differences were not statistically significant. These values fall within the range for Mediterranean soils in the Iberian Peninsula. Martinho et al. (2025) reported mean soil C content in Portugal of 1.78% for pine forest, 2.20% for grassland with sparse tree/shrub cover and 2.26% for grassland without tree/shrub cover, and concluded that in general, Portuguese soils have low organic carbon content due to soil features, climate circumstances and land management. A strong limiting factor for soil C stocks in Curralões was the shallowness of the soil, with depths of between only 6 and 15 cm.

Within the forest and silvopasture areas, a significant spatial gradient was observed with soil carbon content and soil carbon stocks within the tree row being more than double those found in the alleys. This effect is consistent with findings by Howlett et al. (2011) in Spanish dehesas, suggesting that trees act as focal points for organic matter accumulation through leaf fall, root turnover, root exudates and reduced soil temperature under the canopy, which slows the decomposition of organic fractions.

2.8. Spain

2.8.1. Site description

The Majadas de Tiétar Research Station (ES) is located in Extremadura region (Spain) 39° 56'25.1"N; 5°46'28.7"W. It is located between 237 – 283 m.a.s.l. and the average slope is 3.6%. It consists of a traditional silvopastoral system called locally Dehesa (Figure 38). The average annual precipitation is 677 mm and mean monthly temperature 17.2°C. The soil is classified as a Dystric Cambisol over Pliocene-Miocene alluvial deposits. In the uppermost soil layer (0-20 cm), the pH ranges between 5.6 – 5.2, mean bulk density is 1.51 g cm⁻³ and soil texture: 3.9% clay, 20.3% silt, 75.8% sand (Table 33).

Table 33. Characterisation data of the Spanish site.

Parameters	Information
Coordinates	39° 56'25.1"N; 5° 46'28.7"W
Farm size	608 ha
Farm type	Non-organic
Production system/s	Livestock
Agroforestry system in place	Yes
Soil type	Dystric Cambisol
Average annual rainfall	677 mm
Mean annual temperature	17.2°C

The main purpose of the site is livestock rearing mainly cattle and sheep. Livestock density is low, leading to a low grazing pressure at the trial site: 0.3 LU ha⁻¹. Majadas de Tiétar Research Station is highly equipped with multiple sensors to measure carbon and water fluxes and environmental variables. An overview of the different variables monitored can be accessed in the following link:

<https://www.bgc-jena.mpg.de/majadas>

Figure 38. Overview of Majadas de Tiétar trial site.

The vegetation of the site is characterized by a permanent grassland layer interspersed with scattered trees. Tree density is about 25 tree ha⁻¹. The main tree species is Holm-oak (*Quercus ilex*), with other tree species, such as Portuguese-oak (*Q. faginea*) and cork-oak (*Q. suber*), also present, but at a lower density (Figure 38). The tree layer is composed mainly by matured individuals with an estimated age

of more than 100 years. The herbaceous layer is dominated by annual species where species such as *Tolpis barbata*, *Gaudinia fragilis*, *Anthoxanthum aristatum*, *Avena barbata*, *Lotus parviflorus* and *Ornithopus compressus* are dominant. The climate of the site is Mediterranean, characterized by strong seasonality with a dry period during summer and wet and mild winter season.

2.8.2. Sampling design and measurements

The sampling design followed an “isolated individual” framework, where the influence of an isolated tree is assessed. Six central trees were selected (Figure 39). Around each central tree, three samples were collected: one located under its canopy, half-way from the tree trunk to the drip line of the canopy, and two samples beyond the tree canopy, in two opposite directions, both points being at the same distance to the tree, but this distance varying between trees to represent half the mean distance to the three nearest trees (Table 34). Sampling points were not located at specific distances related to the root protection area guideline (sensu Aynekulu et al., 2025) because sampling points are part of a long-term assessment of SOC dynamics, and the location is fixed. Soil samples have been taken in the same locations in 2015, 2019 and 2025.

Figure 39. Overview of the sampling point locations depicting the habitat tree (T) or grassland (G).

Table 34. Number of trees and distance to the nearest trees of the sampling points located beyond tree canopies.

Sampling point	Number of trees in a buffer of 15 m radius	Average distance to the three nearest trees (m)	SD distance to the three nearest trees (m)
MQ1G1	2	13.91	2.57
MQ1G2	0	20.31	2.82
MQ2G1	0	20.13	4.94
MQ2G2	1	13.75	3.72
MQ3G1	2	11.46	4.96
MQ3G2	2	12.91	2.45
MQ4G1	1	16.89	3.45
MQ4G2	1	16.45	3.71
MQ5G1	3	11.14	1.16
MQ5G2	2	14.01	6.22
MQ6G1	0	18.62	4.60
MQ6G2	1	15.15	2.55

Soil samples were taken at each point at a depth of 30 cm with an undisturbed liner soil sampler (Eijkelpkamp). The soil sampler has a bayonet connection that allows collecting undisturbed samples in a PVC liner 50 mm in diameter (Figure 40). Intact samples were then divided into 0-5, 5-10, 10-20 and 20-30 cm layers for further processing. Samples were oven dried until reaching constant weight and sieved at 2 mm. The mass of fine soil and coarse fragments greater than 2 mm were weighed separately. Bulk density was calculated for each layer as the ratio between mass of dry soil and sampled volume.

Figure 40. Detail of an intact soil sample collected in the liner.

Soil pH was measured with a glass electrode (soil: water 1:2.5) pH meter (CRISON Basic20, Alella, Spain). For each soil layer, 10 g of soil were ground in a ball mill and then analysed in an elemental analyser DUMATHERM® N Pro analyser (C. Gerhardt GmbH & Co. Germany) to determine soil organic carbon (SOC, %) and total nitrogen (TN, %).

For the earthworm measurements, in a subset of sampling points, on 12 May 2025 and 19 November 2025, soil monoliths of 20 cm x 20cm x 20 cm were excavated under and beyond four tree canopies

(Figure 41). Each sample was laid on a tray and hand sorted. Earthworms were counted and returned to the soil.

Figure 41. Detail of the sampling procedure to excavate soil monoliths.

Community level physiological profiling (CLPP) was used to assess soil microbial functional diversity for the samples collected in spring 2025. This method allows to assess the potential response of the living microbial community (i.e. active and dormant) to substrate addition. Only the samples from the top-soil (0-5 cm) were analysed. This method assesses microbial functional diversity based on the capacity of a soil to decompose multiple carbon substrates with contrasted chemical characteristics. The MicroResp™ methodology was used to conduct CLPP analyses following the manufacturer instructions. In brief, air-dried soil samples were adjusted at 60 % of water holding capacity and pre-incubated during 24h to reactivate soil microbial communities. Subsequently, carbon substances were added and samples were incubated during 6h with de detection plates. Four different substrates (glucose, alanine and gamma-amino butyric acid and oxalic acid) from three chemical classes (sugar, amino-acids and carboxylic acids) were used to produce the respiration rates. Water was also used as control. The sum of all respired substrates per sample (MSIR), corrected by the respiration of samples with only water, was used as an indicator of microbial functional capacity. Relative usage of substrates as compared to MSIR was used to compute a Shannon functional diversity index.

2.8.3. Results

Soil organic carbon

There was a significantly higher carbon stock under (36.3 \pm 14.4 t C ha⁻¹ \pm S.E.) than beyond tree canopies, in open grasslands, (23.8 \pm 7.09 t C ha⁻¹ \pm S.E.), for the full soil profile ($P < 0.001$), until 30 cm depth (Figure 42). There were significant differences among depths that was maintained along the soil profile (no significant interaction between habitat and depth). The carbon stock decreased with soil depth, showing higher differences between habitats in the upper soil layer, being significant from 0 to 5 ($p = 0.004$), and 5 to 10 cm ($p = 0.019$) (Figure 43).

Figure 42. Carbon stock beyond (G) and under tree canopy (T) up to 30 cm depth. Crosses depict average values and \pm SE.

Figure 43. Carbon stock beyond (G) and under tree canopy (T) for each studied soil layer. Crosses depict average values and \pm SE.

Soil pH

Soil pH was acidic in both habitats, being slightly higher beyond tree canopies (5.47 \pm 0.06, mean \pm SE) than under tree canopies (5.34 \pm 0.07, mean \pm SE), but without reaching significant differences ($p = 0.198$).

Soil biodiversity

The number of earthworms found on each habitat was low, tending to be higher, on average, in grassland (4.6 \pm 1.6 earthworms \pm S.E.) than under trees (3.3 \pm 2.4 earthworms \pm S.E.) for each

sampling point, but there were no significant differences in the number of earthworms between habitats. Differences were kept in both seasons, although they were more noticeable in autumn. There was no significant interaction between habitat and season. The total number of earthworms related to the total volume of soil explored tended to be higher in grasslands too (Figure 44).

Figure 44. Effect of habitat and season on the recorded number of earthworms.

2.8.3.1. Soil microbial functional diversity

Basal respiration was on average significantly higher beyond tree canopies ($0.572 \pm 0.027 \mu\text{g CO}_2\text{-C g}^{-1} \text{soil h}^{-1} \pm \text{SE}$) than under tree canopies ($0.572 \pm 0.056 \mu\text{g CO}_2\text{-C g}^{-1} \text{soil h}^{-1} \pm \text{SE}$) ($p = 0.01$). Similarly, multiple induced substrate respiration, after accounting for the effect of water, was also higher beyond tree canopies ($1.71 \pm 0.16 \mu\text{g CO}_2\text{-C g}^{-1} \text{soil h}^{-1} \pm \text{SE}$) than under tree canopies ($1.24 \pm 0.40 \mu\text{g CO}_2\text{-C g}^{-1} \text{soil h}^{-1} \pm \text{SE}$), but without reaching significant differences. By contrast, Shannon diversity tended to be higher under trees than beyond canopies, but without reaching significant differences. (Figure 45).

Figure 45. Basal respiration, multiple substrates induced respiration (MSIR) and Shannon diversity index, based on relative microbial substrate usage of soils beyond (G) and under tree canopy (T) up to 5 cm depth. Crosses depict average values and \pm SE.

2.8.4. Discussion

The potential of trees, and other woody species, to modify soil properties in Mediterranean dehesas has been extensively studied (Rolo et al., 2023). In general, these studies have shown that trees create spatial heterogeneity in the system and can alter chemical, biological and physical soil properties (Gallardo, 2003). This pattern has been shown to be consistent with other grazed grasslands in semi-arid ecosystems, where woody elements create fertile islands, being key for the delivery of ecosystem services related to decomposition, soil fertility and soil and water conservation (Eldridge et al., 2024).

Our results agree with this general pattern, although, in our case, net effects of trees were weaker. The strongest positive effect was observed on SOC stock. SOC stocks values are in accordance with previous studies in the dehesa. For instance, Pulido-Fernandez et al. (2013) reported higher SOC stock values in dehesa ($\sim 40 \text{ t ha}^{-1}$) than in open grasslands ($\sim 20 \text{ t ha}^{-1}$). They also found that main SOC stocks were found in the top-soil. Simón et al. (2013) also reported a positive spatial auto-correlation between canopy cover and SOC stocks, showing that tree effects could be extended beyond tree canopies up to a distance equal to the crown radius.

Soil biological activity is a fundamental component of soil health. Earthworm abundance was slightly lower under trees than in open areas, particularly in autumn. Previous research on earthworm diversity in dehesas has also reported a negative effect of woody habitats (Moreno et al., 2015). The authors suggested that a potential reduction of soil moisture under trees could limit the presence of earthworms. This would agree with the higher reduction observed in autumn, at the onset of the rainy season.

Soil respiration can provide valuable information on the potential of a soil to cycle nutrients, decompose organic matter, or stabilize soil processes. Key mediators of these fluxes are soil microbes, and the level of respiration is commonly linked to the abundance and composition of microbes. Our results showed lower basal respiration and multiple substrate-induced respiration (MSIR) under trees than in open grasslands. These results are in disagreement with previous research that showed lower basal respiration in pastures than in cork oak forest (Francaviglia et al., 2017). Smith et al. (2021) also reported that the basal respiration was decoupled from microbial biomass, its main driver. These results together with the slightly lower values of Shannon diversity as compared to trees, points to the dominance of a particular microbial group driving soil respiration in open areas.

2.9. United Kingdom

2.9.1. Site description

Clapham Park is situated within the urban edge of the county town of Bedford in Eastern England. In the 1860s, the fields comprised part of Clapham Park Estate and a house was at the centre of the Estate in 1872. Although the house is still privately owned, the surrounding agricultural land, including the wood, is now owned by Bedfordshire County Council. The Council leases the land on an annual basis to a livestock farmer.

The climate is characterised by an average annual rainfall of 652 mm and average maximum and minimum temperatures of 14.4°C and 6.1°C respectively (UK Meteorological Office, 2025) (Table 35). The soil at Clapham is described as 'lime-rich loamy and clayey soil with impeded drainage' (LandIS, 2025). Particle size distribution analyses revealed a predominantly clay texture, with 26% sand, 32% silt and 42% clay (Upson, 2014).

Table 35. Description of the climate at Bedford (1991-2020) (UK Meteorological Office, 2026).

Month	Maximum temperature (°C)	Minimum temperature (°C)	Sunshine (hours)	Rainfall (mm)
January	7.4	1.6	53	55
February	9.0	1.5	73	45
March	10.6	2.7	115	40
April	13.8	4.1	152	48
May	16.9	6.8	191	52
June	20.0	9.8	186	54
July	22.4	11.9	198	51
August	22.1	12.0	185	59
September	19.0	9.7	142	55
October	14.7	7.3	104	71
November	10.3	4.1	62	65
December	7.7	1.8	48	58
Annual mean	14.4	6.1		
Annual total			1509	652

In February 1998, as part of an EU supported 'Bedfordshire Farm Woodland Demonstration' project, within the same field, 7.34 ha of grassland was planted to a silvopastoral system, and 6.84 ha was planted to a mixed woodland (Burgess et al., 2000) (Figure 46; Table 36). The owner of Clapham Park, Bedfordshire County Council, specified landscape, wildlife, public recreation, and education as four principal objectives for the planting scheme (Burgess et al., 2000). In terms of management, pathways are mown within the woodland area to create footpaths. A local cattle farmer is granted access to graze the silvopastoral area most of the season (Upson, 2014).

Figure 46. Map showing the location of each of the woodland systems planted at Clapham Park, Bedford (1 cm = 65 m).

The silvopastoral areas were planted with 30 groups of 16 trees, and four groups of 75 trees in block, initially surrounded by a stock-proof fence (Table 36). Although the stock-proof fence remained in position for the initial years, 14 years after planting the cattle were able to access the areas between the trees.

Table 36. Description of the species planted and the tree density in the silvopasture and woodland area planted in the southern section of Clapham Park in February 1998 (Burgess et al., 2002).

Unit	Area (ha)	Principal objectives	Species composition	Tree arrangements
1&2	7.34	silvo-pastoral system, amenity, restoration of landscape, timber production	Silvo-pastoral system averaging 100 trees per hectare, in groups as follows: 40% oak, 30% ash 10% hornbeam 10% small-leaved lime 10% field maple	4 groups of 75 trees 30 groups of 16 trees, 6-half standard hornbeam trees. Within the groups trees are spaced at 2 m x 2 m. (The actual area covered by trees is approximately 0.30 ha).
3	0.40	riparian system for wildlife	Riparian system 50% alder, 30% goat willow, and 20% open space.	Planted at a 2 m spacing on the drier peripheral ground, leaving the wet ground and standing water area open
4	6.85	landscape, amenity, wildlife	Mixed-broadleaf 30% ash, 10% oak, 10% wild cherry, 10% small-leaved lime, 20% 'shrub mixture' 20% open ground to form footpaths, rides and glades.	Fenced; principally 2.5 x 2.5 m spacing

2.9.2. Sampling design and measurements

In 2012, 14 years after planting, an intensive set of soil samples were taken at Clapham Park as part of a PhD programme (Upson, 2014). The results of that study were reported in a paper by Upson et al. (2016). In that study, soil samples were taken at depths of 0-10, 10-20, 20-40, 60-80, 80-100, and 100-120 cm.

In September 2025, 27 years after planting, soil samples were again taken at the site. However the intensity of measurements was less than in 2012. A set of ten locations in each of the mixed-broadleaf woodland, the grassland areas within the silvopastoral area, and the wooded areas within the silvopastoral area were selected (Figure 47) (Table 36). At each site, samples of soil for bulk density, and for pH and soil carbon were taken at depths of 0-10, 10-20, and 20-40 cm.

This number of points was selected finding a balance between expected change in soil organic carbon and total number of samples generated. Sampling points were selected among the grid sampling points used in the previous 2016 study, comprising overall evenly spaced points for the particular case of silvopasture, points both belonging to big and small clusters of trees (Upson et al., 2016) (Table 37). In a similar way to Upson et al. (2016), three additional points were also chosen in a nearby mature woodland.

Figure 47. Location of sampling points at Clapham Park in 2025 (Grey: silvopastoral - under tree, green with animal: pasture outside the trees, orange: woodland, brown: mature forest).

Table 37. Co-ordinates of the sampling points at Clapham Park.

System	Plot ID	Co-ordinates (X)	Co-ordinates (Y)	System	Plot ID	Co-ordinates (X)	Co-ordinates (Y)
Pasture	PA 3	504493	252605	Silvopastoral	SP 1	504522	252605
Pasture	PA 8	504583	252575	Silvopastoral	SP 3	504619	252584
Pasture	PA 10	504553	252545	Silvopastoral	SP 8	504567	252519
Pasture	PA 15	504523	252485	Silvopastoral	SP 12	504520	252444
Pasture	PA 17	504553	252455	Silvopastoral	SP 16	504576	252427
Pasture	PA 23	504343	252455	Silvopastoral	SP 20	504395	252473
Pasture	PA 25	504283	252425	Silvopastoral	SP 24	504326	252402
Pasture	PA 27	504373	252425	Silvopastoral	SP 26	504384	252370
Pasture	PA 30	504305	252382	Silvopastoral	SP 30	504245	252398
Pasture	PA 36	504433	252365	Silvopastoral	SP 34	504422	252314
Woodland	FW 1	504493	252365	Mature forest	MF 1	504153	252269
Woodland	FW 3	504643	252365	Mature forest	MF 2	504141	252182
Woodland	FW 5	504543	252315	Mature forest	MF 3	504131	252263
Woodland	FW 6	504593	252315	Mature forest	MF 1	504153	252269
Woodland	FW 9	504543	252265				
Woodland	FW 10	504593	252265				
Woodland	FW 13	504543	252215				
Woodland	FW 15	504643	252215				
Woodland	FW 16	504543	252165				
Woodland	FW 20	504462	252135				

The field samples were collected over two days on 25 and 26 September 2025 by a group of 8 volunteers (Figure 48). The sample sites were located using GPS on a smart phone and initially marked with flags attached to a metal rod.

Measuring bulk density

The first person at the site removed the existing ground vegetation and any litter. Two platforms were then created at a depth of 12.5 cm (to allow a soil sample to be taken at 12.5-17.5 cm) and 37.5 cm (to allow a bulk density sample to be taken at 37.5-40.5 cm). The bulk density samples were collected using the ring (core) method (FAO 2023). This comprised hammering an open ring (diameter of 50 mm) so that the soil became flush with the open surface. The samples were then placed into pre-labelled bags. The samples were placed in plastic bags on site and stored in a cool room until laboratory measurements could be taken on 9 October 2025. The laboratory analysis included an assessment of the wet weight of the soil and the dry weight after oven drying at $105^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ for a minimum period of 24 hours, as indicated by Cranfield University (2020) Standard Operating Procedure 0025 (version 1) for soil bulk density.

A) Samples from the pasture area

B) Soil sampling in the silvopastoral tree area

C) Soil sampling in the woodland area

Figure 48. Soil sampling at Clapham Park Wood (25-26 September 2025).

Measuring pH and soil carbon content

Using the pits created for measuring the bulk density, soil samples were taken at a mean depth of 5 cm, 15 cm, and 30 cm, equating to the mid-point of 0-10, 10-20, and 20-40 cm. At each depth, two separate samples were taken and placed in pre-labelled bags. The pH of the soil was determined in the laboratory at Cranfield University. The total soil content was determined using the Standard Operating Practice for soil organic matter. Unfortunately the Elementar Analyser at Cranfield University was broken from December 2025 to January 2026, and hence the measurements were performed with a smaller scale Elementar Analyser at the University of Leeds. Although it was possible to process the samples prepared for measurement of total carbon, it was not possible to process the samples prepared for the measurements of total organic carbon as the samples were too large.

Earthworm count

For this, the excavated soil from each monolith (20 cm x 20 cm x 20 cm) was placed on a white plastic sheet and earthworms were manually counted, using the procedure described by UKCEH (2020).

Visual examination of soil structure

A visual evaluation of soil structure (VESS) was completed on many (but not all) of the plots, using the procedure described by Cloy et al. (2012) and promoted in the United Kingdom by AHDB (2025). The VESS assessment was made from the soil sample produced for the earthworm count. The soil structure was rated on a five point scale from 1 (good - crumbly), 2 (good - intact), 3 (moderate - firm), 4 (poor - compact) and 5 (poor - very compact).

Statistical analyses

In order to analyse the results obtained from the soil sampling at Clapham Park, we used an ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) test to check if there were statistically significant differences between the means of each variable for our treatments i.e. pasture, woodland, silvopasture. Then the mean values of each variable are presented for all treatments. The results are structured presenting the results for bulk density first, followed by pH and carbon.

2.9.3. Results

Bulk density

In 2025, the bulk density across the three treatments increased ($p = <0.001$) with depth, and there was also a vegetation x depth ($p = 0.059$) interaction (Table 38). The mean bulk density at the site ranged from 1.10 g cm^{-3} at 0-10 cm to 1.27 g cm^{-3} at 20-40 cm (Table 39). The unweighted mean soil bulk density below the pasture (1.24 g cm^{-3}) was higher than that below the woodland and silvopastoral trees (1.19 g cm^{-3}) which were similar (Table 5). The high mean bulk density in the pasture area was caused by high bulk densities below a depth of 10 cm; by contrast the bulk density of the grass was less than in the woodland in the top 10 cm. Some of the bulk density effects could be related to the moisture content as the moisture content varied with vegetation, depth, and there was significant interaction (Table 38). Whereas the mean moisture content of the three vegetations were similar at 10-40 cm, the moisture content in the top 10 cm of pasture was higher (perhaps related to recent rainfall), whereas the rain had not permeated through the tree canopies. There is a strong negative relationship between soil bulk density and the soil water content (Figure 49).

Table 38. Analysis of variance of the effect of the vegetation and depth on bulk density and moisture content with degrees of freedom, p values and partial eta squared (proportion of variance explained).

Variate	Effect	df	Residual df	p	Partial eta squared
Bulk density	Vegetation	2	81	0.435	0.02
	Depth	2	81	< 0.001	0.18
	Vegetation : Depth	4	81	0.059	0.10
Moisture	Vegetation	2	81	0.013	0.10
	Depth	2	81	< 0.001	0.47
	Vegetation : Depth	4	81	0.043	0.11

Table 39. Mean values of soil bulk density and moisture content in the pasture, silvopastoral trees, woodland, and with values for a mature woodland in italics.

Depth (cm)	Soil bulk density (g cm ⁻³)				
	Pasture (n = 10)	Silvopastoral trees (n=10)	Woodland (n=10)	Mean (n=30)	Mature woodland (n=3)
0-10	1.04	1.10	1.17	1.10	1.02
10-20	1.33	1.21	1.18	1.24	1.23
20-40	1.34	1.26	1.22	1.27	1.18
Mean	1.24	1.19	1.19	1.21	1.14
Soil moisture content (wet basis) (g g ⁻¹)					
0-10	0.23	0.18	0.19	0.20	0.23
10-20	0.15	0.15	0.15	0.15	0.15
20-40	0.15	0.15	0.15	0.15	0.13
Mean	0.18	0.16	0.17	0.17	0.17

Bulk density: Standard error of the difference (Sed) between vegetation means = 0.04 g cm⁻³; sed between depth means = 0.04 g cm⁻³, and sed between vegetation x depth means = 0.07 g cm⁻³.

Moisture: Sed between vegetation means = 0.006 g g⁻¹; sed between depth means = 0.006 g g⁻¹, and sed between vegetation x depth means = 0.011 g g⁻¹.

Figure 49. Relationship between moisture content and bulk density for a clay soil.

Soil pH

The mean soil pH (measured in KCl) across the three vegetations ranged from 7.69 to 8.07. There was no effect ($p = 0.117$) of vegetation, and the pH tended ($p = 0.092$) to increase with depth from 7.68 at 0-10 cm to 8.06 at 20-40 cm (Table 40; Table 41). The pH in the mature woodland area tended to be higher than in the main area of the site.

Table 40. Analysis of variance of the effect of the vegetation and depth on pH with degrees of freedom, p values and partial eta squared (proportion of variance explained).

Variate	Effect	df	Residual df	p	Partial eta squared
pH	Vegetation	2	81	0.117	0.05
	Depth	2	81	0.092	0.06
	Vegetation : Depth	4	81	0.968	0.01

The mean level of stones (> 2 mm) across the site was less than 2%. There was a tendency for the portion of stone to be higher in the woodland, than the silvopasture area (Table 41). The mean level of roots in the soil samples tended to be lower in the pasture area (0.02%) than in the woodland areas (0.08-0.12%) (Table 41).

Table 41. Mean values of soil pH (KCl), the percentage weight of stones, and roots (> 2 mm) in the pasture, silvopastoral trees, woodland, with results from a mature woodland in italics.

Depth (cm)	Soil pH in KCl				
	Pasture (n=10)	Silvopastoral trees (n=10)	Woodland (n=10)	Mean (n=30)	Mature woodland (n=3)
0-10	7.67	7.47	7.89	7.68	8.47
10-20	7.90	7.81	8.08	7.93	8.36
20-40	8.17	7.79	8.22	8.06	8.87
Mean	7.91	7.69	8.07	7.89	8.57
Proportion of stones by weight (%)					
0-10	0.14	0.48	0.06	0.23	1.41
10-20	0.99	1.16	3.94	2.03	3.25
20-40	1.52	1.83	2.66	2.00	1.11
Mean	0.88	1.16	2.22	1.42	1.92
Proportion of roots (> 2 mm) by weight (%)					
0-10	0.04	0.09	0.06	0.06	0.02
10-20	0.00	0.13	0.08	0.07	0.19
20-40	0.02	0.13	0.06	0.07	0.03
Mean	0.02	0.12	0.07	0.07	0.08

pH: Sed between vegetation means = 0.18; sed between depth means = 0.18 g cm⁻³, and sed between vegetation x depth means = 0.31.

Total soil carbon

An analysis of variance indicates that there was no effect of vegetation ($p = 0.181$), but that the total carbon declined ($p < 0.001$) with depth (Table 42).

Table 42. Analysis of variance of the effect of the vegetation and depth on pH with degrees of freedom (df), p values and partial eta squared (proportion of variance explained).

Variate	Effect	df	Residual df	p	Partial eta squared
Total carbon	Vegetation	2	81	0.181	0.04
	Depth	2	81	<0.001	0.44
	Vegetation : Depth	4	81	0.909	0.01

The total carbon content declined from 5.89% in the surface layer (0-10 cm), to 3.86% at 10-20 cm, and 3.22% at 20-40 cm) (Table 43). Whereas Upson et al. (2016) reported higher carbon levels in the pasture than below the trees 14 years after planting (Table 44), 27 years after planting there was no difference in total carbon content between the pasture and the silvopastoral trees. However, as with Upson et al. (2016) there was a tendency ($p = 0.181$) for the woodland to have lower total carbon content than the silvopasture trees. The levels of nitrogen generally showed the same pattern as the total carbon, and the C/N ratio in the silvopasture area (10.1-10.6:1), with a tendency for higher C:N ratio moving from the 27 year old woodland to the mature woodland.

Table 43. Mean values of total soil carbon, nitrogen and the carbon to nitrogen ratio (C/N) in the pasture, silvopastoral trees, woodland, with results from a mature woodland in italics.

Depth (cm)	Total carbon (g (100 g) ⁻¹)				
	Pasture (n=10)	Silvopastoral trees (n=10)	Woodland (n=10)	Mean (n=30)	Mature woodland (n=3)
0-10	6.24	6.12	5.31	5.89	10.98
10-20	4.03	4.08	3.48	3.86	7.58
20-40	3.15	3.44	3.07	3.22	6.75
Mean	4.47	4.55	3.95	4.32	8.44
Depth (cm)	Total nitrogen (g (100 g) ⁻¹)				
	Pasture (n=10)	Silvopastoral trees (n=10)	Woodland (n=10)	Mean (n=30)	Mature woodland (n=3)
0-10	0.62	0.57	0.50	0.56	0.84
10-20	0.41	0.38	0.30	0.36	0.50
20-40	0.30	0.32	0.27	0.30	0.38
Mean	0.44	0.42	0.36	0.41	0.57
Depth (cm)	Carbon to nitrogen ratio				
	Pasture (n=10)	Silvopastoral trees (n=10)	Woodland (n=10)	Mean (n=30)	Mature woodland (n=3)
0-10	10.1	10.6	10.6	10.4	13.1
10-20	9.7	10.7	11.6	10.7	15.2
20-40	10.6	10.5	11.5	10.9	18.2
Mean	10.1	10.6	11.2	10.7	15.5

Total carbon: Sed between vegetation means = 0.35 g (100 g)⁻¹; sed between depth means = 0.35 g (100 g)⁻¹, and sed between vegetation x depth means = 0.60 g (100 g)⁻¹

Table 44. Mean values of soil **organic carbon** in 2012 (derived from Upson et al. (2016)).

Depth (cm)	Soil organic carbon (g (100 g) ⁻¹)			
	Pasture (n=40)	Silvopastoral trees (n=20)	Woodland (n=20)	Mature woodland (n=3)
0-10	6.0	5.3	4.6	7.5
10-20	3.2	3.2	2.8	3.9
20-40	2.1	2.0	1.8	1.8

Earthworm and visual examination of soil structure

The number of earthworms recorded was very low and this was associated with dry soil conditions. The highest earthworm numbers occurred in the woodland (Table 45). There was a higher level of earthworms in the surface layer of the pasture than below the silvopastoral trees, and this could have been related to the slightly wetter soil conditions (Table 39).

The highest score for the visual examination of soil structure was observed in the mature woodland where a score of 1.2 is close to a score of 1 which is for a 'good crumbly' soil. The woodland received a score of 2.8 which is between a score of 2 for a 'good intact' soil, and 3 for a 'moderate firm' soil. The pasture and silvopasture trees soils received a rating of 3.8 which is close to a score of 4 for a 'poor compact' soil.

Table 45. Mean values of the number of earthworms and a qualitative score for a visual examination of soil structure (VESS).

	Pasture (n=10)	Silvopasture trees (n=10)	Woodland (n=10)	Mature woodland (n=3)
Earthworms (no / 80 dm ³)	1.0	0.1	1.9	1.7
VESS	3.8	3.8	2.8	1.2

2.9.4. Discussion

The results from the UK site were compared with the results from the UKCEH soil health tool and previous measurements taken at the site.

Bulk density

To allow comparison with the UKCEH Soil Health Tools, the results were weighted to determine a mean value for a soil depth of 0-15 cm. The soil at Clapham Park has a higher bulk density than the mid-point value reported by UKCEH (2022) for improved grassland and broadleaf woodland land covers on heavy clayey soils with an annual rainfall of 650 mm (Table 46; Figure 50).

Table 46. Measured bulk density (0-15 cm) for the four land covers at Clapham compared to UKCEH dataset values for two land covers on a heavy clay soil and low rainfall.

Measured soil bulk density (g cm ⁻³)				UKCEH bulk density		
Pasture	Silvopastoral trees	Woodland	Mature woodland	Improved grassland	Broadleaf woodland	
				Below typical	<0.7	<0.3
1.14	1.14	1.17	1.09	Mid-point	0.9	0.8
				Above typical	>1.3	>1.0

a) Comparison with improved grassland

b) Comparison with broadleaf woodland

Figure 50. Comparison of the measured bulk density (0-15 cm) with the distribution for a) improved grassland and b) broadleaf woodland on a heavy clay soil in the UK, with an annual rainfall of 650 mm.

Soil acidity

The soil at Clapham Park is more alkali than most grassland and broadleaf woodland on clayey soils (Table 47; Figure 51).

Table 47. Measured pH values (0-15 cm) for the four land covers at Clapham compared to UKCEH dataset values for two land covers on a heavy clay soil and low rainfall.

Pasture	Measured pH (KCl)				UKCEH pH dataset	
	Silvopastoral trees	Woodland	Mature woodland		Improved grassland	Broadleaf woodland
7.7	7.6	8.0	8.4	Below typical	<5.5	<4.0
				Mid-point	6.8	5.1
				Above typical	>8.1	>5.9

A) Improved grassland on heavy clay

B) Broadleaf woodland on heavy clay

Figure 51. Comparison of the measured pH compared with the UKCEH (2022) soil dataset for a) improved grassland and b) broadleaf woodland on a heavy clay soil and low rainfall (650 mm).

Soil organic matter

The mid-point for soil organic matter of the UKCEH distribution curve for heavy clay soils on improved grassland and a rainfall of 650 mm is 9.1%, with below and above typical at 6.1 and 15.3%. For a broadleaf woodland with the same soil type and rainfall, the mid-point is 10.5%, with lower and upper 10% values of 8.1% and 33.5% (Table 48). Unfortunately, because measured organic carbon values were not available, to enable an initial comparison we assumed that the soil organic matter was twice the total carbon level. On this basis, the assumed indicative soil organic carbon was in line with what could be anticipated for the clayey soil in a low rainfall area (Figure 52).

Table 48. Indicative soil organic content values (0-15 cm) for the four land covers at Clapham compared to UKCEH dataset values for two land covers on a heavy clay soil and low rainfall.

Indicative soil organic matter (g (100 g ⁻¹))				UKCEH SOM dataset	
Pasture	Silvopastoral trees	Woodland	Mature woodland	Improved grassland	Broadleaf woodland
11.0	10.9	9.4	19.7	Below typical <6.1	<8.1
				Mid-point 9.1	10.5
				Above typical >15.3	>33.5

A) Improved grassland on heavy clay (annual rainfall = 650 mm)

B) Broadleaf woodland on heavy clay (annual rainfall = 650 mm)

Figure 52. Comparison of the assumed soil organic matter (0-15 cm) compared with the distribution for a) improved grassland and b) broadleaf woodland on a heavy clay soil in the UK, with an annual rainfall of 650 mm.

Earthworms

The number of earthworms recorded at the field site was substantially lower than reported in the UKCEH dataset for a similar land cover, soil type and rainfall (Table 49; Figure 53). The UKCEH data guidance indicates that “Sampling should take place in spring and/or autumn when conditions are not dry” (UKCEH, 2022). Singh et al. (2019) in a review of the response of earthworms to climate indicate that earthworm abundance is greatest during wet periods of the year. The readings at Clapham were taken after rainfall, but towards the end of a dry summer.

Table 49. Measured earthworm abundance for the four land covers at Clapham compared to UKCEH dataset values for two land covers on a heavy clay soil and low rainfall.

Earthworm abundance (number (8 dm) ⁻³)				UKCEH worm dataset	
Pasture	Silvopastoral trees	Woodland	Mature woodland	Improved grassland	Broadleaf woodland
1.0	0.1	1.9	1.7	Below typical	<3.4
				Mid-point	17.0
				Above typical	>31.4
					<2.0
					5.1
					>9.9

A) Improved grassland on heavy clay (annual rainfall = 650 mm)

B) Broadleaf woodland on heavy clay (annual rainfall = 650 mm)

Figure 53. Comparison of the measured number of earthworms (20 x 20 x 20 cm) compared with the distribution for a) improved grassland and b) broadleaf woodland on a heavy clay soil in the UK, with an annual rainfall of 650 mm.

2.10. Overall discussion

2.10.1. Soil organic carbon

We decided to only compare the results obtained from the analysis of soil samples across the eight sites using the percentage of soil organic carbon content, not the soil carbon stocks. It is not recommended to compare carbon stocks because carbon stocks are not only affected by carbon content but also by bulk density. Hence soils with a higher bulk density can have a higher carbon stock but this does not necessarily indicate a healthier soil because increased bulk density can be a sign of soil compaction, e.g. a soil that is regularly driven over with a tractor. This is the reason why we decided to focus our attention more on carbon content (% carbon per soil mass unit), because we consider it a truer indicator.

Effect of vegetation and duration of vegetation

Across the eight case studies, the presence of permanent vegetation - trees or shrubs - generally resulted in higher soil organic carbon concentrations compared to arable or open-field controls. (Table 50).

Table 50. Effect of site, vegetation, and soil depth on soil carbon levels, with sites listed according to the maximum reported soil carbon content. At each site and depth the highest soil carbon content (which may or may not be statistically different from other values) is indicated in bold.

Site	Mean temp (°C)	Established	Soil depth (cm)	Soil carbon content (g (100 g) ⁻¹).					
				Arable control	Grass control	Middle of cropped alley	Silvo-pasture grass	Beneath agrofor' tree area	Forest control
Finland ^a (Sammallahti)	4	Pre-1925	0-20		3.67			13.66	11.11
			20-40		2.80			4.50	
UK ^b (Bedford)	10	1998	0-10				6.24	6.12	5.31
			10-20				4.03	4.08	3.48
			20-40				3.15	3.44	3.07
Netherlands (Stoutenburg)	11	2022	0-30			2.25		2.13	
			30-60			1.09		1.03	
Germany (Silvoarable) ^c (Silvopasture) ^d	10	2015	0-30			2.89		3.35	
		2016	0-30				10.58	12.11	
Czechia (Jagava)	8	2015-2017	0-15	1.20		1.10		1.50	
			15-30	0.70		0.90		1.10	
			30-40	0.30		0.40		0.90	
Czechia (Gregorovič) ^e	8	2010	0-10	1.06		0.99		1.76	
			10-20	0.94		0.97		1.16	
			20-40	0.68		0.65		0.84	
			40-60	0.45		0.46		0.64	
Italy ^f (Arnino)	15	2017	0-10	1.40		1.38		1.63	
			10-30	1.03		1.16		0.82	
Spain (Extremadura)	17	Pre-1925	0-5				2.48	5.72	
			5-10				0.83	2.11	
			10-20				0.61	1.05	
			20-30				0.49	0.97	
Portugal (Curralões)	18	1994	0-10		2.00			1.53	1.42

^aForest control is on a mature pre-1925 woodland; grass control is from permanent grass with sheep

^bValues are for total carbon.

^cBeneath agroforestry tree values taken 1.5 m from the tree in the cultivated area.

^dBeneath agroforestry tree values taken 3 m from the tree.

^eValues based on total organic carbon

^fThe arable control includes a seven year rotation of three years of arable crops and four years of mixed temporary grassland

One site, where the soil organic content were not highest beneath the trees was in the Netherlands, where the trees had only been planted four years earlier in 2022 into a grassland field. At the UK site, the total carbon content beneath the tree and grass areas in a silvopastoral area, planted in 1998 and therefore 27 years after planting, were similar. However this compares with a situation, 14 years after planting, where the soil organic carbon was lower beneath the trees than in the pasture areas of the

silvopastoral treatment (Upson et al., 2016). Upson et al. (2016) proposed that pasture can result in substantial inputs of carbon, and it can take several years for trees to establish and attain a similar or greater level of inputs with trees. At the Spanish site, which was subject to high temperatures, the levels of soil organic carbon was higher directly beneath the trees rather than in the grassland areas of a dehesa system. The situation at the Portuguese site also requires explanation. At that site, new woodlands were planted in 1994, and in a similar way to the results reported by Upson et al. (2016), the level of soil carbon beneath the trees remains below that in an area that has been maintained as pasture.

Effect of site

There was a substantial range in the measured levels of soil carbon ranging from 1.42% in the forest control in Portugal to 11.11-13.66% in the forest control and grazed forest treatment in Finland. De Rosa et al. (2024) analysed the soil results collected across Europe as part of the Land Use/Cover Area Frame Survey (LUCAS) in 2009, 2015 and 2018. These results have been used to create European maps of soil organic stocks (Lugato et al., 2014) and changes in soil carbon (De Rosa et al., 2024). Rial et al. (2017) used the LUCAS dataset to create a map of soil organic carbon content across Europe, which also shows high soil organic carbon levels in the north (such as Finland) to low values in the south (such as in Portugal) (Figure 54). The principal factors identified in determining the soil carbon content included the temperature, the aridity, the pH, and the vegetation cover (Rial et al., 2017).

Figure 54. Map of the predicted soil organic carbon content (0-20 cm) across Europe, derived from LUCAS data (Rial et al., 2017).

Methods of measuring soil carbon content

There are a range of methods for measuring soil carbon content. Within this report, soil carbon was determined using the high temperature dry combustion (Dumas) method, which is recognised as a standard method for determining soil carbon (Chatterjee et al., 2009). However the process requires

specialised equipment, which can be easily damaged. For example, the elemental analyser at Cranfield University was broken during this study, and a replacement elemental analyser was used. The difference between total carbon and soil organic carbon is determined by the application of acid to remove the inorganic carbon. Under acidic soil conditions, such as in Germany and Finland, the values for total carbon and total organic carbon are likely to be similar as it is unlikely that carbon is in inorganic form (carbonates).

In the determination of soil health, the establishment of rapid, cheap, and accurate soil carbon and soil organic carbon measurement remains a holy grail. However, soil measurements, combined with a benchmarking tool, can still provide useful learning insights for farmers and advisors. A low cost method of determining soil carbon is the loss of ignition method, but the correlation between the carbon values determined by this method with those derived from Dumas can be as low as 34% (Ng et al., 2025). There is also a tendency for the calculated values to be higher. Within specific regions, it is possible to find correlations between measurements of soil organic carbon and other variable such as near-infrared spectroscopy (NIRS) (Ng et al., 2025). The correlation between NIRS determined and Dumas determined values can range from 30% (Ng et al., 2025) to 95% (Ng et al., 2022). In addition to the challenge of measuring soil carbon and soil organic carbon, Lavalley et al. (2019) recommend that it may increasingly be useful to differentiate between particulate organic matter (POM) and mineral-associated organic matter (MAOM) forms. Whereas the mineral-associated organic matter is generally resistant to oxidation, particulate organic matter can break down rapidly.

2.10.2. Acidity

The pH ranged from 3.8 in the forest soils in Finland to 8.2-8.4 for the site in Italy (Table 51). In general there was minimal effect of vegetation or agroforestry practice on the level of pH. The exception was in Finland where the level of acidity in the forested area (3.8) was substantially greater than in the grass control area (5.1-5.3). This difference may be due to bio-acidification associated with conifers (Westman and Jauhiainen, 1998).

2.10.3. Bulk density

Across the sites, there was not a consistent effect of vegetation on soil bulk density. However in the mature systems in Finland and Spain, the bulk density in the tree area tended to be less than in the grazed or pasture areas (Table 52). An explanation for the lower bulk density in forests is that low bulk densities are closely associated with high levels of soil organic matter (Tamminen and Starr, 1994).

Table 51. Effect of site, vegetation, and soil depth on pH, with sites ranked according to the pH level.

Site	Established	Soil depth (cm)	pH					
			Arable control	Grass control	Middle cropped alley	Silvo-pasture grass	Beneath agrofor' tree	Forest control
Finland (Sammallahti)	Pre-1925	0-20		5.10			3.83	3.80
		20-40		5.28			3.82	
Germany (Silvoarable)	2015	0-30				5.90	5.60	
	(Silvopastoral) 2016	0-30				4.77	4.94	
Netherlands (Stoutenburg)	2022	0-30			5.43		5.37	
		30-60			5.42		5.37	
Spain (Extremadura)	Pre-1925	0-5				5.55	5.58	
		5-10				5.38	5.04	
		10-20				5.45	5.29	
		20-30				5.50	5.43	
Portugal	1994	0-10		6.25			6.10	6.01
UK (Bedford)	1998	0-10				7.67	7.47	7.68
		10-20				7.90	7.81	8.08
		20-40				8.17	7.79	8.22
Italy (Arnino)	2017	0-10	8.25		8.27		8.25	
		10-30	8.37		8.38		8.31	

Table 52. Effect of site, vegetation, and soil depth on soil bulk density levels, ranking from low to higher bulk densities in the surface layer.

Site	Established	Soil depth (cm)	Soil bulk density (g cm ⁻³)					
			Arable control	Grass control	Middle cropped alley	Silvo-pasture grass	Beneath agrofor' tree	Forest control
Finland ^a (Sammallahti)	Pre-1925	0-20		0.95			0.38	0.60
		20-40		1.18			0.67	
Spain (Extremadura)	Pre-1925	0-5				1.18	0.94	
		5-10				1.52	1.43	
		10-20				1.54	1.34	
		20-30				1.43	1.43	
Portugal (Curralões)	1994	0-10		1.00			1.05	1.07
UK (Bedford)	1998	0-10				1.04	1.10	1.17
		10-20				1.33	1.21	1.18
		20-40				1.34	1.26	1.22
Germany (Silvoarable)	2015	0-30			1.42		1.34	
	(Silvopastoral) 2016	0-30				1.34	1.20	
Netherlands (Stoutenburg)	2022	0-30			1.60		1.48	
		30-60			1.60		1.48	
Italy ^b (Arnino)	2017	0-10	1.53		1.46		1.49	
		10-30	1.63		1.58		1.67	

^aForest control is on a mature pre-1925 woodland; grass control is from permanent grass with sheep

^bThe arable control includes a seven year rotation of arable crops and temporary grassland

2.10.4. Earthworms

The greatest number of earthworms was recorded in the Netherlands in the silvopastoral system which was measured in October 2025 (Table 53).

Table 53. Effect of site and vegetation on earthworm numbers.

Site	Earthworm abundance (number (8 dm ⁻³))					
	Arable control	Grass control	Middle of crop alley	Silvo-pasture grass	Beneath agroforest tree area	Forest control
Netherlands (Stoutenburg)			17.0		21.3	
Italy (Arnino)	5.3		7.6		6.0	
Spain (Extremadura)				4.6	3.3	
Finland (Sammallahti) ^a		3.2			1.2	0.0
UK (Bedford)				1.0	0.1	1.9
Portugal (Curralões)		0.0			0.0	0.0

Although the system in the UK was also a silvopastoral system, the soil was still very dry at the time of the measurements in 25-26 September 2025. Across the sites, there was no consistent effect of agroforestry on earthworm numbers. However Hlava and Kopecký, (2013) report that earthworm abundance tends to be reduced in acid soils. The measurements in Portugal were taken in May 2025, when it was very dry.

2.10.5. Other measurements

Across the sites, other measurements were taken at selected sites. In Portugal, biological activity was assessed with a 'soil microbiometer'. However the measurement levels at the relatively inert Portuguese site were below the detection limits of the equipment.

In Spain, an assessment was made of soil microbial functional diversity. This showed higher levels beyond the tree canopies than under the tree canopies.

In the UK, the visual examination of soil structure highlighted that the structure of the woodland soils was better than that in the pasture and tree areas of silvopastoral system. The observation that structure was not directly linked to the assessment of soil carbon content indicates that other factors were also determining the structure of the soil.

2.10.6. Use of the UKCEH soil health tool

The UKCEH soil health tool was used in Finland and the UK. Upon reflection, a useful feature of the tool was its explanation of default ranges for bulk density, pH, soil organic matter, and earthworms. Bulk density is a useful measure of the physical condition of the soil, providing insights into the degree of compaction, soil porosity and structural health. Soil pH signals farmers towards the chemical condition of their soils, influencing nutrient availability and microbial activity. Soil organic matter is related to soil fertility, soil water holding capacity, soil structure and stability, and carbon storage. Earthworm abundance provides an insight in the biological condition of soils, providing insights onto structure, and nutrient availability. However, the information collected during earthworm sampling was greatly influenced by environmental and physical conditions. When conditions were too dry (UK sampling) or when soils were too shallow (Portuguese site), very few earthworms were recorded.

Future research efforts could be directed towards another indicator better reflecting the soil biological state, even when environmental and physical conditions are limiting earthworm populations.

In the UK context, the tool seemed to be a useful tool to inform the manager about how the measured soil compares with soils with a similar soil type, level of rainfall, and land cover in the UK. The tool demonstrates that, on average, in the UK context, areas of woodland tend to have lower bulk densities, lower pHs, reduced earthworm populations and higher soil organic matter than areas of cropland and grassland. Because of the many factors that can affect measures of soil health, a focus on improving understanding rather than a focus on achieving a specific number seems to be useful attribute.

2.10.7. Soil sampling strategy

An additional output of the study was a guidance document on soil sampling strategies (Aynekulu et al., 2026). This has been produced as an accompanying, but separate, document with the objective that it can be used by agroforestry practitioners.

2.10.8. Reporting soil health in the value chain

One of the objectives of the study was to identify methods by which soil health could be accounted for in the value chain. The measurements reported in this Deliverable demonstrate that the inclusion of trees in a system is generally positive in terms of soil carbon storage, and hence crop and livestock products associated with agroforestry systems will tend to be associated with higher soil carbon stocks and thus a lower carbon footprint. However the results also demonstrate that the inherent spatial variability of soil and the difficulty and cost of deriving measurements of soil health means that it is very unlikely to be financially feasible to reliably and routinely quantify the effect of agroforestry systems on soil health. It is probably for this reason, that supply chains that focus on the improvement of soil health tend to put greater emphasis on the use by farmers of soil management plans (input-based financing), rather than direct measurements of soil health per se (result-based financing).

3. Greenhouse gas emissions and carbon sequestration

3.1. Introduction

Agroforestry can play a significant role in mitigating climate change by reducing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and increasing carbon storage in soils and woody biomass. However, estimating the actual carbon sequestration potential of agroforestry systems under specific conditions remains challenging. One way to approach this uncertainty is through the use of biomass carbon calculators or whole-farm GHG calculators.

A carbon calculator helps farmers and farm advisers with evaluating the amount of carbon that is stored in soil and vegetation. The tools can be used to explore how management changes—such as modifying crop rotations or adopting agroforestry practices—may influence future carbon stocks. The tools could help to estimate the amount of carbon that may be accrued each year due to improved practices, and for which it may be possible to create income from carbon crediting.

Greenhouse gas assessment tools for use in agriculture consider the effect of farm practices on carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄) and nitrous oxide (N₂O). The overall impact is typically simplified by expressing the warming potential as carbon-dioxide equivalent to allow comparison of overall warming impacts. Like the carbon calculators, the greenhouse gas calculators also account for emissions from livestock, fertilization and other management activities, providing insight on how changed practices affect total farm-level emissions.

3.2. Material and methods

This section of the report briefly reviews three types of farm carbon and greenhouse gas calculators, 1) the CARAT tool, 2) the Farm Carbon Calculator, and 3) the Open Farm Carbon Tracker. All three tools are freely available, open for use to anyone and can be accessed via the DigitAF Tools Catalogue (<https://digitaf.eu/tools-data-and-projects-catalogue/tools>). The assessments were carried out in five countries (Czechia, Finland, Germany, Italy, the Netherlands, and the United Kingdom), mostly at the same Living Lab farms where the soil health assessments were carried out as described in Section 2.

3.2.1. CARAT Tool

The CARAT (CARbon Agroforestry Tool) tool is an innovative online platform created to measure the amount and spatial distribution of above and below ground carbon captured and stored in agroforestry systems. It was developed in Belgium as a collaboration between ILVO, the Soil Service in Belgium, and Fornalab (CARAT Development Team, 2023). The integration of diverse agroforestry practices and tree species enables the estimation of carbon storage potential. The first step is to select a field of interest using LPIS data from an interactive map of the Flanders region of Belgium, or define a virtual rectangular field if you are outside Belgium up to 1 ha in size. Within the field, you can then allocate the position or the spacing of up to 20 pre-selected tree species (Figure 55). The model includes a soil carbon assessment based on the RothC soil carbon model (Coleman et al., 2024), and the assumption is that the baseline land use is arable rather than grassland.

a)

b)

Figure 55. In CARAT, you can for instance a) design an agroforestry field by allocating the position or spacing of selected tree species and b) make graphical outputs of the soil organic carbon distribution in the field (CARAT Development Team, 2023).

The soil input data includes the clay percentage, the bulk density, the depth to the plough layer, and the initial soil organic content. The user can opt for an arable rotation or grassland. The algorithms of the model then predict the evolution of the woody biomass, the spatial distribution of leaf-fall and the resulting change in soil organic carbon for the duration of the tree rotation (CARAT Development Team, 2023). The output is presented both graphically and via a tabular output.

3.2.2. Farm Carbon Calculator

The Farm Carbon Calculator (FCC) was developed in the UK by a group of farmers who then went to create the Farm Carbon Toolkit Organisation (Farm Carbon Toolkit, 2025). The user can use an online

tool to determine the predicted levels of greenhouse gas emissions and rates of carbon sequestration at a farm business level.

An initially useful feature of the Farm Carbon calculator was a **data collection sheet** that covers fuel use, materials, inventory, fertility and cropping, inputs, livestock, waste, distribution and sequestration (Figure 56). This can still be useful for offline recording of the data used. However towards the end of the study, the data collection sheet has been discontinued as it was becoming increasingly large in size, and hard to use. Instead, users are now advised to work through the online system making use of the available guidance instead, or contact a local advisor. For our study, initially we started filling in the data collection sheets, however, most case studies used the online tool which is more user friendly and clear, and the results can be immediately visualised and demonstrated to the farmer.

Figure 56. The Farm Carbon Calculator produces a data collection sheet (Farm Carbon Toolkit 2025).

In terms of digital tools for agroforestry, the most important data inputs would relate to sequestration, i.e. sequestration due to the growth of above and below ground biomass of trees and crops and accumulation of soil organic carbon in the soil. The Farm Carbon Calculator makes estimates of carbon sequestration by agri-environment measures, hedges, woodlands, and trees outside woodland. However, Parker et al. (2025) explain that for a report to be compliant with the draft LSRG or SBTi FLAG regulations, there is a need to use **directly measured data** that can be used to produce a carbon removals estimate for your farm.

The spreadsheet is designed to accept information of the area and age of general woodland types (coniferous, deciduous, mixed) or specific species and their age in five-year-groups (Figure 57). There is also an option to add the average width and total length of two types of hedgerows, and details about perennial crops. The basis of the references for the individual algorithms are explained within the spreadsheet (Farm Carbon Toolkit, 2025).

Land use							
NOTE: Soil sampling is the recommended way to document changes in carbon within soils							
Calculator Category	Calculator Descriptor	Source descriptor	Input units	USER DATA User Input	Additional input	INFO FCT reference	Help Notes
Woodland				Area (ha)			
Species & age specific	Woodland: detailed analysis		Type, age and area	0	Select an option	58	You will get the option to add the age of your trees on the Calculator in 10 year increments
Average	Woodland: mixed		Hectares	0	.	58	
Average	Woodland: coniferous		Hectares	0	.	58	
Average	Woodland: broadleaf		Hectares	0	.	58	
In field trees				Quantity	Area under crown (m²)		
In field trees (assumed broadleaf trees)	Average area under Crown		Number of trees	0	0	58	
Hedgerows				Width (m)	Length (m)		
Managed (generic, not recommended)	Managed		Meters	0	0	99, 25, 22, 101	
Managed hedgerow under 15 years old			Meters	0	0	87, 88, 89	Average width across the
Managed hedgerow planted more than 15 years ago			Meters	0	0	87, 88, 89	length of the hedge
Large growth with trees	Unmanaged		Meters	0	0	99, 25, 100	

Figure 57. The user can add detailed information about woodland and perennial features into the Farm Carbon Calculator data collection sheet (After Farm Carbon Toolkit, 2025).

3.2.3. Open Farm Carbon Tracker

Open Farm Carbon Tracker (OFCT) is an open source tool that has been developed during the DigitAF project to support the modelling of potential future greenhouse gas fluxes under different scenarios, based on the Carbon Model previously developed by JRC (Tuomisto et al., 2015). The OFCT model can be run on its own or as an integrated part of other applications (Figure 58). A web interface has been developed (OFCT APP), which makes it possible to run the model in a browser (Figure 59).

Figure 58. Modular architecture of Open Farm Carbon Tracker, showing both the model and the web-application.

A significant feature of Open Farm Carbon Tracker is the capacity in selected countries to automatically derive field layouts from the Land Parcel Identification System (LPIS). Using publicly available datasets, field boundaries can be automatically selected in Denmark, Czech Republic, France, Netherlands and Finland. The Open Farm Carbon Tracker can also use LPIS crop reference codes to pre-fill most current crop references for specific countries and years. Within the selected fields, users can specify crop types over future years, together with different levels of tree cover. Using this information, the tool can then derive an estimate of future flows of GHG emissions and carbon sequestration (Figure 59).

Figure 59. Automated graph produced on web interface of OFCT showing farm-scale accumulated emissions and their yearly contributions.

3.3. Czechia

3.3.1. Introduction

In the Czech Living Lab, two tools (CARAT and the Farm Carbon Calculator) were used to assess the GHG emissions at the farm level, using data from the Karel Ježek farm. The organic farm is located in SE part of Czechia (49.1544 N, 15.5340 E), it has a size of nearly 50 ha (4.13 ha of arable land producing animal feed, with the rest of permanent grasslands for grazing and production of hay and haylage), focused on animal production (30 heads of beef suckler cows and in average 20 calves under one year for sale each year). During 2023-25, the family established a silvoarable agroforestry system on nearly 30 ha of their permanent grasslands. The trees are a mixture of forest (oak, maple, alder) and fruit trees (apple, pear, plum and sour cherry) planted in lines with a distance between lines of 18-20m. The trees in the lines are 3 to 6 m apart.

3.3.2. CARAT

The carbon sequestration potential in the silvopastoral system at Karel Ježek farm was simulated in CARAT. The size of the established agroforestry system during 2023-25 was 30 ha in several blocks of land. Because the map functionality is not (yet) supported for Czechia, we initially assumed a 1 ha square (Figure 60). We simplified the silvoarable agroforestry system at Karel Ježek farm to retain only the species available in the tool: oak and maple for forest trees and apple for fruit trees. In the model, we considered that trees were planted in lines with a distance of 20 m and 4 m distance in row, established on grassland used for hay production. The tree density was 100 trees per hectare.

Figure 60. Field layout for the CARAT simulation of one hectare silvoarable system at Karel Ježek farm

For the initial analysis, the bulk density was assumed to be 1.3 g cm^{-3} (Table 54). The grassland is not ploughed but we had to enter a “plough” depth of 10 cm which was the minimum number. The initial SOC at the site was 2%.

Table 54. Input data for soil parameters for the Czech case study site in CARAT.

Description	Value
Field dimensions	100 m x 100 m
Clay percentage	20 %
Bulk density	1.30 g cm ⁻³
Depth of plough layer	0.1 m
Initial soil organic content	2.0 %
Rotation	Permanent grassland

According to the CARAT simulation, soil organic carbon in the silvoarable agroforestry system was predicted to increase by 0.75 t C ha⁻¹ over the next 30 years, equivalent to 22.4 t C for the whole 30 ha (Table 55). By contrast the predicted increase in the biomass carbon in the trees over 30 years was 19.7 t C ha⁻¹.

Table 55. Modelled carbon accumulation in soil organic carbon (SOC) and biomass carbon (C) in the silvoarable AFS at Karel Ježek farm, modelled on the whole 30 ha of agroforestry and per hectare.

Age (years)	Increase in SOC		Biomass C in trees		Total C	
	(t C)	(t C ha ⁻¹)	(t C)	(t C ha ⁻¹)	(t C)	(t C ha ⁻¹)
1	0.80	0.03	46.12	1.54	46.92	1.56
5	2.87	0.10	68.39	2.28	71.26	2.38
10	5.50	0.18	110.56	3.69	116.06	3.87
15	8.39	0.28	175.43	5.85	183.81	6.13
20	12.04	0.40	271.63	9.05	283.67	9.46
25	16.67	0.56	408.06	13.60	424.72	14.16
30	22.39	0.75	591.78	19.73	614.17	20.47

3.3.3. Farm Carbon Calculator

The Farm Carbon Calculator was used to assess greenhouse gas emissions and carbon sequestration from the main fields of the Karel Ježek farm. Briefly summarized, these were: 1) permanent grassland (45 ha) used for production of hay where new silvopastoral agroforestry system was established in 2023-24 on 30 ha, 2) arable land used for the production of grain feed for animals (4.13 ha). Data used for the assessment are for the year 2025. The carbon balance and flows were calculated within the farm boundaries.

At the Karel Ježek farm, livestock production resulted in the largest source of emissions, equivalent to 165.16 tCO₂e yr⁻¹ (Table 56). Crop production to produce animal feed (0.90 tCO₂e yr⁻¹) and fuels, materials and waste disposal (12.58 tCO₂e yr⁻¹) were smaller sources of emissions. The permanent grassland with silvoarable agroforestry was calculated to sequestered 5.56 tCO₂e yr⁻¹, so the total net emissions were 173.08 tCO₂e yr⁻¹. However, if we modelled the farm in a time frame of 15 years from now, when the trees are mature, the silvoarable agroforestry will sequester 73.83 tCO₂e yr⁻¹, so the total net emissions would drop to 104.81 tCO₂e yr⁻¹.

Table 56 Calculated levels of emissions and sequestration at the Karel Ježek farm using the Farm Carbon Calculator.

Source of emissions	Emissions (t CO ₂ e yr ⁻¹)	Sequestration (t CO ₂ e yr ⁻¹)	Net emissions (t CO ₂ e yr ⁻¹)
Livestock production	165.16		
Crop production (feed for animals)	0.90		
Fuels	9.44		
Materials	3.13		
Waste disposal	0.01		
Silvoarable agroforestry		5.56	
Sub-total	178.64	5.56	173.08

Within the benchmarking tool on Farm Carbon Toolkit, the focus is on the gross level of emissions, 0.987 CO₂e ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹, which puts the farm in the lowest 50% when benchmarking the emissions of the Karel Ježek farm against other similar farms (Figure 61).

Figure 61. The benchmarking tool within Farm Carbon Calculator indicates that the emissions from Karel Ježek farm of 0.529 tCO₂e ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹, placed the farm in the lowest 50% for the selected data.

3.4. Finland

3.4.1. Introduction

In the Finnish Living Lab, three tools were used to assess the GHG emissions at the farm level, using data from the Sammallahti farm, the same farm as in the soil health assessment (See Section 2.3). The tools used in the assessment were: 1) CARAT, 2) Farm Carbon Calculator, and 3) the Open Farm Carbon Tracker.

3.4.2. CARAT

Carbon sequestration potential in the forest grazing area at Sammallahti farm was simulated in CARAT. The size of the original field in real life is 3.98 ha. Because the map functionality is not (yet) supported for Finland, we used an imaginary 1 ha square (Figure 62). The forest grazing area at Sammallahti is composed of mixed boreal forest mainly composed of pine, spruce and birch, which are not (yet) available in the CARAT tool. Therefore, we added “standard trees” (62 trees) to the 1 hectare plot and also added alder, rowan, and willow (10 trees for each species) to the site as these species commonly occur in boreal mixed forest and also Sammallahti’s forest grazing area. The tree density was 92 trees per hectare.

Figure 62. Layout for the CARAT simulation of one hectare forest grazing area at Sammallahti farm.

For the initial analysis, the bulk density was assumed to be 1 g cm^{-3} (Table 57) even though the measured bulk density (0.38 g cm^{-3} at 0-20 cm and 0.67 g cm^{-3} at 20-40 cm) was in fact much lower (Table 6). This is because it was not possible to add bulk densities lower than 1 g cm^{-3} . The grazed forest is not ploughed but we had to enter a “plough” depth of 10 cm which was the minimum number. The initial SOC at the site (13.66% at 0-20 cm and 4.5% at 20-40 cm) was also much higher than the maximum of 5% which was allowed to enter in the programme.

Table 57. Input data for soil parameters for the Finnish site in CARAT.

Description	Value
Field dimensions	100 m x 100 m
Clay percentage	16 %
Bulk density	1.00 g cm^{-3}
Depth of plough layer	0.1 m
Initial soil organic content	5.0 %
Rotation	Pasture

According to the CARAT simulation, soil organic carbon in the grazed forest would increase by 1.6 t C ha⁻¹ over the next 30 years, equivalent to 6.2 t C for the 3.98 ha (Table 58). By contrast the predicted increase in the biomass carbon in the trees over 30 years was 78 t C ha⁻¹.

Table 58. Modelled carbon accumulation in soil organic carbon (SOC) and biomass carbon (C) in the grazed forest area at Sammallahti farm.

Age (years)	Increase in SOC		Biomass C in trees		Total C	
	(t C field ⁻¹)	(t C ha ⁻¹)	(t C field ⁻¹)	(t C ha ⁻¹)	(t C field ⁻¹)	(t C ha ⁻¹)
1	0.1	0.0	41	10	31	10
5	0.5	0.1	54	13	54	14
10	1.1	0.3	77	19	78	20
15	1.9	0.5	109	28	111	28
20	3.0	0.7	155	39	158	39
25	4.4	1.1	220	55	224	56
30	6.2	1.6	311	78	317	79

3.4.3. Farm Carbon Calculator

The Farm Carbon Calculator was used to assess greenhouse gas emissions and carbon sequestration from the main fields of the Sammallahti farm. Briefly summarized these were: 1) permanent grass (grazed by sheep), 2) permanent grass (grazed by cattle), 3) grazed forest (grazed by sheep), and 4) commercial forest (ungrazed) (Figure 11). Data were collected for the assessment are for the year 2025. The carbon balance and flows were calculated within the farm boundaries.

At the Sammallahti farm, livestock production resulted in the largest source of emissions equivalent to 23.58 tCO₂e yr⁻¹s (Table 59). Crop production to produce silage (0.28 tCO₂e yr⁻¹) and distribution (0.01 tCO₂e yr⁻¹) were only minor sources of emissions. The permanent grassland was calculated to sequester 1.22 tCO₂e yr⁻¹, and the grazed and ungrazed forest were calculated to sequester 35.43 tCO₂e yr⁻¹.

Table 59. Calculated levels of emissions and sequestration at the Sammallahti farm using the Farm Carbon Calculator.

Source of emissions	Emissions (t CO ₂ e yr ⁻¹)	Sequestration (t CO ₂ e yr ⁻¹)	Net sequestration (t CO ₂ e yr ⁻¹)
Livestock production	23.58		
Crop production (silage)	0.28		
Distribution	0.01		
Permanent grassland		1.22	
Grazed and ungrazed forest		35.43	
Sub-total	23.87	36.65	12.78

The permanent grass (5.26 ha), grazed forest (4 ha) and the ungrazed forests areas (4 ha) were large enough and sequestered 36.65 tCO₂e, enough CO₂ to compensate for the emissions of the farm. For the whole farm, the overall carbon balance was -12.78 tCO₂e yr⁻¹. Within the benchmarking tool on Farm Carbon Toolkit, the focus is on the gross level of emissions, 2.36 CO₂e ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹, which puts the farm in the lowest 30% when benchmarking the emissions of the Sammallahti farm against other similar farms (Figure 63).

Figure 63. The benchmarking tool within Farm Carbon Calculator indicates that the emissions from Sammallahti farm of $2.36 \text{ tCO}_2\text{e ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$, placed the farm in the lowest 30% for the selected data.

3.4.4. Open Farm Carbon Tracker (OFCT)

The OFCT was used to assess greenhouse gas emissions and carbon sequestration again for the same fields as described within the soil health assessment (Figure 11).. However, as the Open Farm Carbon Tracker uses the crop codes from the Land Parcel Identification System (LPIS), we had to select the best matching crop code for each field (Figure 64; Table 60).

Figure 64. Selected fields and practices at Sammallahti farm evaluated in the Open Farm Carbon Tracker.

Table 60. The matching crop codes assumed within the four types of management at Sammallahti farm.

Number	Code
1	Permanent grass (grazed by sheep)(= “Miljøgræs MVJ-tilsagn (0 N), permanent” = permanent grass under an environmental agreement),
2	Permanent grass (grazed by cattle)(= same as above “Miljøgræs MVJ-tilsagn (0 N), permanent” = permanent grass under an environmental agreement)
3	Grazed forest (grazed by sheep)(=“Bæredygtig skovdrift i Natura 2000-område” = sustainable forest management in Natura 2000 areas)
4	Normal commercial forest (ungrazed)(=“Bæredygtig skovdrift” = sustainable forest management)

Input data were the same as for the Farm Carbon Calculator assessment. However, the OFCT has the possibility to make projections for several years. In our assessment we made a projection of the farm emissions over a period of 50 years from 2024 to 2074.

Using the OFCT, the analysis was restricted to a calculated emissions from the livestock and a calculated level of sequestration from the forest area. The annual emissions from livestock production were estimated to be 17.6 tCO₂e yr⁻¹ (Figure 65). By contrast, the grazed forest and the ungrazed forest together were calculated to sequester about 67.5 tCO₂e yr⁻¹. Over the 11 year period from 2024 to 2034, the estimated level of sequestration was 416.4 tCO₂e, equivalent to 41.6 tCO₂e yr⁻¹.

Figure 65. Calculated emissions from livestock and sequestration by the forests in Open Farm Carbon Tracker for the period 2024 to 2034.

3.4.5. Discussion

Use of the Open Farm Carbon Tracker

A demonstration workshop was held on 11 December 2024 on Teams. Twelve persons attended the meeting, mostly researchers, one farmer and one value chain actor (Valio, a dairy producer). Overall, the participants liked the Open Farm Tracker Tool, and everyone was able to use it and create a scenario after the introduction. There was, however, specific feedback related to the functioning of the tool as it is currently not possible to see how the tool works. More specific suggestions were:

- Increase tool transparency: show data sources, calculation methodologies. Currently you cannot see where the data comes from, how the tool works, nor how emissions and sequestration from crops and trees are calculated. It is important to show, understand and modify how the calculations are made for each crop.
- Suggestions:
 - Add Finnish, Swedish and English crop names. It was difficult to work with the tool because for Finland there were now only Danish crop names. Fortunately, some of the crop names (e.g. majs, hassel, etc.) were possible to understand even for non-Danish speakers.
 - Is it possible to include Land Use Change (LUC), or is it already included? In the GitHub there is a table showing some impacts of Land Use Change but not clear if this is already included in the tool. (Edit: It is possible to include, but this could be explained better in the tool instructions).
 - Include more complex agroforestry arrangements, for example main crop and an under sown crop.
 - Include the impact of management and other biophysical factors
 - Is it possible to include historical data? There is LPIS data from 2020. Can we get data before that? For example, can the tool be used for monitoring changes over time?

It was agreed with the stakeholders that another workshop could be held when there are any major updates to the tool.

Comparison of the three tools

All three tools were difficult to use at first sight, but after watching the instruction videos, reading the instructions, and a bit of practice it was possible to make an assessment with all three tools. One major difference between the three tools is that CARAT is used for assessments at the individual field level (only one field possible at a time), while the Farm Carbon Calculator and Open Farm Carbon Tracker can be used for assessments at the whole farm level.

When comparing the tools, it is important to remember the specific units being used. CARAT uses kilograms of carbon (kg C) as a unit, while the Farm Carbon Calculator and Open Farm Carbon Tracker use kilograms or tonnes of carbon dioxide equivalents (kg or t CO₂e). To convert tonnes of carbon to tonnes of carbon dioxide equivalent (CO₂e or CO₂), one needs to multiply the tonnes of carbon by a factor of 3.67. This conversion accounts for the molecular weight ratio of CO₂ (44) to Carbon (12) ($44 / 12 = 3.67$).

There were some clear differences in the estimates of carbon sequestration potential between the three tools, however, some estimates were surprisingly close (Table 61). For the forest grazing area,

CARAT estimated the annual removals at $9.7 \text{ tCO}_2\text{e ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$, which was higher than the derived value of $7.0 \text{ tCO}_2\text{e ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ and $6.4 \text{ tCO}_2\text{e ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ for the Farm Carbon Calculator and the OFCT, respectively. For the whole farm, the Farm Carbon Calculator estimated the total removals at $36.6 \text{ tCO}_2\text{e yr}^{-1}$, whereas the Open Farm Carbon Tracker assumed a net value of $67.5 \text{ tCO}_2\text{e yr}^{-1}$.

Table 61. Comparison of the calculated level of emissions or sequestration (negative values) using CARAT, Farm Carbon Calculator and Open Farm Carbon Tracker.

Input or output	Unit	CARAT	Farm Carbon Calculator	Open Farm Carbon Tracker
Farm area (ha)	ha	n/a	13.2	13.2
Forest grazing area (ha)	ha	3.98	3.98	3.98
Total removals forest grazing area	$\text{t CO}_2\text{e yr}^{-1}$	-38.8	-27.7	-25.3
	$\text{t CO}_2\text{e ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$	-9.7	-7.0	-6.4
Total removals whole farm	$\text{t CO}_2\text{e yr}^{-1}$	n/a	-36.6	-67.5
	$\text{t CO}_2\text{e ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$	n/a	-2.8	-5.1

One reason for the observed differences could be how the sequestration potential of forest and wood pasture is calculated. In the Farm Carbon Calculator, the sequestration potential is based on average volume growth for woodland in the United Kingdom, and tree densities can be adjusted to “high” or “low” tree densities. In the Open Farm Carbon Tracker, it is based on the average volume growth of “forest under sustainable management” but the precise data source is not clear. The average volume growth and biomass increase can be adjusted by changing the percentage of tree cover, which is more precise than just “high” or “low” tree densities as in the Farm Carbon Calculator. In CARAT, tree densities and the position of the trees can be marked quite exactly on a map. However, pine spruce and birch, the most common tree species in Finland were not available as an option to simulate the stand. Instead, a “standard tree” had to be selected which could be one reason for a relatively high estimate in carbon sequestration potential. It is likely that differences in volume growth and/or values entered for tree densities or percentage tree cover have led to different estimates for the two tools in total carbon sequestration.

CARAT does not include livestock, but The Farm Carbon Calculator and the Open Farm Carbon Tracker do include it. There were also (smaller) differences in the emissions from livestock between the Farm Carbon Calculator ($23.58 \text{ tCO}_2\text{e yr}^{-1}$) and Open Farm Carbon Tracker ($17.6 \text{ tCO}_2\text{e yr}^{-1}$). A reason for this difference between the two tools could be how the numbers of livestock are entered. In the Open Farm Carbon Tracker, it is possible to add cattle but not sheep. In the Farm Carbon Calculator, you can add different type and age categories of sheep, such as ewes, rams or lambs. In the Open Farm Carbon Tracker, you can select dairy cows, bulls or meat cattle to specify the type of cattle. The Farm Carbon Calculator gives many more options such as calves, beef cattle, heifers, beef suckler cows, bulls for breeding, finishing bulls, beef replacement heifers, beef finishing steers. The age and type of livestock has a strong impact on emissions and this could have played a role in the observed differences between the tools.

3.5. Germany

3.5.1. CARAT

In the German Living Lab, CARAT was used to assess the GHG emissions at the farm level for the LL Farm Thomas Domin, the same farm as in the soil health assessment (see Section 2.3). The modelling with CARAT focuses on a specific subsection of the silvoarable agroforestry system:

- R1: 0.777 ha of poplar planted in 2015, comprised of five rows at a 2.7 m x 1.0 m tree spacing to the East and five rows of poplar at a 2.7 m x 0.5 m spacing to the West.
- R3: 0.152 ha of a poplar-hardwood combi-system planted in 2020. Subplots are:
 - one row of poplar (*Populus x Canadensis*) to the East (0.076 ha)
 - one row with groups of three high value timer trees: sweet chestnut (*Castanea sativa*), field maple (*Acer campestre*), Turkish hazel (*Corylus colurna*) at a 1.5 m spacing n the group, intermitted by 5 m of shrub species copper rock pear (*Amelanchier lamarckii*), elderberry (*Sambucus nigra*) (0.076 ha), and another row of poplar to the West (0.152 ha).

As CARAT is not (yet) capable of accessing German LPIS polygons, we used a random rectangular field sized 50 m x 100 m (Figure 66). Poplar was modelled using *Populus x canadensis*, sweet chestnut was modelled using 'standard tree' and *Corylus avellana* was used for the shrub species. Trees were added with a distance of 1 m x 2 m for the short rotation coppice for poplar and placed individually for the other species in order to mimic the real planting scheme (groups of three and five shrubs in-between).

Figure 66 a) functional unit representative of a field in the German case study ; blue markers correspond to the locations of the soil samples taken to measure soil health (see section 2.4) b) corresponding layout for the CARAT simulation .

The soil input data were based on field measurements collected in 2025, the clay fraction (< 0.05 mm) was 23%, the assumed bulk density was 1.4 g cm⁻³, the ploughing depth was set to 20 cm and initial soil organic carbon content was set at 3.4% (Table 62).

Table 62 Input data for soil parameters for the silvoarable plot at the Germany site in CARAT.

Description	Value
Field dimensions	100 m x 50 m
Clay percentage	23 %
Bulk density	1.4 g cm ⁻³
Depth of plough layer	0.2 m
Initial soil organic content	3.4 %
Rotation	Arable

It is assumed, that after 10 years all poplars will be harvested and a regrowth will occur, thus repeating the cycle with respect to litter fall and C fixation in the trees' biomass, potentially up to 30 years. The results of CARAT show that in year 10 the expected total SOC-stock increase is 2.1 t C ha⁻¹ and biomass C-Stock accumulated 41 C t ha⁻¹ for the entire specified agroforestry system (Table 63, Figure 67). These values seem high and could be a result of the assumption that each tree is modelled as if it was free standing without competition for light and water. After 20 to 30 years, the field would undergo complete clearance as stock re-sprouting will terminate. However, the ratio between soil and biomass C accumulation of roughly 1:10 seems realistic.

Table 63 CARAT results showing the modelled carbon accumulation in soil organic carbon (SOC) and biomass carbon (C) in the modelled agroforestry system at the German case study site.

Age (years)	SOC stocks		Biomass C in trees		Total C	
	(t C field ⁻¹)	(t C ha ⁻¹)	(t C field ⁻¹)	(t C ha ⁻¹)	(t C field ⁻¹)	(t C ha ⁻¹)
1	0.1	0.3	1.4	2.7	1.5	3.0
5	0.7	1.3	3.8	7.7	4.5	9.0
10	2.1	4.1	20.9	41.8	23.0	45.9

3.5.2. Discussion

The combination of different tree management options (e.g. SRC and value timber/fruited trees) is currently not an option in CARAT. As the model is aiming for the use of value timber tree species, any intermediate harvest is not incorporated. Therefore a time frame of 10 years was selected for this analysis, which is longer than a typical rotation for poplar planted at a spacing of 1 m x 2 m. Therefore, carbon storage is probably overestimated in the model because in reality, competition between closely spaced trees would decrease the actual growth rates and mean annual increments compared to the free-standing trees hypothesized in the model. Above ground tree biomass is set to zero after harvest, only belowground biomass remains, resulting in a stronger re-growth after harvest with multiple stems. This might then indicate that the model is underestimating growth rates for subsequent growth periods, at least for the above-ground biomass. But since a distinction between above and belowground biomass is not made in CARAT, it appears difficult to take this effect of multiple harvests into account.

Figure 67. Example outputs from the CARAT simulation of the assumed silvoarable system at the case study farm in Germany.

3.6. Italy

3.6.1. Introduction

Within the Italian Living Lab, the GHG and carbon tools were applied in two steps. Firstly, the Italian Living Lab manager quantified the gains in carbon from agroforestry using CARAT, and the farm Carbon Calculator to derive the GHG emissions and sequestration of the trial site described in Section 2.5. The tools were then explained to the stakeholders of the Italian Living Lab and simulations were made to gain feedback regarding the use of CARAT and the Farm Carbon calculator.

3.6.2. CARAT

The simulation of a plot in Arnino was performed in CARAT, with the layout of the agroforestry system configured with a field of 100 m x 30 m (Figure 68), using the default parameters described in Table 64. After running CARAT the results obtained are displayed in Table 65.

Figure 68. Diagram generated in CARAT to simulate the agroforestry system design of a plot in Arnino.

Table 64. Input data for soil parameters in CARAT, based on soil analysis from the agroforestry trial.

Description	Value
Field dimensions	30 m x 100 m
Clay percentage	20 %
Bulk density	1.53 g cm ⁻³
Depth of plough layer	0.3 m
Initial soil organic content	1.25 %

Table 65. Simulation results from CARAT of carbon accumulation in soil organic carbon (SOC) and biomass carbon (C) in the modelled agroforestry system at Arnino over 30 years.

Age (years)	Increase in SOC		Biomass C in trees		Total C	
	(t C field ⁻¹)	(t C ha ⁻¹)	(t C field ⁻¹)	(t C ha ⁻¹)	(t C field ⁻¹)	(t C ha ⁻¹)
1	0.00	0.00	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
5	0.01	0.02	0.0	0.2	0.0	0.2
10	0.02	0.08	0.3	1.0	0.3	1.1
15	0.05	0.17	1.4	4.6	1.4	4.8
20	0.09	0.31	3.5	11.5	3.5	11.8
25	0.10	0.43	5.4	18.1	5.5	18.5
30	0.16	0.53	6.6	22.0	6.7	22.5

3.6.3. Farm Carbon Calculator

The Farm Carbon Calculator was applied to calculate the greenhouse gas emissions from three systems at Arnino LTE: (i) conventional, (ii) low-density alley cropping, and (iii) high-density alley cropping. The year considered for all case studies was 2021–2022. Carbon flows were calculated within the farm boundaries. Our objectives were to (i) evaluate the potential of different types of agroforestry as a carbon farming practice and (ii) to test the effectiveness and flexibility of the digital tool in representing different types of agroforestry systems. A brief description of the selected systems is presented in Table 66.

Table 66. Three scenarios considered with the Farm Carbon Toolkit.

System	Arable system	Sources of carbon sequestration
Conventional system (CON):	5.41 ha of cereals and legumes	No carbon sequestration practices implemented
Alley Cropping Low Density system (ACL):	3.76 ha of cereals and legumes	Very low-density in field trees (20-50 stems/ha)
Alley Cropping High Density system (ACH):	1.65 ha of cereals and legumes	Low-density in field trees (50-130 stems/ha)

The results from these case study below show the output per hectare of system which can provide a basis for analysis and discussion (Figure 69, Table 67).

Figure 69. Comparison of greenhouse gas emissions and carbon sequestration of the three systems.

Table 67. Predicted levels of emissions and removals of three scenarios using the Farm Carbon Toolkit.

		Conventional system (CON)	Alley Cropping Low Density system (ACL)	Alley Cropping High Density system (ACH)
Emissions	(t CO ₂ e yr ⁻¹)	12.61	8.38	3.91
	(t CO ₂ e ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹)	2.33	2.23	2.37
Removals	(t CO ₂ e yr ⁻¹)	0.00	0.25	0.31
	(t CO ₂ e ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹)	0.00	0.07	0.19
Net balance	(t CO ₂ e yr ⁻¹)	12.61	8.13	3.60
	(t CO ₂ e ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹)	2.33	2.16	2.18

The main emission category was materials, which was associated with the purchase of 1951 m of deer fencing in a single year. Aside from the deer fencing, the main cost was associated with diesel fuel. The analysis did not include any consideration of emissions from livestock because we considered only the arable and alley cropping treatment that did not include any livestock.

3.6.4. Open Farm Carbon Tracker

The Open Farm Carbon Tracker was used to simulate the levels of greenhouse gas emissions and sequestration association with 18 fields. The fields, representing three types of system, were selected on the map (Table 68). Because the Italian LPIS system is not yet included in the tool, this was done manually. Once the fields were drawn, the areas were calculated automatically. The fuel data input was the same as assumed in the Farm Carbon Calculator (Table 68).

Table 68. Assumed inputs for the Open Farm Carbon Tracker.

Parameter	Assumption
Fields simulated	Arnino: Arable fields (10, 11, 12, 32, 33, 34, 51, 52, 53) Arnino: low alley cropping (silvoarable) fields (no. 21, 22, 23, 47, 48, 49) Arnino: high alley cropping (silvoarable) fields (no. 21, 22, 23)
Fuel use	Arable: 710 l yr ⁻¹ Silvoarable Low Density: 450 l yr ⁻¹ Silvoarable High Density: 215 l yr ⁻¹
Land use	TREE: simulated a rotation of 18 year in silvoarable system. Same rotation length of the financial analysis (18 year are the estimated year needed to growth a poplar for timber production in Mediterranean conditions). CROP: inserted the three-year crop rotation present in Arnino: Durum Wheat, Sorghum, and Faba bean.
Assumed tree Cover	Arable = 0% Silvoarable low density = 14% Silvoarable high density = 24%

In order to complete the simulation, it was necessary to relate the Danish codes to the selected crops. 'Vinterhvede' was assumed for durum wheat, 'Sorghum' was assumed for sorghum, and 'Hestebønner' for Faba bean. The tree option of 'Poppel (0-100 andre træer pr. Ha)' was selected for the poplars.

For the simulation, it was assumed that the only sources of emission or sequestration were the use of fuel and the effect of either arable or tree land cover. Across the three systems, assuming the same land areas as used in the Farm Carbon Calculator assessment, the annual emissions from the use of fuel was equivalent to 0.32-0.35 t CO₂e ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ (Table 69). The predicted emissions associated with the conventional arable system was assumed to be 2.08 t CO₂e ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹. Hence combining the emissions associated with arable cropping and fuel use over 18 years was 43.7 t CO₂e ha⁻¹. After year 1, the silvoarable high density system (24% tree cover; 76% arable) was assumed to result in a net sequestration of 1.66 t CO₂e ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹, and the silvoarable low density (14% tree cover; 86% arable) was assumed to have a net sequestration of 0.17 t CO₂e ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹. After taking into account the emissions in year 1, the high density silvoarable system was assumed to have a net sequestration of 18.6 t CO₂e over 18 years, and the low density systems was assumed to have resulted in a net sequestration of 5.6 t CO₂e (Table 69).

Table 69. Predicted levels of greenhouse gas emissions from energy and land use using the OFCT for the three systems in Italy.

		Arable	Silvoarable low density	Silvoarable high density
Assumed area		5.41	3.76	1.65
Fuel use (Yr 1 to 18)	(t CO ₂ e yr ⁻¹)	1.90	1.20	0.58
	(t CO ₂ e ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹)	0.35	0.32	0.32
Land use (Yr 1)	(t CO ₂ e yr ⁻¹)	11.23	10.18	5.80
	(t CO ₂ e ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹)	2.08	2.71	3.52
Land use (Yr 2 to 18)	(t CO ₂ e yr ⁻¹)	11.23	-0.64	-2.75
	(t CO ₂ e ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹)	2.08	-0.17	-1.66
Net change (Yr 1 to 18)	(t CO ₂ e)	236.4	20.9	-30.5
	(t CO ₂ e ha ⁻¹)	43.7	5.6	-18.5

3.6.5. Discussion

Feedback from the Living Lab stakeholders

Eight stakeholders within the Italian Living Lab were asked to review the usability and utility of the CARAT and Farm Carbon Calculator on a three point scale ranging from low (1) to high (3). Overall, the scores for the two tools were ranked in a similar way with mean scores of 2.0 to 2.4 (Table 70). More detailed feedback on the two tools is provided in Table 71.

Table 70. Overview of scores given to CARAT and Farm Carbon Calculator on usability and utility within the Italian Living Lab; scores ranged from 1 to 3, where 1 was the lowest and 3 the highest.

Stakeholder	CARAT		Farm Carbon Calculator	
	Usability	Utility	Usability	Utility
1 Farmer	2	2	2	3
2 Advisor	1	1	1	2
3 Advisor/Researcher	2	3	3	3
4 Farmer	1.5	2	2.5	2
5 Farmer	2	2	3	3
6 Advisor	3	2	2	2
7 Farmer	3	2	2	2
8 Advisor	2	2	2	2
Average	2.1	2.0	2.2	2.4

Table 71. Stakeholders feedback from the Italian Living Lab on CARAT and the Farm Carbon Calculator (FCC).

User		Marks (1-5)		What would you improve about the tool?		Does the tool help you solve your problems? If no, what specific problems does it solve instead?		How would you improve the usability of the tool?	
		CARAT	FCC	CARAT	FCC	CARAT	FCC	CARAT	FCC
1	Farmer		4	Add details to the legend; absent climatic data	Add crops and scenarios for Mediterranean countries	Likes the option to draw the tree species	Completed; easy to use	Inserting climatic data or reference to local area	
2	Advisor	2	2	Increase the complexity of the design tool (diagram generation), based on one hectare is too simplified	The website crashed before adding any result; no result available in short time; time-consuming	Results of carbon measurements not clear. Not clear what 2-5-10-20 m is, the distance from the tree?	Useful for farm using proper real data (need a great amount of data)	Weak server ; the app crashed several times while 5-6 people were using it simultaneously; graphs of results not very clear	
3	Advisor / Researcher	4	5	Slow app (adding tree as single point was very slow)	Add option to choose the agroforestry species, not only the density	Likes the option to draw, even if it has some limitations	Need great amount of data but filling them on the website is relatively easy		
4	Farmer	3	4	Drawing of the trees; add option to increase the surface; difficulties in reading the results	Add data adapted to the climatic area (i.e. olive)	Difficulties to read the results, therefore difficulties in using the tool		Reading of the graph	Clearer measurement units
5	Farmer	2	4	Practicality of the system design tool; add option to change the system; add legends in final	Simplification of the icons that you can chose				Add data of Mediterranean conditions

				graph					
6	Advisor	3	4	System should be projected to the future; option to add input from personal experience	Improve the translation from English to Italian; Improve choices given (i.e. use of wood)	Help to have a better perception of the agroforestry system	Yes, it helps the farmer understand its impact in a relatively fast and easy way	Tool with high usability and quite easy to understand	Increase ease of comprehension of certain questions; address doubts regarding the correctness of the entered answers
7	Farmer	4	3	Add future and past projection; project should be linked to a specific region	Increase the clarity of the information/instructions to fill in the data	Yes, increase the awareness but it is not specific for an area/climate	yes, it helps to understand the situation of the farm; the drop down menu does not provide choice of the real farm		Difficulties interpreting the various choices in the drop down menu
8	Advisor	3	3	Add legend to the axes in the graph (2-5-10-20 m what do they mean?)				Option to select alternative languages	
	<i>Average / Overall evaluation</i>	3.0	3.6	Improve the readability of the results	Improving the translation in Italian and adaptation to Mediterranean conditions	The possibility of drawing the system and the results allow to increase the awareness of the agroforestry systems but it has some limitations	It provides a good overview of the sustainability of the farm in an easy way despite the need of a great amount of data	Improving the readability of the graphical results	

3.7. The Netherlands

3.7.1. Introduction

In the Netherlands, the approach taken was one where three different carbon tools (CARAT, Farm Carbon Calculator and BodemCoolstof) were compared for performance. Hence, an approach was sought where the same input variables were attempted to put into the model, and subsequently evaluating the outputs of each tool. There was less focus on creating a “digital twin” in that sense; the comparison of the models was deemed more interesting than an attempt to accurately estimate the carbon stock in biomass and soil in the actual farm. However, a whole inventory was also done for the Farm Carbon Calculator.

3.7.2. CARAT

In CARAT, a density of 15 trees ha⁻¹ of walnut trees (*Juglans regia*) was modelled. The spacing of the trees was not necessarily accounted for, since CARAT does not seem to take tree competition into account for the prediction of tree growth; rather the total number of trees seems to be the only variable that counts. The soil input data, however, was based on factual 2025 soil data collected by the farmer. The only value that was kept default was the bulk density, which was unknown at the time of the analysis. The input data is visible in Figure 70.

Figure 70. Agroforestry system layout generated and input values for CARAT at the Dutch case study site.

The output of CARAT shows that in year 30 the expected carbon stock is 2.1 t C ha⁻¹, which translates to 0.26 t CO₂ ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ over a period of 30 years. This is the combined stock of the trees and the soil, where the trees are responsible for the greater part of the stock.

Table 72. CARAT results showing the modelled carbon accumulation in soil organic carbon (SOC) and biomass carbon (C) in the modelled agroforestry system at the Netherlands case study site over 30 years.

Age (years)	Increase in SOC		Biomass C in trees		Total C	
	(t C field ⁻¹)	(t C ha ⁻¹)	(t C field ⁻¹)	(t C ha ⁻¹)	(t C field ⁻¹)	(t C ha ⁻¹)
1	0.00	0.00	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2
5	0.03	0.03	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3
10	0.05	0.05	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.4
15	0.07	0.07	0.6	0.6	0.7	0.7
20	0.11	0.11	0.9	0.9	1.0	1.0
25	0.16	0.16	1.3	1.3	1.5	1.5
30	0.22	0.22	1.9	1.9	2.1	2.1

3.7.3. Farm Carbon Calculator

For the model input of the Farm Carbon Calculator, only newly planted trees were taken into account in the inventory. This is because the primary goal was to learn how the expected carbon stock was modelled in the different tools. In the model settings, the “inventory” was excluded from the GHG calculation. This was done by choosing the “up front” accounting method where the impact is 100% depreciated in the year of acquisition. Since all of the inventory was acquired years ago, the consequence was that the inventory in total was excluded. All other data on emissions was successfully entered in the other categories.

With regards to the sequestration, the tool unfortunately was not able to process multiple soil carbon measurements, although the tool mentions that it should be able to digest such data. In practice the window for entering the data was not shown. Only the newly planted agroforestry was included in the sequestration (Figure 71). The underlying thought was to see how much the newly planted agroforestry systems already compensated the emissions from e.g. livestock (mostly enteric fermentation). It was entered as follows: on 1 ha low density fields of 50-130 stems ha⁻¹ of 0-5 years old trees; on 3 ha very low density trees 20-50 stems ha⁻¹ of 0-5 years old trees; and 600 meters of hedgerows of under 15 years old. In total this sums up to 1.20 t CO₂e.

Type	Field / Description	Quantity	Sequestration (t CO ₂ e)	Edit	Delete	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Soil Organic Carbon - Direct Measurement	Kamp	3 ha	0.00		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Soil Organic Matter - Direct Measurement	Kamp	3 ha	0.00		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Woodland, agroforestry & silvopasture - Modelled > Agroforestry, silvopasture & cricket bat willows > Low density in field trees (50-130 stems/ha) > Low density, 0-5 years	1 ha	-0.09			
<input type="checkbox"/>	Woodland, agroforestry & silvopasture - Modelled > Agroforestry, silvopasture & cricket bat willows > Very low density in field trees (20-50 stems/ha) > Very low density, 0-5 years	3 ha	-0.18			
<input type="checkbox"/>	Hedgerows - Modelled > Managed hedgerow under 15 years old	600 m	-0.93			
Total:			-1.20			

Figure 71. Carbon sequestration calculated for the newly planted agroforestry systems. Excluding soil carbon sequestration.

Overall, the predicted sequestration in the small and young agroforestry system was very small compared to the total emissions of the farm which was dominated by the livestock. Based on the inputs provided, the greatest level of emissions was associated with livestock feed which accounted for 133.75 t CO₂e. There was no estimate of the emissions for enteric fermentation and manure storage which was probably the result of an error in data entry.

Figure 72 Emission and removals total for the Dutch case study farm. Enteric fermentation and manure storage are not included.

3.7.4. *BodemCoolstof Tool*

BodemCoolstof Tool is a Roth-C based model developed by Wageningen University & Research in collaboration with Louis Bolk Instituut and other research partners (Hendriks et al., 2023).

In a previous study, Lesschen et al. (2020) have demonstrated that the outputs from the BodemCoolstof Tool is very sensitive to changes in temperature and precipitation. For example, using default data from 37 dairy farms, a “wet year” (nat jaar) can result in soil GHG emissions of 0.05 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹, whereas a “dry year” resulted in a positive carbon balance of 0.6 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ (Lesschen et al., 2020). The BodemCoolstof Tool used the nearest weather station multi-year historic data from the meteorological institute KNMI. In a newest update, it also uses climate change scenarios to predict the future weather instead of just the past climate data. It is unknown what climate data CARAT uses. Therefore, it is hard to compare the outputs of the models without having the underlying weather data.

3.7.5. *Discussion*

The BodemCoolstof Tool predicts that soil carbon loss or sequestration is related to rainfall, whereas CARAT assumes a default climate. Another difference is the soil depth over which carbon stocks are calculated. The BodemCoolstof Tool allows users to select variable soil depths (Figure 73). In practice,

users often have had sampling done for 0-10, 0-25, or 0-30 cm. Results can be extrapolated to other soil depths using pedotransfer functions. By contrast, although the user specifies a 'depth of plough layer; the assumed depth for the calculations in CARAT are not explicitly stated.

Figure 73. Different soil depths over which the soil sample data was taken in the BodemCoolstof Tool

By contrast whereas CARAT allows the user to input the bulk density (g cm^{-3}), the BodemCoolstof Tool does not. The BodemCoolstof Tool uses standard values based on the overarching soil type (clay or sand) and the amount of organic matter. Though few users will have their own unique bulk density data available, the option to change the input as a user can be a valuable addition to the model. Since the bulk density is multiplied with the carbon content to calculate the carbon stock, the bulk density can have a strong effect on the model output. The bulk density was unfortunately not taken into account in the sensitivity analysis of Lesschen et al. (2020). For future sensitivity analyses it would be recommended to include this variable.

Another notable difference between the two tools is the fact that in the BodemCoolstof Tool the user can enter a unique crop rotation and manure application (Figure 74). In CARAT, the crop rotation and manure application is fixed within "arable" and "grassland" options (Vanneste et al., 2025). In the BodemCoolstof Tool, the user can choose for each year the crop, a green manure, the type of manure, and the amount of manure (Hendriks et al., 2023).

Figure 74. The BodemCoolstof Tool allows users to change the crop rotation (left) and manure application (right)

A last difference is that the BodemCoolstof Tool does not have trees in the model apart from willow. CARAT does include the effect of the tree component on soil carbon, but strictly through a self-developed leaf-litter model that is added on top of the Roth-C model.

An attempt was made to enter roughly the same input data in to the two models. In the BodemCoolstof Tool the sequestration was $2.5 \text{ t CO}_2 \text{ ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$. In CARAT the sequestration in the soil

accounted for $0.027 \text{ t CO}_2 \text{ ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$, suggesting either a difference in inputs or algorithms between the models. One difference that was not yet accounted for was the model runtime (standard 30 years for CARAT, in this case 24 years for BodemCoolstof Tool) though it is unlikely that the difference of 6 years runtime would explain the large variation in the results.

It can be concluded that further integration and harmonisation of agroforestry carbon models would be beneficial for the coherence of model results. The comparison showed that CARAT seems superior for modelling biomass C whilst the BodemCoolstof Tool seems superior for modelling soil C. Tool developers could learn from the best-practices from each other's models. Lastly, sensitivity analysis is a useful method to pinpoint important values that require further examination. Possibly a prompt could be given that warns the user about which input values have particularly high impact on simulation results.

3.8. United Kingdom

3.8.1. Introduction

The UK Living Lab used a different location for the greenhouse gas calculation (a real farm) from that used for soil health (a park belonging to the Bedfordshire city council), so that it was possible to complete a greenhouse gas assessment at a farm scale. The UK case study farm is Hope Farm located in Knapwell, Cambridgeshire in Eastern England. It is a 181 ha commercially managed arable farm owned by the Royal Society for the Protection of Birds (RSPB) (Figure 75). The total area of the farm is 181 comprising 151 ha cultivated area, and 5 ha of grass, and 25 ha of non-cropping (Table 73).

Figure 75. Aerial view of farm boundary (red) and agroforestry field (yellow) at Hope Farm, Cambridgeshire, UK.

Table 73. Total area of farm and outputs at Hope Farm.

Land cover	Typical area (ha)	Yield (t)
Wheat	25.0	192
Barley	73.2	261
Field beans and dry peas	28.4	29
Oilseed rape	22.0	70
Other cultivated	2.4	
Grass	5.0	
Hedgerows (assume 2 m)	3.0	
Wood and trees	5.0	
Other non-cropped	17.0	
Total	181.0	1034

Within the 181 ha of the farm, one 11 ha field (labelled Field 6) was allocated to silvoarable agroforestry with the objective of increasing farm biodiversity and diversifying farm outputs (Figure 76). The silvoarable system, established by staff and volunteers, is an alley-cropping system using three types of trees (Figure 76), in total 1,000 trees. There were apple trees of 13 varieties, cobnut trees of three varieties, and broadleaf shelter belt trees of six species to provide a wind break, consisting of field maple, small leaved lime, hornbeam, wild cherry, hawthorn, and common alder.

Figure 76. Layout of the silvoarable agroforestry system at Hope Farm in Field 6.

In determining a sequestration rate for the apple trees in the agroforestry field, a significant decision was to determine the area allocated to the apple trees. In total 200 apple trees were planted at a spacing of 5.38 m in 6 m wide rows with 24 m wide cropped alleys. In some apple agroforestry systems, the trees are planted in a 3 m row, but at Hope Farm the decision was taken to plant the trees in a 6 m row which could be considered as comprising a 3 m buffer strip for vehicle access and a 3 m tree row. On this basis the area of apple trees was calculated to be 0.32 ha (Table 74). Similar calculations were completed for the hazel and shelterbelt system.

Table 74. Calculation of the area allocated to apple, cobnuts, and shelterbelt trees within the 11 ha field.

Description	Number of trees	Tree spacing	Tree density (trees ha ⁻¹)	Treed area assuming tree row of 3 m (ha)	Assumed area of adjacent 3 m buffer strip (ha)
Apple	200	5.38 m x 30 m	62	0.32	0.32
Hazel	600	1.82 m x 30 m	183	0.32	0.32
Mixed-broadleaf	200	2.73 m x 30 m	122	0.16	0.16
Total	1000			0.80	0.80

3.8.2. CARAT tool

At Hope Farm, CARAT was used to model the impact of the three different silvoarable systems planted within Field 6. The tree species planted comprise apple tree, hazel tree and a mix of broadleaf trees, planted in an alley cropping system at 62 trees ha⁻¹ (30 m x 5.38 m), 183 trees ha⁻¹ (30 m x 1.82 m) and 122 trees ha⁻¹ (30 m x 2.73 m) (Table 75).

Table 75. Calculation of the area allocated to apple, cobnuts, and shelterbelt trees within the 11 ha field.

Description	Number of trees	Tree spacing	Tree density (trees ha ⁻¹)	Treed area assuming tree row of 3 m (ha)	Assumed area of adjacent 3 m buffer strip (ha)
Apple	200	5.38 m x 30 m	62	0.32	0.32
Hazel	600	1.82 m x 30 m	183	0.32	0.32
Mixed-broadleaf	200	2.73 m x 30 m	122	0.16	0.16
Total	1000			0.80	0.80

Although the field size is about 11 ha, CARAT has been designed to calculate the sequestration for an area up to one hectare. The other inputs for the analysis, primarily to parameterise the RothC model was the level of clay in the soil, the bulk density, the depth to the plough layer and the initial soil organic carbon content (Table 76). CARAT has some initial tree species selection options which included apple and hazel, and 'standard tree' was chosen to represent the mixed broadleaf shelterbelt.

Table 76. Input data for the carbon sequestration assessment of the agroforestry trial at Hope Farm.

Description	Value
Field dimensions	100 m x 100 m
Clay percentage	36 %
Bulk density	1.19 g cm ⁻³
Depth of plough layer	0.3 m
Initial soil organic content	2.25 %
Species for apple trees	<i>Malus domestica</i>
Selected species for hazel	<i>Corylus avellana</i>
Selected tree type for shelterbelt	Standard tree

In order to determine the separate effects of the apple, hazel, and shelterbelt system, a maximum field size of 1 hectare was selected and an arrangement of trees was assumed which matched a 30 m inter-row spacing, and which resulted in the appropriate tree density (Table 3). For all three simulations, trees were added manually using the 'add individual trees' function, at a spacing as close as possible to the reality (Figure 77).

a) Apple

b) Hazel

c) Shelterbelt

Figure 77. The layout of the a) apple, b) hazel, and c) shelterbelt trees were configured with the CARAT tool for an area of one hectare.

Results

The CARAT tool produces the results in terms of a figure (Figure 78) and a table (Table 77) which describe the modelled carbon accumulation in the biomass of the trees and a change in soil organic carbon over 30 years. The density and default parameters for the selected tree systems resulted in a substantially higher modelled accumulation of tree biomass by the hazel and shelterbelt system after 30 years (22.9 and 19.5 t C ha⁻¹) than in the apple system (7.89 t C ha⁻¹). The predicted increases in soil organic carbon were proportional to the increase in tree biomass with the greatest positive change occurring in the hazel system and the least in the apple system.

The model also predicted the predicted change in type of carbon with each year from planting over a 30 year period. The results for the hazel system are illustrated in Figure 79, and show that C fractions with distance from the hazel in terms of decomposable plant material (DPM), resistant plant material (RPM), humified organic matter (HUM), microbial biomass (BIO) and inert organic matter (IOM) (Coleman et al., 2024). The addition of the trees was predicted to increase the level of organic matter in the form of resistant plant material, with a greater increase observed at a distance of 2 m from the trees compared to a distance of over 10 m (Figure 79).

Figure 78. Modelled carbon accumulation in the tree biomass and the soil organic carbon in the a) apple, b) hazel, and c) shelterbelt silvoarable system using CARAT.

Table 77. Modelled carbon accumulation in soil organic carbon (SOC) and biomass carbon (C) in the apple, hazel, and shelterbelt system for a period of 30 years.

Age (years)	Apple		Hazel		Shelterbelt	
	Increase in SOC (t C ha ⁻¹)	Increase in biomass C (t C ha ⁻¹)	Increase in SOC (t C ha ⁻¹)	Increase in biomass C (t C ha ⁻¹)	Increase in SOC (t C ha ⁻¹)	Increase in biomass C (t C ha ⁻¹)
1	0.03	0.76	0.14	2.21	0.05	3.23
5	0.09	1.07	0.48	3.13	0.20	4.02
10	0.16	1.64	0.86	4.78	0.44	5.5
15	0.23	2.49	1.22	7.22	0.73	7.61
20	0.34	3.71	1.80	10.77	1.23	10.48
25	0.44	5.45	2.37	15.84	1.78	14.34
30	0.58	7.89	3.12	22.92	2.53	19.52

Figure 79. Change in decomposable and resistant plant material (DPM, RPM), humified organic matter (HUM), microbial biomass (BIO) and inert organic matter (IOM)) within the hazel system.

The CARAT tool also provides a spatial representation of the distribution of leaf fall and how this modifies the soil organic matter (Figure 80). Again the level of leaf fall depends on the distance from the tree, with a predicted accumulation of about 1 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ next to the tree to minimal levels in the middle of the row. In turn, the leaf fall results in higher predicted soil organic carbon increases next to the tree of less than 50 g C m⁻² (which is equivalent to 0.5 t C ha⁻¹) over the 30 year period.

Figure 80. Modelled spatial distribution of leaf fall (kg C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹) for the hazel system and the resulting modelled change in soil organic content at the end of 30 years (g C m⁻²).

Conversion of results

Although the maximum area that can be modelled by the CARAT model is 1 ha, this is sufficient to examine the effect of the silvoarable agroforestry systems at Hope Farm. If the agroforestry system is larger than 1 ha, then the system can be scaled up accordingly. Using the modelled changes in carbon calculation, it was possible to estimate the mean level of carbon sequestration in units of t CO₂e ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹, with values ranging from 1.04 t CO₂e ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ for the apple system to 2.70 t CO₂e ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ for the broadleaf shelterbelt, and 3.18 t CO₂e ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ for the hazel system (Table 78).

Table 78. Conversion of the CARAT results to carbon dioxide equivalents per year.

	Maximum accumulation after 30 years		Mean accumulation
	(t C ha ⁻¹)	(t CO ₂ ha ⁻¹)	(t CO ₂ e ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹)
Apple	8.47	31.1	1.04
Hazel	26.04	94.5	3.18
Broadleaf shelterbelt	22.05	80.8	2.70

3.8.3. Farm Carbon Calculator

Assumptions and data entry for emissions

The assumed boundary of the report was “to the farm gate” but including onwards distribution to destination to the point of sale as requested by the farmer. The method of accounting for inventory items was to assume 100% depreciation in the year of acquisition. Sources of emissions include fuels, materials, and inventory (Table 79) and crops, inputs, waste disposal, distribution and processing (Table 80). Data for Hope Farm were provided by the staff at Hope Farm for the calendar year of 2022. Although there is an option to include changes in soil carbon based on field measurements, for the purposes of this exercise, changes in soil carbon were not included. Within the Farm Carbon Toolkit there is also a column which includes a statement of the level of confidence of a given value in terms of ‘low’, ‘medium’ and ‘high’.

Table 79. Summary table for fuels, materials, inventory, and inputs for use in Farm Carbon Toolkit.

Description		Usage	Emissions (t CO ₂ e yr ⁻¹)	Confidence
Fuels				
Diesel	Red diesel (gas oil)	24,205 L	82.08	High
	Road diesel	1244 L	3.94	High
Electricity	Specific renewable tariff	5,441 kWh	0.90	High
Liquid fuels	Heating oil	1,000 L	3.07	-
Sub-total	Sub-total		89.99	
Materials				
Building materials	Clay bricks	75 bricks	0.03	High
	General cement by bags	1 25 kg bags	0.02	High
	General concrete	28 tonnes	3.00	High
Fence posts	Pine/Spruce posts (4ft 6in)	1000 posts	0.50	High
	Pine/Spruce posts (4ft 6in)	30 posts	0.03	High
	Pine/Spruce posts (5ft 6in)	500 posts	0.62	High
	Pine/Spruce posts (8ft)	102 posts	0.37	High
Horticultural packaging	Cardboard boxes	2 kg	0.00	High
	Paper bags	4 kg	0.01	High
	Polythene bags	2 kg	0.01	High
Pipes	PVC 75mm diameter	3,013 m	7.33	High
	PVC 90mm diameter	1,613 m	5.53	High
Roads & tracks	Concrete road by area	1,512 m ²	116.42	High
Tyres	Rubber tyres by weight	20 kg	0.06	Medium
Wood	Pine/Spruce by volume			
Sub-total			133.93	
Inventory				
Vehicles	£29,000 on new truck		20.88	High
Sub-total			20.88	

Table 80. Assumed values for data inputs for inputs, crops, livestock, waste disposal, and distribution.

Description		Weight harvested	Emissions (t CO ₂ e yr ⁻¹)	Confidence
Inputs				
Fertiliser	Custom blend solid fertiliser	64 t	95.33	Medium

Fungicides	Custodia	15 L	0.14	-
	Prozaro	16 L	0.12	-
Generic spray products	Fungicide	18 kg a.i.	0.53	Medium
	Growth Regulator	11 kg a.i.	0.21	Medium
	Herbicide	333 kg a.i.	8.88	Medium
	Molluscicide	6 kg a.i.	0.07	Medium
Growth reg'tor	Canopy	39 L	0.26	
Herbicides	Astrokerb	37 L	0.50	
	Easel	133 kg	2.66	
Sub-total			108.70	
a.i.: active ingredient				
Crops				
Wheat	Most wheat straw left in field	192 t harvested	9.76	Low
Barley	Wholecrop or most of the barley straw removed	261 t harvested	8.39	Low
Cattle FYM	Cattle FYM: spread on cropland over rest of year	50 t	1.16	Low
Field beans and dried peas	Most of the pea and bean residues left in field	29 t harvested	1.75	Low
Oilseed rape	Most of the oil seed rape residues left in field	70 t harvested	12.36	Low
Old organic fertility options	Green Waste Compost - Autumn Application	900 t (fresh wt)	26.09	Low
Poultry manure	Poultry FYM (40% DM): Spread in Autumn	144 t	23.68	Low
Sub-total			83.17	
Livestock				
Horses	Horses	3 head	2.00	Low
Ewes	Ewes	81 head	18.79	Low
Sub-total			20.78	
Waste disposal				
Paper and board	Board - recycled	0 t	0.00	Medium
	Paper - recycles	0 t	0.00	Medium
Plastics	Average plastics - recycled	2 t	0.03	na
Refuse	Commercial waste - landfill	1 t	0.68	na
	Organic food waste - composting	2 t	0.02	na
Sub-total			0.73	
Distribution				
Contracted	Lorry (3.5 - 33 t)	336 miles	23.64	Medium
Sub-total			23.64	

Assumptions for data entry for carbon sequestration

Considering Hope Farm as a whole, the three assumed sources for carbon sequestration were related to on-farm involvement in agri-environment schemes, existing woodland and hedges, and the tree component of the new agroforestry system in Field 6. As previously indicated, although it is possible

to estimate changes in soil carbon on the basis of two field measurements, such values were not included in the analysis.

Agri-environment schemes

In England, the government offers payments for a number of agri-environment measures which form part of the mid and higher tiers of the Countryside Stewardship scheme, which was launched in 2015 and continued to 2024. The Countryside Stewardship Scheme was available in mid- and higher levels with specified levels for payments such as “AB1 nectar flower mix”, which paid £739 per hectare (UK Government, 2023). There are a range of schemes that farmers can enter, and different schemes have different codes (UK Government, 2025a, 2025b). The managers at Hope Farm have implemented about 24 hectares of such measures. In the Farm Carbon Toolkit, an estimate of the reduction in greenhouse gas emissions is estimated which equates to 75 t CO₂e yr⁻¹ (Table 9), equivalent to a mean of about 3.2 t CO₂e ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ (Table 81).

Table 81. Calculations of the on-farm carbon sequestration through designated agri-environment measures in England, by hedgerows and woodland, and in the silvoarable agroforestry system.

Description	Area	Emissions (t CO ₂ e yr ⁻¹)	Confidence
Agri-environment measures			
AB1 Nectar flower mix ^a	2 ha	-8.18	na
AB11 Cultivated areas for arable plants ^a	1 ha	-2.60	na
AB5 Nesting plots for lapwing ^a	2 ha	-5.41	na
AB9 Winter bird food ^a	4 ha	-21.06	na
SW1 4-6 m buffer strip on cultivated land ^a	2 ha	-9.61	na
AB8 Flower rich margins and plots ^b	2 ha	-5.72	na
BE3 Management of hedgerows ^c	6 ha	-21.88	na
GS2 Permanent grassland with very low inputs	5 ha	-1.75	na
Sub-total	~24 ha	-76.21	
Woodland and hedgerows			
Hedgerows (large growth with trees)	8,356 m	-93.92	Low
Managed hedgerow planted more than 15 years ago	5,239 m	-13.60	Low
Mixed woodland by age	2 ha	-15.27	Medium
Sub-total		-122.79	
Agroforestry tree area			
Top Fruit (average)	0.32 ha	-1.06	Low
Nuts	0.32 ha	-1.47	Low
Deciduous woodland by age	0.16 ha	-0.33	Medium
Sub-total	0.80 ha	-2.86	
Total		-201.86	

^a: assuming a winter wheat baseline

^b: assuming a temporary grassland silage baseline

^c: assuming a hedge (2 sides) baseline

^d: assuming a semi-improved grassland – lowland sheep baseline

Woodland and hedges

The Farm Carbon Calculator also provides estimates of the carbon sequestration rates by hedges and woodlands. The length of hedges on Hope Farm has been calculated as 8,356 m of hedgerows with

'large growth with trees' and 5,239 m identified as 'managed hedgerow planted more than 15 years ago'. In the Farm Carbon Calculator, Parker et al. (2025) report that the sequestration factor for **managed** hedgerows are based on data described by Drexler et al. (2023) and Biffi et al. (2022, 2023). Although Drexler et al. (2023) provides data on the biomass of hedgerows, they do not quote an annual sequestration value. Biffi et al. (2022), quote a soil organic carbon sequestration rate beneath 37 year old hedgerows of $1.48 \text{ t C ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ in the top 50 cm of soil, and an average width of 1.70 m for hedges more than 10 years old. Biffi et al. (2023) quote an accumulation of biomass carbon of $0.43 \text{ t C ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ for hedges between 13 and 40 years old. On this basis, the 5329 m length x 1.70 m x $0.191 \text{ kg C m}^{-2}$ would sequester 1.73 t C yr^{-1} , which would be equivalent to $6.34 \text{ t CO}_2 \text{ yr}^{-1}$. This compares with a calculated value from the calculator of $13.60 \text{ t CO}_2 \text{ yr}^{-1}$ (Table 81). By contrast, Biffi et al. (2023) quote a biomass sequestration of $2.26 \text{ t C ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ at the age of 12 years. On this basis, the 5328 m length would sequester $13.60 \text{ t CO}_2 \text{ yr}^{-1}$. Hence it seems that the carbon sequestration rate may be based on the sequestration rate of a hedge aged between 6 and 12 years.

Parker et al. (2025) report that the sequestration factor for hedgerows defined as 'large growth with trees' is derived from Falloon et al. (2004), Crossland (2015) and Taylor et al. (2012). Crossland (2015) reported carbon sequestration values for unmanaged blackthorn, hazel, and hawthorn hedges ranging from 1.1 t C km^{-1} to 3.66 t C km^{-1} . Hence the 8356 m of unmanaged hedge could be sequestering $9.2\text{-}30.6 \text{ t C yr}^{-1}$ or $33.7\text{-}112.1 \text{ t CO}_2 \text{ yr}^{-1}$. The Farm Carbon Calculator calculated a sequestration of $93.9 \text{ t CO}_2 \text{ yr}^{-1}$ (Table 81) which is near the top of the range.

Apple trees

The sequestration rate for apple trees in the Farm Carbon Calculator is derived from perennial crops in New Zealand (McNally and Gentile, 2021, who quote Kerckhoffs and Reid, 2007). The mature weight for apple trees is calculated as 18 t C ha^{-1} . Assuming that this is achieved over 20 years, then the sequestration rate is 0.9 t C ha^{-1} , which equates to $3.30 \text{ t CO}_2 \text{ ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$. Hence the assumed apple area of 0.32 ha results in the prediction of a biomass sequestration rate of $1.06 \text{ t CO}_2 \text{ e yr}^{-1}$ (Table 81). This is approximately double a global default rate of $0.42 \text{ t C ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ ($1.54 \text{ t CO}_2 \text{ ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$) quoted for apple by Ogle et al. (2019) for the Intergovernmental Panel for Climate Change. This shows the variability models can incorporate depending on the data source used for the calculations.

Cobnuts

Within the agroforestry system, 600 cobnut plants were established at a spacing of 1.82 m within 6 m vegetation rows separated by 24 alleys. Assuming a tree row of 3 m and a buffer strip of 3 m, this would equate to an area of trees of 0.32 ha (Table 75). Assuming this area, the Farm Carbon Calculator estimates a sequestration rate of $1.47 \text{ t CO}_2 \text{ yr}^{-1}$ (Table 81), which equates to $4.59 \text{ t CO}_2 \text{ ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$. This is equivalent to a tree species with a carbon biomass of 25 t C ha^{-1} after 20 years. The source of this value is not immediately obvious, as the stated weight of walnut trees is 37.5 t C ha^{-1} .

Broadleaf shelterbelt

The Farm Carbon Calculator estimates that the 0.16 ha of shelterbelt trees sequester the equivalent of $0.33 \text{ t CO}_2 \text{ yr}^{-1}$ (Table 81), which would equate to a value of $2.05 \text{ t CO}_2 \text{ ha}^{-1}$. Parker et al (2025), indicate that this value is derived from the Woodland Carbon Code (2024). For example, the Woodland Carbon Code estimates that Beech type trees from an unthinned stand at a plant spacing of 2.5 m x 2.5 m with a yield class of 4 would result in a mean sequestration to biomass over 200 years of $5.07 \text{ t CO}_2 \text{ ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ if unthinned or $2.86 \text{ t CO}_2 \text{ ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ if thinned. By contrast, the predicted

sequestration rate of Beech trees, with a yield class of 4, in the first five years after planting is only 0.12 t CO₂ ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹. Hence there is substantial scope for different values depending on particular assumptions made.

Results

The Farm Carbon Calculator allows the assessment of the emissions in terms of Scopes 1, 2, and 3 and “outside of scope”. It also distinguishes between emissions in the form of carbon dioxide, methane, and nitrous oxide (Table 82). It is also possible to present the results in terms of the balance between emissions and sequestration (Figure 81).

Table 82. Summary of farm-level emissions at Hope Farm in terms scope, and in terms of proportion derived from carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄) and nitrous oxide (N₂O).

	Emissions by scope (t CO ₂ e)				Emissions by GHG (t CO ₂ e)				
	Scope 1	Scope 2	Scope 3	Outside of scope	Only CO ₂ e available	CO ₂	CH ₄	N ₂ O	Total (t CO ₂ e)
Fuel	72.43	0.39	16.73	0.44	16.70	71.97	0.08	0.80	89.99
Materials	0.00	0.00	133.93	0.00	133.93	0.00	0.00	0.00	133.93
Inventory	0.00	0.00	20.88	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	20.88
Crops	83.17	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	83.17	83.17
Inputs	46.38	0.00	62.32	0.00	62.32	0.00	0.00	46.38	108.70
Livestock	20.78	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	17.97	2.81	20.78
Waste disposal	0.00	0.00	0.73	0.00	0.73	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.73
Distribution	0.00	0.00	23.64	0.00	4.54	18.78	0.00	0.33	23.64
Total	222.76	0.39	258.24	0.44	218.22	90.75	18.05	133.49	481.83

Figure 81. Gross emissions and sequestration rates (expressed as negative values) and the net level of calculated greenhouse gas emissions from Hope Farm. At a farm scale, the calculated level of sequestration from the 0.80 ha of agroforestry trees is too small to be visible.

When the level of emissions are divided by the 181 ha of the farm, the total level of emissions was overall 2.67 t CO₂e ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹, primarily comprised of 1.26 t CO₂e ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ of Scope 1 emissions and 1.43 t CO₂e ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ of Scope 3 emissions. Overall, the level of sequestration was 1.11 t CO₂e ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹, primarily derived from 0.42 t CO₂e ha⁻¹ from the agri-environment schemes and 0.68 t CO₂e ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ from the existing hedgerows and woodland. The effect of 0.80 ha of the agroforestry trees was minimal. The overall net effect was a net emission of 1.57 t CO₂e ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹. One of the outputs of the

Farm Carbon Calculator is to express the mean value per hectare relative to the 'mean average value for this selection', which can provide an initial basis for discussion (Figure 82).

Figure 82. The Farm Carbon Calculator provides a graphical output which includes the following commentary: “Your value for total emissions per ha is 1.6 t CO₂e ha⁻¹, which is below the median average value for this section and it is within the lowest 40% of the selected data”

3.8.4. *Open Farm Carbon Tracker*

The Open Farm Carbon Tracker (OFCT) is an open source tool for diagnosis of farm scale greenhouse gas fluxes and modelling of potential future greenhouse gas fluxes under different scenarios (Open Farm Tracker, 2026), which has been partially developed as part of the DigitAF project (European Commission, 2024). In selected countries (Austria, Denmark, Finland, France and the Netherlands), it is possible to select fields from publicly available datasets of the land parcel identification system (LPIS). The calculated area of Field 6 at Hope Farm was calculated by Open Farm Tracker to be 11.96 ha. Outside of those five countries, it is possible to outline and save the area of a specific field (Figure 83). Once a field is selected it is possible to specify specific crops and trees that can be grown in that field which are described at present in the Danish language (Table 83).

Figure 83. The first stage is to create an image of the field in Open Farm Carbon Tracker.

Table 83. Crop names used in the Denmark (2023) dataset in Open Farm Carbon Tracker.

No.	Land use	Crop	ID	Crop name in Danish
1	Arable	Spring barley	1	Vårbyg
10	Arable	Winter barley	10	Vinterbyg
11	Arable	Winter wheat	11	Vinterhvede
19	Arable	Spring Oilseed Rape	21	Vårraps
20	Arable	Winter Oilseed Rape	22	Vinterraps
27	Arable	Broad bean	31	Hestebønner
40	Arable	Winter oat	57	Vinterhavre
197	Agroforestry	Agroforestry w. permanent grass	482	Skovlandbrug med permanent græs
198	Agroforestry	Agroforestry w. grass	483	Skovlandbrug med græs i omdrift
199	Agroforestry	Agroforestry w. arable crop	484	Skovlandbrug med omdriftsafgrøder
200	Agroforestry	Agroforestry w. permanent crop	485	Skovlandbrug med permanente afgrøder
205	Perm. crops	Common hazel (<i>Corylus avellana</i>)	490	Hassel, træ (<i>Corylus avellana</i>)
240	Perm. crops	Apple	528	Æbler
249	Perm. crops	English walnut	537	Valnød (almindelig)
250	Perm. crops	Sweet chestnut	538	Kastanje (ægte)
280	Afforestation	Afforestation on agricultural land	587	Skovrejsning på tidl. landbrugsjord 3
283	Forestry	Short rotation coppice	591	Lavskov
284	Forestry	Willow	592	Pil
285	Forestry	Poplar	593	Poppel (0-100 andre træer pr. ha)
286	Forestry	Alder	594	El

The OFCT allows an assessment of the effect of different proportions of tree cover on the level of emissions within a stated area. For Field 6 at Hope Farm, Open Farm Tracker was run assuming an 11 year cycle of continuous wheat crop with different proportions of the field allocated to an apple crop. The model then uses that information to derive a level of greenhouse gas emissions or sequestration associated with that land cover for the year of planting and for subsequent 10 years.

It is also possible to enter data into the OFCT to account for other sources of greenhouse gas emissions not directly associated with land use. For example a fuel use of 1607 Litres and 330 kWh was assumed for the 11.61 ha, which was used to derive an energy-related greenhouse gas emission which was equivalent to 0.37 t CO₂e ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹, irrespective of whether the field was fully planted to wheat or trees. In the year of planting, higher levels of emissions were linearly associated with high proportions of trees (Table 84, Figure 84). For the year after planting, higher levels of tree cover were linearly related to higher levels of predicted sequestration. The mean rate of sequestration was assumed to be constant for each of the years after planting between years 2 and 11 (Table 84). The results assuming the tree species was hazel resulted in the same results as for apple.

Table 84. Predicted levels of greenhouse gas emissions from energy and land use for Field 6 using the OFCT for different proportions of the field allocated to wheat and apples.

Year	Land use (t CO ₂ e ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹)							
	Fuel use	Wheat Apples	100% 0%	80% 20%	60% 40%	40% 60%	20% 80%	0% 100%
1	0.37	2.20	3.76	5.32	6.88	8.44	10.00	
2	0.37	2.20	-1.24	-4.68	-8.12	-11.56	-15.00	
3	0.37	2.20	-1.24	-4.68	-8.12	-11.56	-15.00	
4	0.37	2.20	-1.24	-4.68	-8.12	-11.56	-15.00	
5	0.37	2.20	-1.24	-4.68	-8.12	-11.56	-15.00	
6	0.37	2.20	-1.24	-4.68	-8.12	-11.56	-15.00	
7	0.37	2.20	-1.24	-4.68	-8.12	-11.56	-15.00	
8	0.37	2.20	-1.24	-4.68	-8.12	-11.56	-15.00	
9	0.37	2.20	-1.24	-4.68	-8.12	-11.56	-15.00	
10	0.37	2.20	-1.24	-4.68	-8.12	-11.56	-15.00	
11	0.37	2.20	-1.24	-4.68	-8.12	-11.56	-15.00	
Total	4.11	24.20	-8.64	-41.48	-74.32	107.16	-140.00	

Figure 84. Result from the OFCT of predicted level of emissions of greenhouse gases with different proportions of the planting of apple trees relative to continuous production of winter wheat.

3.8.5. Discussion

Comparison of methods

The three tools have different methods of estimating greenhouse gas emissions. The CARAT tool which was used to determine the carbon sequestration rates related to trees in a single field predicted a mean sequestration of apples at a spacing of 30 m x 5.26 m (62 trees per hectare) of 1.04 t CO₂e ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ (Table 85). The Farm Carbon Toolkit is designed for determining the level of greenhouse gases for a whole farm, but it does include a component that estimates the sequestration related to agri-environment schemes, hedgerows and woodlands, and agroforestry systems. The Farm Carbon Calculator estimated a mean net level of greenhouse gas emissions across the whole farm of 1.50 t CO₂e ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹, which is of a similar magnitude to the value of 2.20 t CO₂e ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ imputed for winter wheat in the OFCT (Table 85). The calculated sequestration rate of the apple trees in the Farm Carbon Calculator depended heavily on the assumed area of allocated to the apple trees. If the 6 m row was considered as comprising 3 m of apple trees and 3 m of buffer strip, the annual biomass sequestration equates to 0.33 t CO₂e per hectare of system, whereas if it was assumed to comprise a 6 m row of apples, then the predicted annual sequestration in the tree biomass rises to 0.66 t CO₂e per hectare of system. This is similar to the value of 0.78 t CO₂e ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ assumed by the OFCT assuming that 20%

of the area was allocated to apples and 80% to wheat. However, the assumed sequestration value for 100% apple of 12.72 t CO₂e ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ using the OFCT was substantially greater than the value of 3.30 t CO₂e ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ assumed in the Farm Carbon Calculator.

Table 85. Comparison of the predicted emissions using the three tools, with negative value (indicated in red) indicating net sequestration.

	Predicted emissions (t CO ₂ e ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹)		
	CARAT (30 years)	Farm Carbon Toolkit (single year)	Open Farm Tracker (11 years)
Whole farm		About 1.50	
0% apple; 100% wheat			2.20
10% apple (tree only)		-0.33	
20% apple (tree only)		-0.66	
62 apple trees per hectare (tree and soil)	-1.04		
20% apple; 80 % wheat			-0.78
100% apple		-3.30	-12.72

3.9. Overall discussion across sites

The cross-site assessment of the carbon and greenhouse gas tools using CARAT, the Farm Carbon Calculator (FCC), the Open Farm Carbon Tracker (OFCT), and BodemCoolstof (CoolStof), shows significant differences in modelling approaches, usability, transparency, and readiness for carbon farming schemes. While agroforestry is consistently predicted to improve soil carbon, biomass accumulation, and GHG performance across the examined DigitAF Living Lab farms in Czechia, Finland, Germany, Italy, the Netherlands, and the United Kingdom, it remains challenging to quantify these benefits in a robust and standardised way. This section discusses the key findings and outlines a pathway for improving agroforestry integration into carbon calculators.

Integrating agroforestry in farm carbon and greenhouse gas calculators

Each of the examined tools were designed with a specific purpose in mind. If the tools result in different answers, then one potential reason is that they were designed to answer different questions. CARAT was specifically designed to determine the predicted sequestration in biomass and in the soil for silvoarable agroforestry systems, and the basis of the calculations have been published (Vanneste et al., 2025). The Farm Carbon Calculator was designed for use at a farm level to identify the main factors determining greenhouse gas emissions and carbon sequestration. The basis for the calculation are described by Parker et al. (2025). Although there are plans to enhance the agroforestry components within the tool, the assessment of sequestration rates are primarily based on look-up tables based on woodland stands of different species of different age classes. The Open Farm Carbon Tracker is a new tool which has the useful feature where the user can use aerial photographs to identify fields and potentially make use of the land parcel identification system. Within initial fields, the tool allows the assessment of the effect of different proportions of tree cover and cropping on greenhouse gas emissions. The calculations for the tree sequestration are relatively simple comprising a fixed rate of sequestration irrespective of the age of the tree from the first year after planting. The BodemCoolstof Tool does not include the effect of trees, but it is a tool for determining the effect of, for example, temperature and rainfall, on predicted rates of soil greenhouse gas emissions or net sequestration. Therefore, these tools differ in the elements that are included in the system, as well as the available options. Table 86 synthesizes the main similarities and differences between these tools.

Table 86. Main similarities and differences between carbon assessment tools for agroforestry

Tool	System boundary	GHG taken into account	Carbon pools (soil, above-ground biomass, belowground biomass...) and emission	Time scale (years)	Type of agroforestry system (silvoarable, silvopastoral, alley cropping, SRC, etc...)	Specific limits highlighted in the LL
CARAT	1 field or 1 hectare	CO ₂	Soil, overall tree biomass	30	Silvoarable, alley cropping	Specific for Belgium, limited number of tree species
Farm Carbon Calculator	Farm	CO ₂	Soil, overall tree and shrub biomass, GHG emissions	1	Hedgerows, or areas with low to high tree density	Specific for UK, limited agroforestry integration
Open Farm carbon Tracker	Farm	CO ₂	Tree and shrub biomass, GHG emissions	from 1 to 100+	Depends on agroforestry types available in LPIS	LPIS codes currently only for Denmark
BodemCoolS toff	Field	CO ₂	Soil carbon loss and sequestration	up to year 2050	none	Specific for the Netherlands, no trees included

Improving the usability of carbon tools for farmers

The creation and development of carbon sequestration and greenhouse gas assessment tools is a developing field and it is important to remember that the results are assessments rather than measurements. Typically one common area of feedback when using models related to agroforestry is that users request for a specific tree species to be added. Whilst this may be appropriate in some cases, in many situations the limitation is more likely to be the availability of tree growth, crop yield, and soil carbon content data which can be used to inform the look-up tables or predictions of growth rates. Hence on recommendation is the collation of tree growth libraries for specific regions so that the tools would give a more realistic results about what can be expected in a specific region. Hence one of the activities within the DigitAF project has been to promote the availability of data to inform model development.

Another important improvement would be to allow farmers to select the farm and/or plots in LPIS systems for automatic input from public databases. For instance, CARAT allows field selection using the LPIS database. This is currently only available for Belgium, adding LPIS datasets for more countries would streamline field mapping and improve spatial accuracy. Similarly, the Open Farm Carbon Tracker already includes the feature to select fields via the LPIS database for Austria, Denmark, Finland, France and the Netherlands. Including current crop codes as part of the baseline dataset would further facilitate accurate carbon calculations and make the tool use more efficient for farmers.

Improving tool usability for carbon farming schemes

Agroforestry systems are, in principle, eligible for EU carbon farming certification under the Carbon Removal Certification Framework (CRCF), which recognises a variety of agricultural practices that enhance carbon sequestration (European Union, 2024). However, gaining access to these schemes is contingent upon the ability to accurately quantify and verify carbon removals, demanding robust

methodologies for Monitoring, Reporting and Verification (MRV). This means farmers must demonstrate, with reliable data, the carbon benefits of their agroforestry practices to meet certification standards. The tools examined in this report could be candidates for MRV tools: farmers wishing to enter carbon farming schemes could use them to assess storage potential of their new agroforestry systems.

However, there are several key difficulties that agroforestry farmers face when attempting to use these tools:

- **System complexity:** Agroforestry systems integrate trees, crops, and/or livestock, resulting in intricate multi-layered biomass and soil carbon interactions. This complexity makes modelling and prediction far more challenging compared to conventional monoculture systems.
- **Numerous combinations:** There are countless possible combinations of tree and crop species, each with distinct growth rates, root structures, and carbon allocation profiles. Even within a single species, variations in density and spatial arrangement can have unpredictable, non-linear impacts on carbon sequestration.
- **Data limitations:** The long-term nature of agroforestry means field measurements must span many years to provide robust model validation, but the lack of extensive long-term agroforestry experiments makes it difficult to generate the necessary data.
- **Transparency:** One important feedback from the stakeholders in Italy and Finland was that it was difficult or not possible at all to see where the data comes from and how the results were calculated. Adding a clear references to data sources, methodologies and calculation methods would increase the transparency of the tools and also increases trust by the stakeholders. In addition, when data sources and methodologies are available, other researchers working in the same field can more easily contribute when updated data or improved methodologies become available.

One significant challenge for agroforestry is the CRCF's stringent minimum model accuracy requirement: at least 90% of observed values must be captured within the model's 90% confidence interval. This high statistical standard is designed to ensure genuine environmental integrity and avoid over-crediting, which could result in financial penalties or the need to return credits if targets are not met. For agroforestry practitioners, this means tools must not only be sophisticated but also robust which is a demanding expectation given the complexity of these systems. Our findings indicate that although most tools require similar input data, the results can vary substantially between tools for the same farm. This can be due to differences in the underlying assumptions, the boundary for the systems being considered (what is or is not included), the biophysical models, all of which affect the accuracy and consistency of output. This means that they are not yet ready to be used in MRV for carbon farming.

To improve compatibility with the monitoring, verification and reporting requirements central to carbon farming schemes, the European Agroforestry Federation has recommended incorporating remote sensing and geospatial data, as well as integrating the Land Parcel Identification System (LPIS) into administrative systems (IACS)(Lawson et al., 2026). The same enhancements could in principle be integrated in farm carbon and GHG calculators too. These enhancements could allow for more accurate mapping of agroforestry elements and facilitate reliable tracking of carbon changes at the field level. Further, broadening the definitions of agroforestry within tools to encompass not only existing crops and trees but also landscape features and forests would increase the accuracy and

inclusiveness of carbon assessments. This would help ensure that all relevant carbon sinks within a farming landscape are recognised and measured.

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